

DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATIONS OF AN ANALYZER FOR AIRBORNE NON-VOLATILE AEROSOL COMPOUNDS

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**Caminante, no hay camino,
Se hace camino al andar.**

ANTONIO MACHADO

ENTWICKLUNG UND ANWENDUNG EINES ANALYSATORS ZUR BESTIMMUNG LUFTGETRAGENER, NICHTFLÜCHTIGER AEROSOLBESTANDTEILE

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Einleitung und Motivation

Aerosole spielen in vielfältigen atmosphärischen Prozessen eine wesentliche Rolle und können dabei das Klima der Erde nachhaltig beeinflussen. Der Begriff des atmosphärischen Aerosols umfaßt alle sich in der Luft befindlichen flüssigen und festen Partikel, die in ihrer Größe zwischen wenigen Nanometern bis hin zu mehreren hundert Mikrometern Durchmesser variieren. Diese stammen aus natürlichen und anthropogenen Quellen und unterliegen im Laufe ihrer Verweildauer in der Atmosphäre einer Reihe von Transformationsprozessen (z.B. Koagulation, Kondensation, Wolkendurchgang), was zu räumlich und zeitlich stark veränderlichen Aerosolkonzentrationen führt. Aerosolpartikel wirken direkt auf das Klima, indem sie die Solarstrahlung streuen und absorbieren, und indirekt, indem sie in ihrer Eigenschaft als Wolkenkondensationskerne Wolkenbildung, Albedo und Niederschlagsprozesse beeinflussen (Twomey, 1974; Charlson et al., 1987). Von besonderer Relevanz ist die Bedeutung anthropogener Aerosole, deren klimatische Auswirkungen in der Größenordnung denen der Treibhausgase gleichgesetzt werden, allerdings mit entgegengesetztem Vorzeichen (Charlson et al., 1992).

Für das Verständnis des gesamten, aerosolbedingten Strahlungsantriebs, dessen Ausmaß noch immer mit großer Unsicherheit verbunden ist, stellt die experimentelle Aerosolcharakterisierung eine wesentliche Voraussetzung dar. Dabei ergeben sich die optischen Eigenschaften der Partikel (Absorption, Streuung) aus deren physiko-chemischen Eigenschaften (Konzentration, Größenverteilung, größen aufgelöste chemische Zusammensetzung, Mischungszustand, und Morphologie) (Philippin et al., 2000).

Bisher wurde in globalen Klimamodellen vor allem die Klimawirksamkeit von Sulfatpartikeln untersucht (Kiehl and Briegleb, 1993; Benkovitz and Schwartz, 1997). Große Bedeutung für den Strahlungshaushalt kommt jedoch auch kohlenstoffhaltigen Partikeln zu, die als Indikator für Luftverschmutzung gelten (Heintzenberg and Winkler, 1991; Penner and Novakov, 1996). Kohlenstoffpartikel, die eine komplexe Mischung verschiedener Verbindungen umfassen, entstehen vor allem in Verbrennungsprozessen und werden im allgemeinen in die zwei Klassen des elementaren und organischen Kohlenstoffs eingeteilt. Der elementare (schwarze) Kohlenstoff weist starke Absorptionseigenschaften auf und führt daher zu signifikanter Extinktion sichtbaren Lichts (Horvath, 1993). Während elementarer Kohlenstoff außerdem bezüglich seiner chemischen, insbesondere seiner katalytischen Eigenschaften eine wichtige Rolle spielt (Smith et al., 1989), wird organischem Kohlenstoff ein beachtliches Potential bei der Aktivierung von Wolkenströpfchen zugeschrieben (Novakov and Penner, 1993). Ein wesentlicher Aspekt der submikronen, kohlenstoffhaltigen Partikel ist weiterhin ihre gesundheitsgefährdende Wirkung auf den Menschen (Pope and Dockery, 1999).

Die experimentelle Untersuchung kohlenstoffhaltigen Materials im atmosphärischen Aerosol stellt aufgrund der komplexen Struktur und Zusammensetzung der Partikel eine große Herausforderung dar. Bis heute ist die Bestimmung und Quantifizierung der hauptsächlich im Submikrometerbereich zu findenden kohlenstoffhaltigen Komponenten wegen der geringen Masse der Partikel schwierig. Konventionelle chemische Verfahren untersuchen die Vielzahl existierender kohlenstoffhaltiger Verbindungen mit Hilfe einer ebenso vielfältigen Reihe von Analysemethoden. Diese beruhen oftmals auf einer auf Filter- oder Impaktorproben angewandten Volatilitätstechnik (Thermodesorption), wobei flüchtige Partikelkomponenten bei bestimmten Temperaturen verdampft, und die nichtflüchtigen Partikelfractionen extrahiert werden (Cadle and Groblicki, 1982; Cachier et al., 1989; VDI-Richtlinie 2465, 1997). Das absorbierende, kohlenstoffhaltige Material ist bei hohen Temperaturen thermisch resistent (*refraktorisch*) und stellt den überwiegenden Anteil der nichtflüchtigen Partikelmasse dar (Wolff and Klimisch, 1982; Heintzenberg and Winkler, 1991). Wegen der geringen Größe der Submikrometerpartikel sind diese konventionellen Analysemethoden mit sehr langen Sammelzeiten auf Filtern und Impaktoren verbunden. Sie lassen, vor allem in zeitlich stark variierenden Luftmassen, keine größen aufgelöste Charakterisierung des Kohlenstoffgehalts submikroner Partikel zu.

Einen technischen Fortschritt stellen luftgetragene Volatilitätsmethoden dar, die das temperaturabhängige Verdampfungsverhalten einer polydispersen Aerosolpopulation untersuchen, indem sie die nach der Konditionierung resultierenden Größenverteilungen mit optischen Partikelspektrometern bestimmen (Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; Jennings et al., 1994). Trotz dieser schnellen und größenabhängigen Messung erlaubt es diese *in-situ*-Technik nicht, die einzelnen Residuen ihren spezifischen Ausgangsgrößen zuzuordnen und den Mischungszustand einzelner Partikelgrößen zu bestimmen.

Eine Weiterentwicklung dieser luftgetragenen Volatilitätsmethoden wurde durch Größenverteilungsmessungen thermisch konditionierter, *quasi-monodisperser* Partikelgrößen erreicht (Rader and McMurry, 1986). Ein derartiger Volatilitäts-Tandem-Differential-Mobilitäts-Analysator (VTDMA) wurde bereits erfolgreich eingesetzt, um bei niedrigen Temperaturen (bis maximal 120 °C) die leichtflüchtige Schwefelsäurefraktion in Aerosolpartikeln in der sauberen, marinen Grenzschicht zu bestimmen (Orsini et al., 1999).

Im Rahmen dieser Dissertation wurde ein neuartiges VTDMA-System konzipiert, das erstmalig in der Lage ist, alle *nichtflüchtigen* Komponenten luftgetragener Aerosolpartikel spezifischer, *quasi-monodisperser* Größen mit hoher zeitlicher Auflösung zu bestimmen. Zu diesem Zweck wurden die Prinzipien des VTDMA übernommen und dahingehend erweitert, bei sehr viel höheren Temperaturen neben der Schwefelsäure alles weitere, flüchtige Partikelmaterial (z.B. Ammoniumsulfat, Ammoniumbisulfat, organische Kohlenstoffverbindungen) abzdampfen. Dies ermöglicht letztlich die Quantifizierung der nichtflüchtigen, vor allem kohlenstoffhaltigen, Aerosolkomponenten, die besonders in kontinental verschmutzten Luftmassen hohe Volumenanteile aufweisen. Die nach der thermischen Konditionierung gemessenen refraktorischen Partikelgrößen sind ihrer Ausgangsgröße eindeutig zugeordnet, was bei der Untersuchung der größenabhängigen chemischen Zusammensetzung der Partikel einen großen Vorteil bietet. Mit diesem System können erstmals einzelne Aerosolpartikel im submikronen Größenbereich, in dem die herkömmlichen

Analysemethoden keine größen aufgelöste Information liefern können, auf ihre nichtflüchtigen Kohlenstoffkomponenten untersucht werden.

Entwicklung und Kalibrierung des Volatilitätsanalyzers

Im entwickelten VTDMA-System werden zunächst quasi-monodisperse Submikrometerpartikel aus einer polydispersen Aerosolpopulation mittels eines Differentiellen Mobilitätsanalyzers (DMA) selektiert und ihre Anzahlkonzentration mit einem Kondensationspartikelzähler (CPC) bestimmt. Die sich anschließende Konditionierungseinheit besteht aus mehreren Heizstrecken, welche auf konstanten Temperaturen zwischen 25 °C und 300 °C gehalten werden. Dadurch können die den jeweiligen Temperaturen entsprechenden, flüchtigen Partikelkomponenten abgedampft werden. Die resultierenden Größenverteilungen der nichtflüchtigen Komponenten werden nachfolgend mit Hilfe einer weiteren Kombination aus DMA und CPC gemessen. Die Messung einer Größenverteilung (bei einer selektierten Ausgangsgröße und einer Temperaturstufe) dauert etwa 6 – 8 Minuten. Die gemessene Größenverteilung entspricht dabei nicht der wahren Partikelgrößenverteilung nach dem Konditionierungsprozeß, sondern ist das Ergebnis der Rückfaltung der gemessenen Daten mit der DMA Transferfunktion (Knutson and Whitby, 1975). Daher müssen gemessene Daten invertiert werden, wozu der Dateninversions-Algorithmus von Voutilainen et al. (2000) verwendet wird. Meßunsicherheiten aufgrund Partikelmehrfachladungen, statistischer Fehler der Partikelzähler (Poissonfehler) und Ungenauigkeiten durch z.B. instabile Flußraten und Spannungen in den DMAs betragen etwa 10 bis 15 %. Durch die anschließende Parameterisierung der invertierten Größenverteilungen können die nichtflüchtigen Anzahl- und Volumenfraktionen (Verhältnis konditioniert zu unkonditioniert) der selektierten Größenklasse bestimmt werden.

Der VTDMA wurde im Labor kalibriert, um die gemessenen Daten bezüglich der Partikelverluste im System aufgrund von Diffusion und Thermophorese korrigieren zu können. Die Kalibriermessungen zeigen, daß die Transporteffizienz der Partikel im VTDMA mit abnehmender Partikelgröße und zunehmender Temperatur abnimmt. Von selektierten 150 nm Partikeln gelangen zum Beispiel bei 25 °C 96 %, und bei 300 °C 81 % durch das System. Abhängig von der Konditionierungstemperatur (zwischen 25 bis 300 °C) sinkt die Transporteffizienz bei Partikelgrößen zwischen 10 und 20 nm auf 50 %.

Die Labormessungen dienen weiterhin dazu, das Verdampfungsverhalten künstlicher Aerosole wie z.B. Schwefelsäure (H_2SO_4), Ammoniumsulfat ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$) und Ammoniumbisulfat (NH_4HSO_4) zu bestimmen. Messungen von Partikeln bis 150 nm ergaben, daß bei 80 °C ein großer Teil der Schwefelsäure abdampft, und somit auch das noch flüchtigere Nitrat (z.B. in Form von Ammoniumnitrat) und vermutlich auch leichtflüchtige organische Verbindungen. Bei 180 °C sind die Sulfatverbindungen (d.h. H_2SO_4 und ihre neutralisierten Produkte $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ und NH_4HSO_4) komplett verflüchtigt. Unterschiede im Verdampfungsverhalten zwischen $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ und NH_4HSO_4 konnten nicht festgestellt werden. Diese Ergebnisse der Kalibriermessungen sind einzigartig, da die ermittelten Volatilitätstemperaturen (Temperaturen bei denen die spezifischen Komponenten komplett verdampft sind) für quasi-monodisperse Aerosolpartikel weit niedriger sind als diejenigen, die bislang für *Bulk*-Aerosole oder polydisperse Partikelpopulationen gemessen

wurden (Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; Rood et al., 1987). Es ist zu erwarten, daß bei 280 °C weitere leichtflüchtige Partikelkomponenten wie z.B. organische Verbindungen (Novakov et al., 1997) im VTDMA-System verdampfen. Das nach der Konditionierung bei 280 °C im VTDMA verbleibende, refraktorische Partikelmaterial wird als nichtflüchtig bezeichnet und umfaßt vor allem nichtvolatilen Kohlenstoff (d.h. elementaren, schwarzen, bzw. graphitischen Kohlenstoff) und möglicherweise schwerflüchtige organische Kohlenstoffverbindungen. Weiterhin können im atmosphärischen Aerosol Spuren von Seesalz, Krustenmaterial, Metallen oder Flugasche vorhanden sein. Diese stellen jedoch im submikronen Größenbereich einen vernachlässigbaren Massenanteil dar (Heintzenberg, 1989).

Volatilitätsanalysen atmosphärischer Aerosolpartikel

Die Verteilung nichtflüchtigen Materials in atmosphärischen Aerosolpartikeln unterliegt starken räumlichen und zeitlichen Schwankungen und hängt hauptsächlich von der Art und ihrer Entfernung zu den Quellen ab (z.B. wird nichtvolatiler Kohlenstoff vor allem bei der unvollständigen Verbrennung fossiler Brennstoffe gebildet). Die Verteilung des nichtvolatilen Materials kann durch i) Mischungsprozesse (von Aerosolpopulationen aus verschiedenen Quellen), und durch ii) Transformationsprozesse wie z.B. Koagulation und Kondensation beeinflusst werden. Zur Untersuchung von Aerosoltypen mit verschiedenen Anteilen refraktorischen Materials wurden umfangreiche VTDMA-Messungen in unterschiedlicher Distanz zu Verbrennungsquellen durchgeführt.

1. Zunächst wurden Partikel in unmittelbarer Nähe von Verbrennungsquellen untersucht. Hierzu wurden VTDMA-Messungen in verdünnter Abgasluft von verschiedenen Fahrzeugen (Diesel, Direkteinspritzer, Benziner, und erdgasbetriebenes Fahrzeug) durchgeführt (*FORD 98*). Die dabei gewonnenen Ergebnisse zeigen, daß die nichtflüchtige Fraktion emittierter Partikel stark vom jeweiligen Fahrzeugtyp, Brennstoff und Betriebszustand abhängig ist.

Die monomodale Struktur der nichtflüchtigen Größenverteilungen selektierter 50 nm Partikel (das Konzentrationsmaximums aller emittierten Partikeldurchmesser liegt nahe 50 nm) bei Dieselfahrzeugen läßt darauf schließen, daß alle 50 nm Partikel ursprünglich denselben Anteil an nichtflüchtigem Material besitzen. Diesel-emittierte Partikel zeigen hohe nichtvolatile Volumenfraktionen zwischen 75 und 100 %. Die nichtflüchtige Anzahl- und Volumenfraktion steigt mit zunehmender Geschwindigkeit (d.h. Umdrehungszahl) und abnehmendem Luft-Brennstoff-Verhältnis (*air-fuel-ratio* (AFR)). Je kleiner das AFR desto "fetter" das Luft-Brennstoff-Gemisch. Die Anzahlfraktion Diesel-emittierter Partikel ist immer etwa 100 %, was darauf hindeutet, daß alle Partikel nichtflüchtige Kerne besitzen.

Im Gegensatz dazu sind bei Direkteinspritzer nur 4 bis 8 % des Volumens von Partikeln nichtvolatil, wobei etwa 50 % aller Partikel in der Konditionierstrecke des VTDMA-Systems komplett verdampfen.

Ein beträchtlicher Anteil des von benzin- oder erdgasbetriebenen Fahrzeugen emittierten Partikelmaterials ist bereits bei 25 °C volatil, möglicherweise aufgrund der Verdampfung semivolatiler Komponenten in der sauberen Schleierluft der DMAs. Dieser Effekt ist von großer Relevanz, da er in allen DMA-basierten Partikel-Größenverteilungsmessungen zu erwarten ist, dort aber nicht nachgewiesen werden kann. Die Ergebnisse der

Volatilitätsmessungen repräsentieren somit bezüglich Anzahl- und Volumenfraktion obere Grenzwerte, da bei 25 °C die Partikel nicht mehr unkonditioniert sind. Die von Benzinfahrzeugen emittierten Partikel zeigen im Vergleich zu Diesel-emittierten Partikeln eine beträchtlich kleinere, nichtflüchtige Volumenfraktion. Die Werte liegen unterhalb von 11 bis 33 %, steigend mit abnehmendem AFR. *Fette* Brennstoffgemische zeigen erwartungsgemäß den größten Anteil nichtvolatilen Materials. Überraschenderweise enthalten die von erdgasbetriebenen Fahrzeugen emittierten Partikel relativ viel refraktorisches Material (bis ca. 30 %).

2. Volatilitätsmessungen von Partikeln wurden in einer stark verschmutzten, urbanen Region in Leipzig während einer einwöchigen, kalten Winterperiode durchgeführt (*VoLE 99*). Die Volatilitäts-Größenverteilungen von 150 nm Partikeln zeigen während der gesamten Meßkampagne denselben multimodalen Charakter mit zwei signifikanten Moden: der erste Mode (bei ca. 145 nm) nahe der selektierten Partikelgröße repräsentiert *quasi-nichtflüchtige* Partikel; ein zweiter, breiter Mode bei kleineren Partikeldurchmessern (40-60 nm) repräsentiert alle verbleibenden *partiell-nichtflüchtigen* Partikel mit verschiedenen Volumenanteilen an nichtflüchtigem Material. Die nichtflüchtige Anzahl-fraktion ist konstant (~ 100 %), was zeigt, daß alle Ausgangspartikel nichtvolatile Kerne besitzen. Das gesamte nichtflüchtige Volumen variiert zwischen 12 und 24 % und liegt im Durchschnitt bei 18 ± 4 %. Etwa 14 % aller 150 nm Partikel sind *quasi-nichtflüchtig*. (150 nm Partikel wurden repräsentativ für Akkumulationsmode-Partikel ausgewählt; die entsprechenden refraktorischen Residuen sind noch groß genug (d.h. > 15 nm), um sie mit dem VTDMA detektieren zu können, was z.B. bei atmosphärischen 50 nm Partikeln nicht immer der Fall ist.) Die morphologischen Partikelanalysen des refraktorischen Materials zeigen die typische, kohlenstoffhaltige Struktur.

Zusätzliche Analysen der chemischen (*Bulk*-) Partikelzusammensetzung ergeben, daß die submikrone Gesamtkohlenstoffmasse im Schnitt etwa 23 % beträgt. Etwa 75 % des Gesamtkohlenstoffes sind organisch, wobei der leichtflüchtige organische Anteil die Mehrheit (79 %) bildet (leicht- und schwerflüchtige organische Anteile wurden bei 280 °C bzw. 590 °C durch Thermodesorption bestimmt). Ein Vergleich von nichtflüchtigen Volumenfraktionen (von 150 nm Partikeln) mit nichtflüchtigen Kohlenstoff-Massenfraktionen der entsprechenden *Bulk*-Partikel-Größenbereiche (aus Thermodesorption) (d.h., 50/140 nm und 140/420 nm) zeigt eine gute Korrelation beider Größen.

3. In einer dritten Meßkampagne wurden umfangreiche VTDMA-Messungen in einer nicht-urbanen Region ca. 70 km südöstlich von Berlin durchgeführt (*LACE 98*), um die Volatilität von Aerosolpartikeln in mäßig verschmutzten Luftmassen zu untersuchen. Die typischen Volatilitäts-Größenverteilungen von 150 nm Partikeln zeigen, verglichen mit *VoLE 99*, einen kleineren *quasi-nichtflüchtigen* Mode und einen signifikanten *partiell-nichtflüchtigen* Mode bei ca. 40 nm. Die Gesamtanzahl der Partikel bleibt nach der Konditionierung konstant, d.h. alle Partikel enthalten nichtflüchtiges Material. Das Gesamtvolumen der refraktorischen Komponenten variiert zwischen 8 % und 21 % und beträgt durchschnittlich 11 ± 2.9 %. Etwa 6 % aller 150 nm Partikel sind *quasi-nichtflüchtig*.

Die Ergebnisse der chemischen Analyse zeigen, daß der Gesamtkohlenstoff ca. 22 % der submikronen Masse beträgt. Etwa die Hälfte des Gesamtkohlenstoffs ist organisch. Messungen zur Unterscheidung von leicht- und schwerflüchtigem organischen Kohlenstoff (vgl. *VoLE 99*) sind nicht verfügbar. Ein Vergleich von nichtflüchtigen Volumenfraktionen (von 150 nm Partikeln) mit nichtflüchtigen Kohlenstoff-Massenfraktionen (aus Thermodesorption) im *Bulk*-Partikel-Größenbereich 140 - 420 nm zeigt eine gute Korrelation beider Parameter (Philippin et al., 1999a). Aufgrund der geringen Masse und niedrigen atmosphärischen Partikelanzahlkonzentrationen sind die ermittelten Kohlenstoff-Massenfraktionen für 50 - 140 nm Partikel nahe der Detektionsgrenze und daher mit hohen Unsicherheiten verbunden.

Eine Klassifizierung der während *LACE 98* beobachteten Luftmassen (anhand von Rückwärtstrajektorien, meteorologischen Parametern und chemischer Partikelzusammensetzung) zeigt folgenden Trend: kontinental-beeinflußte, marine Partikel enthalten den geringsten nichtflüchtigen Volumenanteil, der mit dem Verschmutzungsgrad zunimmt, wohingegen kontinental-beeinflußtes Aerosol aus Osteuropa (d.h. aus Gebieten verstärkter Industrieemissionen) die höchsten Werte aufweist.

Zusammenfassend läßt sich aus den Resultaten der Volatilitätsmessungen von *FORD 98*, *VoLE 99*, und *LACE 98* schließen, daß der Volumenanteil nichtflüchtiger Komponenten mit zunehmender Distanz zu den Verbrennungsquellen abnimmt (Philippin et al., 1999b). Direkt an der Quelle zeigen 50 nm Dieselpartikel durchschnittlich 88 % nichtflüchtiges Material. In Quellferne dagegen betragen entsprechende Werte in 150 nm Partikeln im Durchschnitt 18 % im stark verschmutzten urbanen, und 11 % im mäßig verschmutzten, nicht-urbanen Aerosol. In allen atmosphärischen Aerosolpartikel können nichtflüchtige Kerne nachgewiesen werden. Dieses Ergebnis ist signifikant und stellt vor allem im Zusammenhang bei der Entstehung von Sekundärpartikel (aus Nukleation und anschließender Kondensation) eine wesentliche Erkenntnis dar. Die Struktur der atmosphärischen Volatilitäts-Größenverteilungen spiegelt den möglichen Einfluß sowohl verschiedener Quellen als auch der Misch- und Transformationsprozesse wider. Die *quasi-nichtflüchtige* Partikelanzahlfraktion war während *VoLE 99* größer (14 %) als während *LACE 98* (6 %), was zeigt, daß der Anteil an *quasi-nichtflüchtigen* Partikeln mit größerer Entfernung zu Verbrennungsquellen abnimmt. Ein Vergleich zwischen der Ergebnisse von Volatilitätsanalyse und Thermodesorption zeigt trotz der methodischen Unterschiede (Vergleich von Volumen- mit Massenfraktionen; von luftgetragenen, quasi-monodispersen Partikeln mit Impaktor-gesammeltem *Bulk*-Aerosol, von nichtflüchtigem Gesamtvolumen mit nichtflüchtiger Gesamtkohlenstoffmasse) eine gute Übereinstimmung. Aus den Vergleichsmessungen kann geschlossen werden, daß das nichtflüchtige Material im VTDMA überwiegend aus nichtvolatilem Kohlenstoff besteht. Allerdings sind schwerflüchtige, organische Kohlenstoffverbindungen, die während des Konditionierungsprozesses im VTDMA nicht abdampfen, nicht auszuschließen (ihr Anteil am Gesamtkohlenstoff wird während *VoLE 99* auf maximal 26 % geschätzt, wird hingegen während *LACE 98* geringer eingestuft, da dort das Verhältnis von organischem zu elementarem Kohlenstoff geringer ist).

Zusammenfassung und Ausblick

Die im Rahmen dieser Arbeit gewonnenen Ergebnisse zeigen, daß mit dem Volatilitätsanalysator ein wertvolles Instrument zur Untersuchung nichtflüchtiger, im wesentlichen kohlenstoffhaltiger, Komponenten submikroner Aerosolpartikel zur Verfügung steht. Die Anwendung der Methode ist sowohl in stark verschmutzten Gebieten mit hohen Anteilen nichtflüchtigen Materials (z.B. an der Quelle von Verbrennungsprozessen), als auch in weniger belasteten Regionen mit deutlich niedrigeren Aerosolkonzentrationen und deren geringeren Anteilen nichtflüchtigen Materials, geeignet. Die luftgetragene Meßmethode ist bei der Untersuchung einzelner Partikel den herkömmlichen, chemischen Methoden weit überlegen, denn sie erlaubt, größen aufgelöste Information über die Partikel, die bisher aufgrund ihrer zu geringen Masse nicht mit einer ausreichenden zeitlichen Auflösung analysiert werden konnten, zu gewinnen. Dies ermöglicht erstmals die Untersuchung nichtflüchtiger Aerosolkomponenten in zeitlich und räumlich stark variierenden Luftmassen. Zusätzliche Laborstudien zum Volatilitätsverhalten weiterer Aerosole mit wohldefinierter Zusammensetzung (interne und/oder externe Mischungen von elementarem und unterschiedlichen organischen Kohlenstoffen), die im Rahmen dieser Arbeit nicht untersucht wurden, werden die wesentlichen Ergebnisse dieser Arbeit wertvoll ergänzen. Dadurch wird die Deutung des Verdampfungsverhaltens atmosphärischer Aerosole besonders im Hinblick auf mögliche Transformationsprozesse erleichtert werden. Zukünftig wird der in dieser Arbeit entwickelte VTDMA eine tragende Rolle bei der Untersuchung physiko-chemischer Prozesse submikroner Aerosolpartikel spielen und notwendige Modellparameter liefern, um die Größe des Einflusses nichtflüchtiger Aerosolkomponenten auf den Strahlungshaushalt der Atmosphäre und auf die Gesundheit des Menschen abschätzen zu können.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND SYMBOLS

APS	Aerodynamic Particle Sizer
AFR	air-fuel ratio
BC	black carbon
CPC	Condensation Particle Counter
DMA	Differential Mobility Analyzer
DMPS	(Twin-) Differential Mobility Particle Analyzer System
EC	elemental carbon
EPS	Electrostatic Particle Sampler
<i>FORD</i>	measurement campaign at FORD emissions laboratory
GC	graphitic carbon
HC	hydrocarbons
HTDMA	Hygroscopicity Tandem Differential Mobility Analyzer
<i>LACE 98</i>	Lindenberg Aerosol Characterization Experiment
nvC	non-volatile carbon
OC	organic carbon
OC ^I , OC ^{II}	organic carbon, volatile at 280 °C, 590 °C
PSAP	Particle Soot/Absorption Photometer
PM ₁	submicrometer particles (< 1 μm (geometric) diameter)
PM ₁₀	supermicrometer particles (< 10 μm (geometric) diameter)
<i>rev</i>	engine revolution
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
TC, TOC	total carbon, total organic carbon
<i>VoLE 99</i>	Aerosol Volatility measurements in Leipzig
VTDMA	Volatility Tandem Differential Mobility Analyzer
β	aerosol-to-sheath air flow rate through DMA
δ_{rel}	relative deviation of measured quantities
η, η_{air}	viscosity, dynamic air viscosity
η_{diff}	diffusional transport efficiency
η_{thermo}	thermophoretic transport efficiency
$\Phi_{N,qnv}, \Phi_{N,pnv}$	<i>quasi-non-volatile</i> number fraction, <i>partially-non-volatile</i> number fraction
$\Phi_{V,qnv}, \Phi_{V,pnv}$	<i>quasi-non-volatile</i> volume fraction, <i>partially-non-volatile</i> volume fraction
Φ_{Dp}	relative size ratio
Φ_N, Φ_V	relative particle number fraction, relative particle volume fraction
$\Phi_M, \Phi_{M,EC}$	mass fraction, EC mass fraction
$\mathcal{S}(\rho)$	density parameter
λ	mean free path
λ	equivalence ratio (relative AFR)
λ	wavelength of light

ρ, ρ_{air}	density, density of air
σ_a	absorption coefficient
σ_s	specific attenuation cross-section
τ_{vap}	time for evaporation
$\tau_t, \tau_{\text{max}}$	total residence time, residence time at maximum temperature
Ω	DMA transfer function
B	mechanical particle mobility [m/N·s]
C_c	Cunningham slip correction factor
d	diameter of sampling line
D_B	Brownian diffusion coefficient, particle diffusivity
D_p	particle diameter
$D_{p,\text{geo}}, D_{p,\text{aero}}$	geometric particle diameter, aerodynamic particle diameter
g_f	growth factor
i	volatilization step
k	Boltzmann constant ($= 1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$)
L	length of sampling line
$n(D_p)$	particle number distribution
N, N_{total}	particle number, total particle number
$N_{150\text{nm}}$	number concentration of 150 nm particles
N_i	residual particle number after volatilization step i
$N_{\text{qnv}}, N_{\text{pnv}}$	<i>quasi-non-volatile, partially-non-volatile</i> particle number concentration
p	pressure
Q	flow rate
Q_a, Q_d	aerosol flow rate, dilution flow rate
r	particle radius
Re	Reynolds number
RH	relative humidity
T, $T_{\text{initial}}, T_{\text{max}}$	temperature, initial temperature, maximum temperature
T_{vapor}	volatilization temperature
v	velocity
V, V_{total}	particle volume, total particle volume
V_i	residual particle volume after volatilization step i
$V_{\text{qnv}}, V_{\text{pnv}}$	<i>quasi-non-volatile, partially-non-volatile</i> particle volume concentration
w_s, w_d	wind speed, wind direction
Z_p	electrical particle mobility

1. INTRODUCTION

Atmospheric aerosols play a fundamental role in the Earth-atmosphere system, encompassing all liquid and solid particles suspended in the air. These particles originate from natural sources such as windblown dust, sea spray, volcanic eruptions, and forest fires, as well as from anthropogenic sources, such as fuel combustion and industrial processes. The variety of sources and the transformation processes aerosols experience during their lifetime (e.g., coagulation, condensation, cloud processing, sedimentation) cause a highly varying temporal and spatial distribution of chemical compositions, number concentrations, and size distributions. Due to their short lifetime (particles ranging between 0.1 to 10 μm in diameter show tropospheric residence times on the order of days to a week), aerosols tend to be concentrated close to their sources. Thus, in industrialized areas concentrations of 10^4 to 10^5 cm^{-3} are being found, whereas in remote and marine regions as well as in the upper troposphere particle numbers are reduced to several hundreds per cubic centimeter or below (Junge, 1963; Prospero et al., 1983).

Aerosol particles affect climate in two ways: directly by scattering and absorbing solar radiation, and indirectly by modifying the optical properties and lifetime of clouds (Twomey, 1974; Charlson et al., 1987). To date, the global aerosol burden is known to have increased since pre-industrial times, largely due to anthropogenic activities, i.e., the combustion of fossil fuels (Cachier, 1998). The magnitude of the climatic perturbations produced by anthropogenic aerosols through direct and indirect contributions to radiative forcing is considered comparable but opposite in sign to that caused by greenhouse forcing (Charlson et al., 1990; 1991; 1992; Charlson and Heintzenberg, 1995). The assessment of the radiative forcing is still associated with high uncertainties due to the limited knowledge of the temporal and spatial global distribution of aerosols and their related physico-chemical and optical properties. Global modeling studies require extensive laboratory and field measurements to completely characterize aerosols with respect to their concentration, size distribution, size-dependent chemical composition, state of mixture, and morphology, as well as information about aerosol-related formation and transformation processes which are still poorly understood (Heintzenberg and Covert, 1990; Heintzenberg et al., 1996).

In the past, considerable attention has been given to understanding the climatic effect of particulate sulfate (Langner and Rodhe, 1991; Kiehl and Briegleb, 1993; Benkovitz and Schwartz, 1997). However, carbonaceous material has been confirmed to be of prime importance in the atmosphere (Wolff et al., 1982; Ogren and Charlson, 1983; Heintzenberg and Winkler, 1991; Penner and Novakov, 1996). It comprises a significant fraction of the aerosol mass, particularly in urban regions, but is found in remarkable quantities even in rural and remote areas (Wolff and Klimisch, 1982). Particulate carbon, residing mainly in the submicrometer particle size range (Heintzenberg and Covert, 1984), encompasses a complex mixture of substances and is generally classified into two fractions, elemental (EC) and organic carbon (OC). Carbon-containing substances are produced predominantly by combustion processes and are particularly important due to the absorbing potential of elemental (or “black”) carbon. Thus, particulate carbon substantially contributes to the extinction of visible light (Horvath, 1993). Being solely primary, elemental

carbon is emitted directly from its sources and is considered an important tracer for anthropogenic pollution (Penner et al., 1993; Cooke and Wilson, 1996; Lioussse et al., 1996). Essential in aerosol-related processes are furthermore the chemical and in particular the catalytic properties of elemental carbon (Chang et al., 1981; Smith et al., 1989) and the ability of organic carbon to act as cloud condensation nuclei (Novakov and Penner, 1993; Penner, 1995; Corrigan and Novakov, 1999). Moreover, environmental implications of carbonaceous particles include visibility degradation (Groblicki et al., 1981; Japar et al., 1986; Larson and Cass, 1989; Larson et al., 1989) and soiling (Hamilton and Mansfield, 1991). Recent interest concerns the carcinogenic and toxic effects of carbonaceous (submicrometer) particles on the human health (Pope and Dockery, 1999).

The complexity of the structure and composition of carbonaceous aerosol particles poses challenges on its experimental determination. In the past, measurement and quantification of carbonaceous material in the submicrometer particle size range has been difficult due to the small size and accordingly small mass of the particles. Conventional chemical methods study the variety of existing carbonaceous compounds by an equally diverse range of detection methods. These involve mostly volatility techniques that are based on extracting the desired, non-volatile carbonaceous aerosol portion at known characteristic temperatures. They allow to separate the volatile organic carbon (OC) from the non-volatile elemental carbon (EC) (Cadle and Groblicki, 1982; Cachier et al., 1989; VDI-Richtlinie 2465, 1997), which comprises the predominant non-volatile aerosol portion (Wolff et al., 1982; Gray et al., 1986; Heintzenberg and Winkler, 1991). The majority of chemical methods imply particle collection necessarily over long time intervals, thus, inhibiting to resolve the size-segregated physico-chemical nature of aerosols in rapidly changing environments. Moreover, large differences between the above volatility-based methods exist (producing different results), and they are furthermore associated with measurement artifacts commonly encountered with filter sampling of organic aerosols (McDow and Huntzicker, 1990; Novakov et al., 1997).

Technological advance represent airborne volatility methods which determine the change in particle size by heating a polydisperse aerosol populations and measuring the resulting particle number size distribution using optical particle sizers (e.g., Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; Jennings and O'Dowd, 1990; Jennings et al., 1994). Although these in-situ techniques provide results with high temporal resolution they do not allow to determine the mixing state of the chemical compounds within individual particles sizes or to assign changes in particle number concentration to specific size ranges.

A further advancement of the in-situ volatility method was to measure the size distribution of thermally conditioned *quasi-monodisperse* aerosol particles. This technique was realized for the first time with a volatility tandem differential mobility analyzer (VTDMA) (Rader and McMurry, 1986; Covert and Heintzenberg, 1993). The early VTDMA was employed to quantify solely the prevailing volatile sulfuric acid fraction of aerosol particles in the remote marine boundary layer by exposing the particles to temperatures of 120 °C in maximum (Orsini et al., 1999).

The present research work adopted and extended the principles of this previous VTDMA to develop a volatility analyzer that is capable of evaporating volatile material at substantially higher temperatures, allowing to quantify all non-volatile aerosol compounds. This volatility analyzer is designed to investigate particularly the carbonaceous compounds of particles in continentally polluted air masses. The improved instrument selects quasi-monodisperse submicrometer particles from a polydisperse aerosol population, and subsequently evaporates their volatile compounds by exposing them to conditioning temperatures between 25 °C and 300 °C (the conditioning unit consists of eight heating columns being kept at different temperatures). The change in particle size due to heating is recorded by measuring the resulting refractory number size distribution. These results can be quantified in terms of non-volatile number and volume fractions, representing the total number and volume of the refractory material with respect to the unconditioned, quasi-monodisperse particles. In advance of any field measurement, laboratory studies are needed to determine the characteristic temperature at which the major aerosol compounds, i.e., sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, and volatile organic carbon, completely evaporate in the VTDMA system.

Subsequently, extensive field measurements were conducted to examine the non-volatile nature of atmospheric aerosols in the lower troposphere. The data analyzed originate from several field campaigns covering measurements of a) vehicle-emitted particles representing aerosols directly at a combustion source, expected to contain large fractions of non-volatile carbon (*FORD 98*); of b) particles in a heavily polluted urban environment with high amounts of carbonaceous material (*VoLE 99*); and of c) particles in a moderately polluted, non-urban, rural region (*LACE 98*). The goal of the series of field studies was to investigate the volatile behavior of different aerosol types containing different amounts of carbonaceous material and to give evidence of their mixing state. Of particular importance are measurements of particles in the small, submicrometer size range where the above methods can not deliver size-specific information.

This dissertation introduces the subject of non-volatile aerosol compounds in chapter 2 which briefly reviews the fine particle composition, points out the importance of non-volatile aerosol fractions, and summarizes commonly used methods to determine carbonaceous aerosol compounds as far as they are relevant to this work. The design of the newly developed volatility analyzer and the results of the laboratory measurements are presented in the following chapters 3 and 4. Thereafter in chapter 5, the reader is acquainted with a simple concept allowing to relate the mixing of volatile and non-volatile compounds within aerosol particles to the results of the volatility field measurements. These are extensively described in chapter 6 which is divided into four subchapters, dedicated to the discussion of volatility measurements of particles in differently polluted environments and a synopsis resuming the important results. Finally, chapter 7 summarizes the thesis and gives an outlook for future studies.

2. VOLATILITY OF FINE AEROSOL PARTICLES

Information about physical and chemical aerosol properties can be obtained by investigating the volatility characteristics of the aerosol particles. Various aerosol compounds exhibit a different volatile behavior which is indicative for the composition of the entire aerosol particle. The following chapter will discuss the importance of the non-volatile constituents in submicrometer aerosol particles and focuses particularly on the carbonaceous compounds and their significance in the atmosphere.

2.1. FINE PARTICLE COMPOSITION

An important feature of atmospheric aerosol size distributions is their multimodal character (cf. Fig. 2.1). Generally, fine and coarse particles exist which are produced, transformed, and removed differently, thus, revealing different physical, chemical, and optical properties. Although the boundaries between fine and coarse particles are not precise, all particles smaller than one micrometer are generally termed *fine* particles. Fine particles typically comprise most of the total number of particles and a significant fraction of the mass. Associated modes include nuclei or ultrafine mode (1 - 20 nm), Aitken mode (20 - 100 nm), and accumulation mode (100 - 1000 nm). Particles in the nucleation mode are formed by gas-to-particle conversion of supersaturated vapors

Figure 2-1. Schematic of an atmospheric aerosol size distribution indicating the main sources and formation processes (from Whitby (1978)).

and subsequent condensation processes. The lifetime of these particles is short (sometimes on the order of minutes to hours). These particles grow into the accumulation mode by coagulation, condensation of low volatility vapors, and cloud processes. Accumulation mode particles have long lifetimes, on the order of days to weeks, and are slowly removed by incorporation into cloud droplets and subsequent precipitation, and dry deposition. The major chemical components of the fine aerosol encompass sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, organic and elemental carbon. Moreover, they may contain a variety of trace metals from combustion processes, and varying quantities of minerals or sea-salt. The degree to which the different components are distributed within the fine aerosol particles depends on their natural and anthropogenic sources and ensuing aging processes. An example of fine particle composition representative for urban, non-urban, and remote locations is illustrated in Figure 2.2. These data are compiled, averaged results of a large number of data sets from various locations all over the world (Heintzenberg, 1989).

Figure 2-2. Average fine particle composition in urban, non-urban, and remote locations (Heintzenberg, 1989). The undetermined fraction (N\D) includes mass fractions of individual compounds < 6 % as well as not analyzed mass. OC and EC denote organic and elemental carbon, respectively.

Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) is partly produced by primary, e.g., industrial, sources but mostly arises from secondary particle formation of the oxidation of sulfur dioxide from fossil fuel emissions. Natural sulfate is formed from emissions of marine dimethyl sulfide gas (DMS) and volcanic SO_2 . Sulfate is present as sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), or, if gaseous ammonia is available, as its (partially) neutralized components, i.e., ammonium bisulfate (NH_4HSO_4) and ammonium sulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$). Nitrate stems from the oxidation of nitrogen dioxide to nitric acid, and forms basic particulate material as a result of its reaction with ammonia or sodium chloride (the primary production of particulate nitrate is of little importance). Carbonaceous aerosol particles are mostly formed through combustion processes and are emitted into the atmosphere in particulate and condensable gaseous form. Their fraction, therefore, increases with increasing proximity to combustion sources and encompasses elemental and organic carbon. Particularly the black carbonaceous portion, although a minor component, is responsible for relevant atmospheric processes (e.g., light absorption).

2.2. IMPORTANCE OF NON-VOLATILE PARTICLE FRACTIONS

Based on their chemical composition fine aerosol particles can have different physical and optical properties (e.g., volatile behavior, hygroscopicity, radiative effect). This work focuses on the investigation of volatile and non-volatile particle properties which can provide valuable information about particle chemical composition and mixing state.

2.2.1. Non-volatile Particle Compounds

The volatile behavior of aerosol particles is a function of the temperature-dependent thermodynamic properties of its components or mixture of compounds and their residence times in a given, elevated temperature field (cf. Chap. 4.2). Different studies employing airborne volatility techniques demonstrated that individual components in polydisperse aerosol particles such as sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, as well as the volatile organic carbon compounds can be evaporated at temperatures between approximately 50 and 250 °C, depending on their degree of neutralization (e.g., Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; O'Dowd and Smith, 1993; Hudson and Da, 1996; Smith and O'Dowd, 1996; Cantrell et al., 1997; Kreidenweis et al., 1998). The fraction of less volatile organic and elemental (or black) carbon is thermally resistant at these temperatures. Further, non-carbonaceous particle components exist in our atmosphere that are considered strongly non-volatile. These are sea-salt, crustal material, trace metals, and fly ash. Sea-salt aerosol (NaCl) is produced by bursting bubbles at the ocean surface and is therefore mostly of supermicrometer size. Crustal material (e.g., Si, Al, Fe, Ca, K, Mn) is generally found in the coarse particle mode and is attributable to mechanical processes, e.g., wind erosion (Wallace and Hobbs, 1977; Whitby, 1978). Trace metals (e.g., Pb, Zn, As, Cu, Ni, Se, Cd) can originate from both, natural (e.g., windblown dust, volcanic eruption) and anthropogenic sources (e.g., fossil fuel combustion, metal industry) (Claes et al., 1998). Therefore, trace metals are found in different size classes. Supermicrometer particles contain naturally emitted trace metals, whereas those in the submicrometer size range are associated with anthropogenic emissions (Davidson and Osborne, 1986; Injuk et al., 1992; Horvath et al., 1996). Fine particles from combustion often contain small quantities of so-called *fly ash*, a mixture of ashes, dust, and soot (e.g., Fe₂O₃, ZnO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃) which are non-volatile and relatively chemically inert. Trace metals and fly ash represent only trace quantities of the fine particle mass and are mostly important for their adverse effects on the ecosystem and human health (Pacyna, 1998).

Although sea-salt, crustal material, trace metals, and fly ash are found in fine aerosol particles, their fraction is small compared to that of the carbonaceous compounds and does not contribute significantly to the overall mass of the submicrometer particles (Heintzenberg, 1989). Therefore, we confine the discussion of non-volatile submicrometer compounds to the carbonaceous fraction. In the following sections, the variety of carbonaceous compounds, their sources, and implications are presented and discussed.

2.2.2. Carbonaceous Aerosol Particles

Carbonaceous material in atmospheric aerosol particles originates mostly from combustion processes which produce both primary and secondary particles (cf. Fig. 2.3). Primary particles are formed by direct combustion emissions, secondary particles result from nucleation and subsequent condensation of low-volatility products or adsorption of organic gases onto preexisting particles. The principal anthropogenic source of carbonaceous particles is incomplete combustion of fossil and biomass fuel (e.g., industrial emission, power generation, vehicle traffic, and biomass burning for agricultural purposes). The principal natural sources are natural fires and emissions from vegetation (organic carbon) but are found to be a minor contributor to the global atmospheric burden of carbon. Combustion of fossil fuel and biomass burning emit similar amounts of particulate black carbon into the atmosphere, averaging 6.6 and 5.6 Tg of mass per year, respectively (Liousse et al., 1996). Corresponding values from natural black carbon sources are negligibly small. Anthropogenic sources contribute with about 73.1 Tg of mass per year to the particulate organic carbon, whereas natural sources emit only 7.8 Tg of mass per year. About one third of the global fossil fuel emissions are from North America and Western Europe, and another larger portion (more than 50 %) from Eastern Europe, former USSR, and China. The principal biomass emission sources are found in Africa and South America (Cooke and Wilson, 1996).

Figure 2-3. Primary and secondary sources of carbonaceous material and associated direct and indirect radiative effect.

The complex composition and structure of the anthropogenically-emitted carbonaceous products is dependent on fuel type (fossil fuels, biomass) and combustion temperature. The resulting products can subsequently undergo chemical and physical transformations (e.g., coagulation, condensation, chemical reactions, cloud processes) and transport processes (e.g., convective or advective mixing, deposition).

For the manifold composition of carbonaceous particulate matter, no standard analysis methods and terminologies exist. The terms *elemental*, *graphitic*, *black carbon*, and *soot* are often used interchangeably and are method-based. The different definitions are briefly explained in the following.

- ◆ **Elemental carbon** (EC) exists in the form of diamond, graphite, or fullerenes. They are distinguished by their atomic structure. Diamond has a high density of $3.51 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (Cotton et al., 1988) and is arranged in a stable tetrahedron carbon structure, formed under high temperatures or pressures ($> 10^3 \text{ K}$ and $>10^8 \text{ hPa}$, respectively). Graphite has a density of $2.22 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and shows a layered structure, with the individual carbon atoms being surrounded by only three other carbon atoms. The layered structure enables the material to take up other molecules and ions. Recent studies show that the graphitic layers do not always represent two-dimensional surfaces but can form three-dimensional, curved crystallites with molecules consisting of more than 60 carbon atoms, so-called fullerenes (Kroto et al., 1985; Krätschmer et al., 1990). Graphitic microcrystals are 2 to 3 nm in diameter and form primary particles that are roughly spherical in shape and vary in size between 20 and 30 nm (cf. Fig. 2-4a). EC particles are only produced in combustion processes and are therefore solely primary.

Figure 2-4. (a) Illustration of graphitic microstructure of primary particles (adapted from Seinfeld and Pandis (1998)) and (b) aggregated carbon particle from TEM analysis (own measurements).

- ◆ The term **graphitic carbon** (GC) is generally employed for carbonaceous components containing graphite-like microcrystalline structures. Graphitic particles are only produced from high-temperature combustion processes. They are generally identified on a molecular level by Raman spectroscopy (Rosen and Novakov, 1977; Keller and Heintzenberg, 1997).
- ◆ **Black carbon** (BC) refers to the optically absorbing component of carbonaceous material. It often consists of agglomerates of primary particles and is the most polymerized fraction of the carbonaceous combustion aerosol particles (cf. Fig. 2-4b). The degree of aggregation appears random. Black carbon encompasses elemental carbon, graphitic carbon, and other absorbing carbon compounds.

- ◆ **Soot** generally specifies black carbon plus organic components. It originates from an incomplete combustion of carbon-containing fuels and forms if insufficient amounts of oxygen are present during combustion processes. Soot forms long-branched or straight chain aggregates that can agglomerate to develop particles up to a few micrometers. The exact density of soot particles is unknown, but due to particle-inherent voids it is assumed to be less than $2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ or even smaller than $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (Wagner, 1981; Zier and Goetz, 1982; Samson et al., 1987; Schultz, 1993; Hitzenberger et al., 1999). Due to the large surface of soot particles, other substances can easily adsorb, resulting in compositional changes as these soot particles age (e.g., condensation or adsorption of more volatile components on the surface of carbon cores).
- ◆ Small quantities of carbon can exist as **carbonate carbon** (CC). (Mueller et al., 1972) showed that the concentration of CC (e.g., CaCO_3 , NaHCO_3) was insignificant in samples of atmospheric aerosol particles at a particular urban location compared to EC or OC, i.e., being smaller than 2 – 5 % of the total carbon.
- ◆ **Non-volatile carbon** (nvC) refers to the non-volatile component of carbonaceous material that is refractory at a given temperature. It encompasses EC, GC, BC, as well as the majority of soot (the organic, soot-associated compounds are assumed to be volatile). Since nvC depends on the thermal properties of the carbonaceous compounds it is strongly method-dependent.
- ◆ **Organic carbon** (OC) constitutes the majority of particulate carbon and can be of both, primary and secondary origin. It encompasses a complex mixture of organic compounds such as alkanes, alkenes, aldehydes, aromatics (e.g., polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs)), ketones, etc.. Secondary OC is produced from precursor gases by condensation or adsorption from the gaseous phase on existing particle surfaces. Both, biogenic and anthropogenic sources contribute to primary and secondary organic particulate matter.

Elemental and organic particulate matter is generally mixed with other components within the atmospheric aerosol as it ages, through coagulation, condensation of secondary aerosol compounds (coatings of inorganic material), or cloud processing. For example, vehicle-emitted particles consist of a core of EC covered with a layer of PAHs and an outermost shell of volatile compounds (Steiner et al., 1992). Carbonaceous particles in urban areas are found to consist of aggregated spherules, with a wide range of carbon structures from OC to EC within the aggregates (Katrinak et al., 1992). The ratio of OC to EC in atmospheric aerosols is, therefore, variable. Due to the proximity to the combustion source, the fraction of carbon as part of the total aerosol mass is obviously higher in urban than in remote locations.

Typical urban concentrations of elemental (or black) carbon range from about 2 to $10 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, but can be as high as $50 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (Countess et al., 1981; Novakov, 1982; Heintzenberg and Winkler, 1984; Cachier et al., 1989; Tanner and Miguel, 1989). In non-urban and rural regions, values are often found between 0.05 and $2 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (Cachier et al., 1986; Clarke, 1989; Jennings et al., 1993),

and in remote (marine) areas the concentrations decrease to between 0.001 and 0.3 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (Hansen et al., 1988; Heintzenberg and Leck, 1994; Bodhaine, 1995). The results of a comparison of a large number of data sets for submicrometer particles showed that organic carbon represents about 31, 24, and 11 % of the total fine particle mass in urban, non-urban, and remote locations, respectively. The fraction of elemental carbon is lower, averaging approximately 9, 5, and 0.3 %, respectively (Heintzenberg, 1989).

2.2.3. Environmental Implications

Previous sections showed that non-volatile carbon is an important constituent of the atmospheric fine aerosol. This is particularly relevant since the majority of the carbonaceous material is anthropogenic. Due to its physico-chemical properties, non-volatile carbon has a significant impact on climate, environment, and human health. The different types of combustion sources and subsequent transformation processes produce a variety of aerosol types containing non-volatile carbon (cf. Fig. 2.5), leading to various interactions and effects.

Figure 2-5. Examples of typical soot agglomerates and coated soot agglomerates (e.g., with inorganic material).

The significance of the non-volatile fraction in atmospheric aerosol particles is briefly discussed in the following.

- Carbonaceous particles contribute to the **extinction of solar radiation** by both, scattering and absorption, thus, influencing radiative transfer and causing visibility degradation. Light absorption by particles is almost exclusively due to black carbon (BC has a large optical absorption cross section). This absorption has even been observed in remote locations (Waggoner et al., 1981; Heintzenberg, 1982; Clarke, 1989). Black carbon can effectively influence the Earth's climate by warming the atmosphere while decreasing the solar radiation reaching the surface (direct radiative effect) (Twomey et al., 1984; Schwartz, 1996). A crucial parameter used in estimating the direct radiative effect of atmospheric aerosols is the single-scattering albedo ω_0 (i.e., the ratio of scattering to extinction) which varies between the extreme values of 0 (no scattering) and 1 (no absorption). An increasing carbonaceous portion decreases the single-scattering albedo of the particles. The critical value of $\omega_0 \approx 0.85$ is considered the limiting value between global cooling and warming (however, this value

depends also strongly on other parameters, e.g., particle size, optical thickness, scattering angle, and underlying surface albedo) (Shettle and Fenn, 1979; Bohren and Huffman, 1983).

- Pure elemental carbon tends to be hydrophobic and is itself relatively inert. However, the agglomerated structure of EC results in a high surface to mass ratio which may catalytically **promote chemical reactions** in the atmosphere, especially in the presence of water. The oxidation of dissolved SO₂, e.g., can be accelerated due to the presence of carbon particles in water (Chang et al., 1981; Benner et al., 1985; Santachiara et al., 1989; Smith et al., 1989). Previous studies showed that black carbon particles coated with organic compounds have an increased **hygroscopicity** (Andrews and Larson, 1993). Hygroscopic particles grow by taking up water when the relative humidity (RH) increases. For example, during cloud processing particles may grow to sizes which are more efficient scatterers (Lelieveld and Heintzenberg, 1992).
- Particulate organic carbon has the ability to serve as **cloud condensation nuclei** (indirect radiative effect) (Ducret and Cachier, 1992; Novakov and Penner, 1993; Penner, 1995), thus, influencing the droplet number concentration and, as a consequence, the cloud albedo. Chylek and Hallett (1992) showed that the absorption of solar radiation by soot particles is increased if the particles are incorporated into cloud droplets.
- EC, deposited within or upon snow-covered surfaces may reduce the **albedo** of snow (Grenfell et al., 1981; Clarke and Noone, 1985).
- In addition to climate-relevant effects, other consequences of carbonaceous material are **soiling** of building by deposition (Hamilton and Mansfield, 1991), and most importantly, its **health effects**, for it can deeply penetrate into the lung, deposit in the pulmonary region, and provide adsorption sites for associated carcinogenic pollutants (Dockery and Pope, 1994; Brunekreef et al., 1995; Bascom et al., 1996; Peters et al., 1997; Cooney, 1998; Pope and Dockery, 1999).

2.3. EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF NON-VOLATILE PARTICLE COMPOUNDS

The principal methods to determine non-volatile carbon are volatility-based methods which are essentially thermal separation techniques followed by chemical analysis. Other, e.g., optical detection methods are only briefly discussed as far as they are relevant to this work.

2.3.1. Thermal Methods

Thermal methods are based on the resistance of black or elemental carbon to thermal conditioning at specific temperatures. Thermal methods are essentially intended to separate and quantify the

organic and elemental carbon fractions. The differentiation between OC and EC depends on the specific method.

- ***Thermal Desorption Method***

Previous to the thermal analysis, aerosol particles are usually collected on filter or impactor samples. The thermal desorption method separates the volatile OC from the total carbon (TC) during an initial precombustion step at predefined temperatures. EC is determined in a following step by heating the residue to much higher temperatures and analyzing the remaining carbon as CO₂. The TC fraction is calculated as the sum of OC and EC. The temperature-based differentiation between OC and EC is performed by a series of different techniques, employing conditioning times between several minutes and hours. For example, OC is volatilized under oxidative gas flow at temperatures between 340 and 400 °C, and EC is subsequently determined at combustion temperatures between 650 and 1100 °C, both under pure oxygen (Cadle and Groblicki, 1982; Cachier et al., 1989; Cachier et al., 1989). Another technique applies temperatures up to 650 °C to determine OC, using an inert gas (N₂ or He). EC is subsequently measured at 650 to 700 °C under O₂ (Wolff et al., 1982; Ulrich et al., 1990; VDI-Richtlinie 2465, 1997). Further methods use infrared spectrophotometry to measure simultaneously the possible darkening of the filter by charring to discriminate between OC and EC (Huntzicker et al., 1982; Chow et al., 1993). Disadvantages of the thermodesorption / oxidation method are the potential underestimation of EC due to resulting carbonation (i.e., production of carbonate (CO₃)) at high temperatures, and the possibility of the oxidation of EC during the removal of organic phases. Other similar methods exist that use wet extraction as a first step to separate OC with organic solvents (e.g., acetone, toluene/isopropanol) (Novakov, 1982; Kuhlbusch, 1994; Petzold and Nießner, 1996; VDI-Richtlinie 2465, 1996). A possible artifact of these methods, however, is the difficulty of separating organic vapors from particles (McDow and Huntzicker, 1990; Turpin et al., 1994) and the refractory behavior of certain OC compounds to extraction. Organic vapors can adsorb on the filter substrates during particle collection, thus, increasing the true particulate OC content. OC or other species having adequate vapor pressures can also evaporate from the filter, yielding reduced concentrations. Both effects falsify the results of determining the particulate carbonaceous composition. A general drawback of the thermal desorption method is the variable refractory behavior of OC compounds, leading to a variable quantification of OC for given temperatures. Moreover, due to lack of mass in the small particle size range, long particle collection times are required implying a small temporal resolution (order of hours to days).

- ***Airborne Volatility Methods***

Airborne volatility methods investigate physical or optical characteristics of aerosol particles after thermal conditioning to specific temperatures. This technique was initially applied to marine aerosol particles to separate the more volatile ammonium sulfate from refractory sea salt (Twomey, 1971). In a number of studies, temperature-controlled nephelometry was used to study the change in the light extinction coefficient of submicrometer particles due to the volatilization of particle material (Larson et al., 1982; Rood et al., 1985; 1987). Derived

characteristics were used to differentiate between sulfuric acid and ammonium sulfate aerosols. In other studies, polydisperse aerosol particles were passed through a heating tube with temperatures between 290 and 320 °C to isolate the aerosol refractory material (Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; Clarke and Porter, 1991; Hudson and Da, 1996). The residual aerosol size distribution was subsequently measured with a laser particle counter. Following studies extended this work to investigate supermicrometer, refractory sea-salt particles and elemental carbon (Jennings and O'Dowd, 1990; Jennings et al., 1994). Additionally, electron-microscopic analyses were carried out to relate the volatility results to specific particles sizes (Kreidenweis et al., 1998). These volatility measurements are of advantage since they allow to investigate aerosols in small concentrations with fast sampling time (order of one hour). The results of the measurements, however, are ambiguous since the analysis method is not size-resolved and the results do not reveal to which particular, initial size class the heating-based changes in the particle number concentration can be ascribed to. An improved technique represents the adoption of a volatility tandem differential mobility analyzer (VTDMA) to separate quasi-monodisperse particles and measure the residual size distributions after conditioning (Rader and McMurry, 1986). This VTDMA technique was used to investigate volatile sulfate compounds of arctic aerosols up to temperatures of 250 °C (Covert and Heintzenberg, 1993) and to identify the aerosol sulfuric acid fraction with temperatures up to 130 °C (Orsini et al., 1999). The study of the thermal effects on selective submicrometer particle sizes to characterize the non-volatile aerosol content, implying particle conditioning to 300 °C, has not been performed until up to this work and is extensively discussed herein.

2.3.2. Optical and Morphological Methods

Optical methods focus on the measurement of the carbon fractions that affect the absorption of light. Black carbon is considered the most effective particulate absorber for visible light. Few other compounds exist (e.g., the mineral dust compound '*hematite*') that have a light absorption comparable to that of BC. They are of influence only when large amounts in the particles are available (Bohren and Huffman, 1983). The optical methods are based on measuring the decrease of transmitted light due to light-absorbing particles which is directly related to the BC content. Commonly used methods are e.g., the **aethalometer** (Hansen et al., 1983), **Particle Soot/Absorption Photometer** (PSAP), and 4-wavelength **Soot Photometer** (Bussemer, 1998). Since these instruments require calibration with BC samples of known composition, the derived BC content is associated with uncertainties due to the variety of existing carbon types. The morphology of non-volatile carbon particles can be observed by **transmission electron microscopy** (TEM). A beam of highly focused electrons is directed towards the substrate, thus, producing characteristic radiation and information regarding the microstructure of the respective species. TEM allows to characterize the agglomerated structure of individual carbon particles (cf. Fig. 2-4b).

3. DEVELOPMENT OF THE VOLATILITY ANALYZER

3.1. OBJECTIVES

The goal of this study is the development of an experimental, in-situ method allowing to determine non-volatile aerosol fractions of size-segregated atmospheric particles by evaporating their volatile components and successively quantifying their resulting refractory material. The method should provide results with high temporal resolution and for small atmospheric concentrations. The investigation of the volatile behavior is focused on small, submicrometer particles where conventional experimental methods are insufficient due to the lack of particle mass. This volatility technique involves the following steps:

- ▶ Selection of quasi-monodisperse particles from a polydisperse aerosol population and quantification of their number concentration.
- ▶ Conditioning of these quasi-monodisperse particles by heating them to a specific temperature, leaving the non-volatile compound with respect to the chosen heating temperature behind.
- ▶ Determination of the residual number size distribution of the refractory material.
- ▶ Quantification of non-volatile number and volume fractions of the refractory material to infer chemical information about non-volatile aerosol components.

Based on the measurements of volatile marine aerosol components using a volatility analyzer (Orsini et al., 1999), its principles are adopted and extended to allow a fast thermal conditioning to high temperatures for the evaporation of the entire volatile material. The measurement technique and the design of the new volatility analyzer are described in the following chapter.

3.2. DESIGN OF THE VTDMA

A schematic of the developed **V**olatility **T**andem **D**ifferential **M**obility Analyzer (VTDMA) is illustrated in Figure 3.1. The instrument consists of three parts:

3.2.1. Particle Selection

In the first part of the system, polydisperse aerosol particles are passed through a neutralizer to achieve bipolar charge equilibrium (cf. Appendix A.1). With the differential mobility analyzer DMA-1 (cf. Appendix A.2) charged particles of a defined narrow mobility width ΔZ_p are selected from an aerosol population. This is realized with a DMA operated at a constant voltage corresponding to the particle mobility Z_p , i.e., the particle diameter D_p , of interest. Particles below diameters of about 80 nm are assumed to be solely singly-charged (cf. Chap 3.3). The sheath air is adjusted to a flow rate of $20 \text{ l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, complying with an aerosol flow rate of $2 \text{ l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, thus,

Figure 3-1. Schematic of Volatility Tandem Differential Mobility Analyzer (VTDMA).

establishing an aerosol-to-sheath air ratio, β , of 0.1. The flow rates are manually adjusted to ensure flow equilibrium inside the DMA on a regular basis. Pressurized sheath and excess air are regulated to eliminate any flow fluctuations inside the system. The sheath air is dried and carried through a citric acid filter to exclude traces of e.g. ammonium entering the system that would neutralize sulfuric acid on the particles. The relative humidity (RH) of the sheath air before the DMA-1 and in its excess air (sheath air plus aerosol flow) are continuously monitored with RH-sensors (Vaisala, HMP 230). RH in the DMA is typically on the order of 0 to 5 %. The resulting flow of quasi-monodisperse aerosol particles after DMA-1 is directed through a small mixing chamber to guarantee a homogeneous particle profile inside the sampling tube. The flow is subsequently split to simultaneously determine the concentration of the initially selected particles with a Condensation Particle Counter CPC-1 (cf. Appendix A.3) and to direct the remainder of the flow to the conditioning unit. All aerosol lines of the VTDMA system consist of stainless steel tubes with an inner and outer diameter of 4 and 6.35 mm, respectively. The transport tubes are designed with minimal distance and number of bends. The flow through the sampling lines is maintained laminar, holding a Reynold number of $Re = 350$ (cf. Appendix D).

3.2.2. Particle Conditioning

After size selection, the quasi-monodisperse particles are passed on to a conditioning unit where it is thermally conditioned to predefined temperatures. The heating unit comprises eight heating columns, each being maintained at a fixed temperature between ambient and a maximum of 300 °C. The setup of different heating paths enables instantaneous switching between different temperatures. The selection of a pertinent heating column is realized by a valve assembly (magnetic valves Type JMEH-5/2- $\frac{1}{8}$ -S, Festo, Chemnitz) on top and at the bottom of each column and is software-controlled. Each column consists of an inner, 6.35 mm-stainless steel tube for the aerosol flow (cf. Fig. 3-2). The tube is surrounded by a second, 25.4 mm-steel tube filled with sand to act as buffer between heating coil and aerosol line. A glass-silk heating wire (Type WK 401/401030, 24 V, 120 W, Winkler, Heidelberg) is coiled around the outer tube and allows fast heating of the aerosol. Sand reacts slowly to small temperature changes and guarantees a stable and homogeneous temperature field. The tubes are furthermore surrounded by a thick layer of glass padding and an additional quartz fiber fleece for insulation. At the bottom of each column a thermocouple of 95 mm length and 1 mm diameter (Fe-CuNi, Ruger, Stuttgart) is inserted into the center of the aerosol tube with its tip being at a distance of 36 mm from the end of the heating path to continuously measure the aerosol temperature. The analog signals of the eight temperature sensors are relayed to the software system and corrected with an appropriate temperature coefficient according to DIN 43710 (Deutsche Industrial Norm). The software digitally controls the heater via software-PID regulator to maintain automatically the temperature inside the inner tube at a setpoint temperature with deviations less than 2 %.

Figure 3-2. Schematic of a single VTDMA heating column.

After entering the conditioning tube, the aerosol particles are heated from the wall boundary to the center by conduction. The temperature field inside the tube and the evaporation rate particles was simulated by a model to verify that the residence time in the heating path is sufficient for complete evaporation of these particles (cf. Appendix B). The calculations were limited to sulfuric acid particles since thermodynamic data, e.g. for ammonium sulfate and ammonium bisulfate particles, were not available. Therefore, the evaporation of these substances was examined experimentally using artificial aerosols in the laboratory. The calibration study is discussed in detail in the following chapter (cf. Chap. 4). For thermal particle conditioning, the temperatures in the heating tube are chosen between ambient (about 25 °C) and 300 °C. Ambient temperatures are selected as reference for the unconditioned aerosol particles, 300 °C is the maximum temperature technically feasible for this setup to evaporate the volatile particle fractions. Temperatures above 300 °C require carrier gases such as helium or nitrogen to avoid measurement artifacts due to charring of the organic matter which may lead to an overestimate of measured non-volatile material. Intermediate temperature steps are chosen to distinguish between more or less volatile constituents.

3.2.3. Measurement of Particle Number Size Distribution

Aerosol particles ensuing from the thermal conditioning process are passed on to the third part of the system to determine their resulting number size distribution, termed in this study as ‘*residual size distribution*’ or ‘*(non-) volatility size distribution*’. The size distribution is determined by a second DMA-2 scanning a range of particle diameters in combination with a second CPC-2 to measure the particle concentrations in each channel. An example of resulting volatility size distributions of both, ambient and conditioned particles is demonstrated in Figure 3-3.

Figure 3-3. Illustration of volatility size distributions of particles exposed to ambient and elevated temperatures, revealing a multi-modal structure after the conditioning process.

DMA-2 is operated in a scanning mode by stepping the mobility window created by the DMA across the mobility distribution (i.e., scanning the range of diameters with an appropriate number of channels or size bins). The total time for a CPC to determine the concentration at one particular DMA-2 channel is adjusted to between 8 – 10 sec during which the DMA voltage is kept constant. An additional waiting time of 5 sec between the different channels is adopted to allow CPC-2 to adapt to the new particle size. Generally, DMA-2 is operated at an aerosol-to-sheath air flow ratio β of 0.2 (aerosol flow rate of 1 l·min⁻¹, sheath air flow rate of 5 l·min⁻¹). Midpoint diameter and shape of the transfer function Ω depend on the design of the specific DMA, i.e., geometry, actual flow rates through the DMA, and applied voltage to center rod (Knutson and Whitby, 1975). A high size resolution decreases the temporal resolution (and vice versa). Therefore, the number of size bins and the DMA-2 scan range vary during the different experiments and are optimized to respective measurement conditions. An individual volatility scan comprises approximately 6 to 8 min and amounts to about 30 min for four different temperature steps. Thus, the determination of volatility distributions at, e.g., three particle diameters, encompasses about 1 ½ to 2 hours before being repeated.

3.3. DATA INVERSION

The measured particle number concentration downstream of DMA-2 is not the true number size distribution resulting from the conditioning process, but represents the convolution of the actual distribution with the DMA transfer function Ω (Knutson et al., 1975), as illustrated in Fig. 3-4.

Figure 3-4. Transformation of particle size distribution through VTDMA.

Therefore, the actual volatility size distribution measured by DMA-2 needs to be recalculated using a rather complex data inversion algorithm. Different methods have been used in the past to invert particle size distribution measured in a TDMA (cf. Appendix C). The data inversion algorithm

employed for our VTDMA measurements was developed by Voutilainen et al. (2000). For simplification, the data inversion is discussed in terms of particle diameter, bearing in mind that the actual size is defined by the mobility-equivalent diameter selected with the DMA. This algorithm describes the relation between the unknown ('true') size distribution $n_2(x)$ and the measured particle concentration $N_2(p)$ downstream of DMA-2 as

$$N_2(p) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k(x; p) n_2(x) dx + \varepsilon . \quad (3-1)$$

k denotes the kernel function consisting of DMA transfer function, charge distribution function, and CPC counting efficiency function (cf. Appendix A.3). p is a parameter vector containing temperature, midpoint mobility, flow rates and other system-specific parameters. x is the logarithm of the particle size, and ε the associated measurement error. The observed equation (Eqn. 3-1) is discretized and expressed in matrix form. Accurate solutions that satisfy the required stability criterion are achieved with the aid of the *Tikhonov regularization* (Lloyd et al., 1997). This technique uses a weighted, non-homogeneous smoothing procedure and thereby allows to reconstruct e.g., narrow peaks without over-emphasizing outside peak regions.

VTDMA measurements (i.e., DMA-based measurements in general) are based on classifying particles according to their mobility-equivalent diameter. At particle diameters above approximately 80 nm the occurrence of multiply-charged particles becomes significant (cf. Appendix A-2). This implies that particles at a selected mobility contain not only singly-charged particles but also doubly- or triply-charged particles of correspondingly larger sizes. For example, singly-charged particles of 150 nm diameter have the same mobility as doubly-charged particles at 235 nm and triply-charged particles at 313 nm. According to the calculated bipolar charge equilibrium their occurrence corresponds to about 28 % (singlets), 13 % (doublets), and approximately 5 % (triplets)¹ (Wiedensohler, 1989; Keady et al., 1983). The above inversion algorithm (similar to any TDMA inversion algorithm) assumes that the bipolar charge distribution remains unaltered during conditioning and that the particles are only singly-charged. Corrections with respect to multiple charges can not be made since i) the number concentrations of the multiply-charged particle diameters are unknown, and ii) the diameter shift of the multiply-charged particles due to conditioning can not be distinguished from that of singly-charged particles. This induces an uncertainty in the measurements which can be estimated roughly in the individual cases and is generally in the order of approximately 10 to 15 %, including errors due to counting statistics (Poisson) and measurement instabilities (e.g., of the flow rates, DMA voltages).

All measured volatility size distributions during this study represent inverted size distributions. The inverted solutions are corrected in an ensuing step for the transport efficiency in the VTDMA system (cf. Chap. 4) and the counting efficiencies of the CPCs (cf. Appendix A.3). The parameterization of the result is discussed in the following subchapter (cf. Chap. 3.4).

¹ The values are given for the negatively charged particles only.

3.4. DERIVED AEROSOL FRACTIONS

The interpretation of VTDMA data requires a parameterization of the inverted results. The inverted number size distribution, termed in the following as $dN/d\log D_p$, can be quantified by considering relative number and volume fractions, $\Phi_{N,i}$ and $\Phi_{V,i}$, respectively. $\Phi_{N,i}$ and $\Phi_{V,i}$ are defined as ratio of the integrated number ($N_{total,i^\circ C}$) and volume ($V_{total,i^\circ C}$) concentration (cf. Fig. 3-5) after a single heating step versus the concentration of the initially selected particle diameter at ambient temperature, $N_{total,25^\circ C}$ and $V_{total,25^\circ C}$, respectively. $\Phi_{N,i}$ and $\Phi_{V,i}$ specify the residual particle fraction at temperature i as

$$\text{number fraction } \Phi_{N,i} = \frac{N_{total,i^\circ C}}{N_{total,25^\circ C}}, \text{ and} \quad (3-2)$$

$$\text{volume fraction } \Phi_{V,i} = \frac{V_{total,i^\circ C}}{V_{total,25^\circ C}}. \quad (3-3)$$

Figure 3-5. Integrated number and volume concentrations of ambient ($N_{total,25^\circ C}$, $V_{total,25^\circ C}$) and conditioned ($N_{total,i^\circ C}$, $V_{total,i^\circ C}$) aerosol particles to temperature i .

N_{total} is calculated from integrating the measured number size concentration as

$$N_{total} = \int_{D_p, \min}^{D_p, \max} \frac{dN}{d \log D_p} \cdot d \log D_p. \quad (3-4)$$

$D_{p,\min}$ and $D_{p,\max}$ denote the minimum and maximum particle diameter measured. The number size distribution is converted to the volume size distribution $dV/d\log D_p$ (cf. Eqn. 3-5) from which the total volume V_{total} can be derived (cf. Eqn. 3-6):

$$\frac{dV}{d \log D_p} = \frac{\pi}{6} \cdot D_p^3 \cdot \frac{dN}{d \log D_p}, \quad (3-5)$$

$$V_{\text{total}} = \int_{D_{p,\min}}^{D_{p,\max}} \frac{dV}{d \log D_p} \cdot d \log D_p. \quad (3-6)$$

Furthermore, if pronounced peaks, i.e., modes exist in the resulting distribution, the size ratio $\Phi_{D_{p,i}}^j$ describes the ratio of the geometric mean diameters of resulting to initial mode, as

$$\text{size ratio } \Phi_{D_{p,i}}^j = \frac{D_{p,i^\circ C}^j}{D_{p,25^\circ C}}, \quad (3-7)$$

with j indicating the respective mode in a j -modal size distribution. The mean mode diameters $D_{p,25^\circ C}$ of the initial distribution, and $D_{p,i^\circ C}^j$ of the final distribution, respectively, are derived from parameterizing the inverted number size distributions with Gaussian modes.

4. CALIBRATION OF THE VTDMA SYSTEM

The performance of the VTDMA instrument is characterized in the laboratory to correct the measured atmospheric data. Corrections are necessary due to the complexity of the specific sampling system which may affect the physico-chemical nature of the aerosol. The calibration measurements are intended to determine

- the sampling and transport efficiency of the aerosol particles through the VTDMA system which is decreased due to diffusional and thermophoretic losses, and
- the temperatures necessary to volatilize particular aerosol compounds, allowing to differentiate between volatile and non-volatile particle constituents.

The calibration procedure is performed with artificial test aerosols of predefined composition. The methods are discussed in the following.

4.1. DETERMINATION OF AEROSOL TRANSPORT EFFICIENCY

Losses of particles through the VTDMA system are caused by diffusional and thermophoretic processes. Total particles losses can be obtained from either model calculations or from direct measurements. Since theoretical studies of diffusion and thermophoresis in the VTDMA system are not straightforward (cf. Appendix D), the particle transport efficiency is determined experimentally by measuring the total particle losses through the entire tubing system. Diffusional and thermophoretic deposition is size- and temperature-dependent, therefore, loss measurements are performed for a series of particle diameters and heater temperatures. For the penetration measurements, artificial test aerosols are utilized that are easily generated and unaffected by evaporative processes inside the heating path, i.e., that are non-volatile above maximum VTDMA heater temperatures (300 °C). Adequate stable aerosols are, e.g., sodium chloride (NaCl) or silver (Ag) particles, which start to evaporate at temperatures above 600 and 900 °C, respectively. For this setup, NaCl is employed since it requires a lower volatilization temperature and enables a simpler generation of particles between 15 and 150 nm. The aerosol generation setup is shown in Figure 4-1. It consists of a tube furnace generator (Type D-02 GTE, Ströhlein Instruments, GSM, Neuss), containing a 80 cm ceramic tube with an inner diameter of 15 mm. Near the center of the furnace a ceramic boat is positioned carrying bulk aerosol material which is vaporized into a regulated carrier air stream. Upon heating, particles are formed by homogeneous nucleation and subsequent condensation in the colder section of the tube. Particle formation takes place for NaCl at furnace temperatures above 600 °C. Flow rates and furnace temperatures are varied in order to generate polydisperse aerosols in the size range of interest.

Higher evaporation temperatures increase the mass of condensable NaCl-vapor which enables the particles to grow to larger sizes (Scheibel and Porstendörfer, 1983). Higher flow rates increase the cooling rate of the gas-vapor mixture which broadens the width of the size distribution. The carrier gas flow rate Q_a through the furnace is varied between 1.5 and 2.5 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. Occasionally, additional quench air (at 1.5 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) is used to quench coagulation and condensation processes. Furthermore, the concentration of the generated polydisperse particles is adjusted in a dilution unit. Subsequently, the particles are passed on to a DMA with associated CPC to measure the number size distribution.

Figure 4-1. Schematic of the aerosol generation setup using NaCl particles. Q_a and Q_q refer to the gas flow through the furnace and the quench air flow, respectively.

Examples of resulting particle size distributions for furnace temperatures between 600 and 800 °C and varying flow rates are presented in Figure 4-2, representing mode average diameters between approximately 10 and 100 nm. After generating the polydisperse aerosol, the particles are passed on to the VTDMA system. The transport efficiency $\eta_{\text{diff+thermo}}$ within the system is determined by comparing the concentration of selected particle sizes at the outlet of DMA-1 (n_{initial}) with that at the inlet of DMA-2 (n_{final}), i.e., before and after the heating path, using CPC-1 and CPC-2, respectively. The experimental setup is illustrated in Figure 4-3. The transport efficiency is, thus, obtained by

$$\eta_{\text{diff+thermo}} = \frac{n_{\text{final}}(D_p, T)}{n_{\text{initial}}(D_p)} \quad (4-1)$$

with $n_{\text{final}}(D_p, T)$ denoting the total particle number concentration after exiting the conditioning unit, and $n_{\text{initial}}(D_p)$ the initial particle number concentration of the selected monodisperse aerosol. CPC-1 and CPC-2 are different instruments and, thus, have slightly different counting efficiencies with respect to particle diameter which were considered according to Appendix A.3.

Figure 4-2. Particle size distributions for different furnace temperatures and flow rates of NaCl aerosol particles. The amplitudes of the approximately log-normal distributions are dependent on the dilution ratio.

Figure 4-3. Experimental setup for measuring VTDMA transport efficiency, indicating the measurement points, $n_{initial}$ and n_{final} , and the selected particle diameters and conditioning temperatures.

The selected particle diameters are chosen in the size range between 8 and 150 nm. The conditioning temperatures are in the range between 25 °C and 300 °C, with each column being fixed at one particular temperature. For calibration, particles at different diameters are heated to the different temperatures. The resulting, measured transmission efficiencies are illustrated in Figure 4-4. The measurement points are fitted with an exponential five-parameter fit (Eqn. 4-2), with the parameters given in Table 4-1:

$$\eta_{fit} = a + b_1(1 - \exp(-\frac{D_p}{c_1})) + b_2(1 - \exp(-\frac{D_p}{c_2})) . \quad (4-2)$$

The curves demonstrate the dependence of the transport efficiency on particle diameter and conditioning temperature. The efficiency decreases with decreasing particle size and increasing temperature. At a particle size of 150 nm the measured efficiency reaches 96 % at ambient temperatures and drops to 81 % at 300 °C. At 50 nm, between 90 and 76 % of particles are transmitted, and only 85 to 67 % of 35 nm particles pass through the system. Below 30 nm, the efficiency curves show a steep decrease due to diffusion (cf. Appendix D) and drop to a 50 % efficiency at particle diameters between 10 and 20 nm, corresponding to 25 and 300 °C, respectively.

Figure 4-4. Transport efficiency curves of the VTDMA as a function of particle diameter and conditioning temperature. The symbols represent averaged values of the measured efficiencies along with their standard deviation (error bars), the lines denote the exponential fits of the measurements.

T [°C]	a	b ₁	c ₁	b ₂	c ₂
25	-6.22E+02	6.79E+02	3.23E+00	3.84E+01	2.64E+01
70	-1.20E+03	1.24E+03	2.42E+00	5.07E+01	2.08E+01
100	-1.46E+03	1.48E+03	2.11E+00	7.72E+01	1.38E+01
120	-1.28E+03	1.29E+03	2.25E+00	7.93E+01	1.47E+01
140	-6.74E+02	7.02E+02	2.95E+00	5.92E+01	1.65E+01
160	-4.28E+05	4.28E+05	7.79E-01	1.25E+02	1.20E+01
180	-3.63E+03	3.58E+03	1.49E+00	1.34E+02	1.08E+01
190	-3.63E+03	3.58E+03	3.10E-04	1.33E+02	1.09E+01
220	-5.38E+03	5.41E+03	2.10E+00	5.74E+01	1.70E+01
240	-2.30E+02	2.98E+02	5.78E+00	1.61E+01	4.32E+01
250	-3.01E+03	2.95E+03	5.00E-05	1.51E+02	1.63E+01
300	-5.44E+02	6.12E+02	6.44E+00	1.37E+01	6.07E+01

Table 4-1. Parameters of the five-parameter fits of the VTDMA transport efficiency as used in Eqn. 4-2.

Based on the results of the calibration, volatility measurements with the VTDMA below diameters corresponding to a 50 % counting efficiency are associated with a high uncertainty. In the following, the measured VTDMA transport efficiencies, termed as ‘*VTDMA efficiency*’, are applied to the individual volatility size distributions to correct for the losses based on diffusional and thermophoretic deposition in the sampling lines.

4.2. EVAPORATION OF VOLATILE AEROSOL COMPONENTS

The second part of the calibration measurements focus on investigating the volatility of particular quasi-monodisperse aerosols compounds. The transfer of particle mass from the solid to the gaseous state (and reverse) is a function of the temperature-dependent thermodynamic properties (e.g., vapor pressure, chemical potential, diffusion coefficient, mean free path) of the different compounds and the residence times of the particles within the system. A temperature increase in a system containing airborne particles will tend to shift the equilibrium of the system towards the gas phase. Certain compounds (e.g., ammonium sulfate) might also decompose before they change into the gaseous state which affects their evaporation rate. Model calculations can be performed to obtain evaporation rates of particles of known composition in the conditioning path of the VTDMA system. For example, the evaporation rate of pure sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) particles was modeled using an aerosol dynamics model (Appendix B). The residence time of 150 nm H₂SO₄ particles in the conditioning path at 300 °C was calculated to be below 32 ms until they were completely evaporated (the total residence time of the particles in the elevated temperature field was 297 ms). However, similar modeling of other aerosol components or compounds is not straightforward, and corresponding thermodynamic data are not always available. Therefore, the volatile behavior of laboratory aerosols of predefined composition in the VTDMA system is determined experimentally. Various particle compounds are tested for their characteristic *volatility temperature* (i.e., temperature at which a compound is completely evaporated) in the VTDMA system. Assuming sulfate to be the dominant submicrometer aerosol component, the goals of these

measurements are: i) to determine the volatility temperature of sulfuric acid and of its neutralized products, ammonium sulfate ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$) and ammonium bisulfate (NH_4HSO_4), i.e., to discriminate between all three sulfate compounds; ii) to identify the non-volatile, refractory particle fraction (cf. Chap. 2). Nitrate (i.e., often in the form of NH_4NO_3) is found to be more volatile than sulfate (Bassett and Seinfeld, 1984; Rood et al., 1985; O'Dowd and Smith, 1993) and is, therefore, not investigated during the laboratory measurements. Previous studies adopted the volatility technique solely to polydisperse aerosols particles and derived temperatures at which various species vaporize. Such particles, consisting of sulfuric acid and other volatile compounds (e.g., ammonium nitrate, ammonium chloride), were found to evaporate at temperatures between 70 and 150 °C, typically at 100 – 110 °C for sulfuric acid (Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; O'Dowd and Smith, 1993; Smith and O'Dowd, 1996; Cantrell et al., 1997; Kreidenweis et al., 1998). Ammonium sulfate and bisulfate were found to evaporate at temperatures between approximately 180 °C and 220 °C (Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; Rood et al., 1987; O'Dowd and Smith, 1993; Hudson and Da, 1996; Smith and O'Dowd, 1996). Around 300 °C, all the above mentioned components have evaporated completely and the remaining, particulate material is termed '*refractory*'. Compared to polydisperse particles specific, quasi-monodisperse particles might exhibit a different volatile behavior due to their smaller mass. In order to determine temperatures that allow to distinguish between the more and less volatile submicrometer aerosol compounds, VTDMA laboratory measurements are performed with laboratory-generated sulfuric acid, ammonium sulfate, and ammonium bisulfate aerosols.

Aerosol particles of different composition are generated using a constant output, recirculating atomizer (TSI model 3076, Minneapolis, MN). The experimental setup is illustrated in Fig. 4-5. Filtered, gaseous nitrogen is used in the system as carrier gas due to its inert behavior and to avoid neutralization reactions of, e.g., sulfuric acid and ammonium bisulfate. As the compressed air enters the atomizer through a small intake hole (0.343 mm diameter) it forms a high-velocity jet.

Figure 4-5. Schematic of aerosol generation setup to produce H_2SO_4 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, and NH_4HSO_4 particles. Q_a and Q_d refer to the gas flow of the atomizer and the additional dilution air flow, respectively.

The solution is thereby drawn through a vertical hole from below and then nebulized by the jet as it expands. Large droplets are removed by impaction on the wall opposite the jet and the finer droplets leave the atomizer at the top. Since the exiting aerosol particles are wet, they are further diluted with a flow of nitrogen Q_d and passed through a liquid trap. The aerosol flow rate from the atomizer Q_a is approximately $2 \text{ l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, that of the dilution gas Q_d about $3 \text{ l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. A dilution unit is used to adjust the number concentration of the particles to be measured. Since the generated particles have a high electrostatic charge, the aerosols are neutralized subsequently with a bipolar charger (cf. Appendix A.1) before entering the measurement system. To monitor the output of the atomizer, a DMA and CPC are used to measure the resulting size distributions (cf. Fig. 4-6). The mean particle size of the generated aerosol is determined by the concentration of the solution. A concentration of 0.1 %_m (*percent by mass*) is appropriate to produce H_2SO_4 , NH_4HSO_4 , and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ particles up to 200 nm. The 0.1 %_m H_2SO_4 -solution is prepared by using 1.05 ml of a 95 %_m- H_2SO_4 -solution per 1 liter of deionized water (Milli-Q, $18.2 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$). Corresponding 0.1 %_m $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - and NH_4HSO_4 -solution is produced with 1 mg of solute per 1 liter of deionized water. The size distributions of the sulfate particles generated with the atomizer are generally broader compared to the NaCl distributions produced with the tube furnace generator (cf. Fig. 4-2). Sulfuric acid tends to be easily neutralized by traces of ammonium being present, therefore, the solution is reproduced on a daily basis. Since ammonium sulfate and ammonium bisulfate solutions are stable they are utilized on average for two to three days.

Figure 4-6. Size distributions of ammonium sulfate and ammonium bisulfate aerosols generated with the atomizer.

The generated, polydisperse aerosol particles are passed through the VTDMA system to measure their volatility. The volatility distributions are recorded for selected particle diameters (15 - 150 nm) at different temperatures from ambient up to the maximum temperature at which the particles are completely evaporated. Since smaller particles volatilize more rapidly than larger particles at the same temperature (due to smaller mass), results for the largest particles (150 nm diameter) are presented only. The resulting volatility scans of 150 nm sulfuric acid, ammonium

bisulfate, and ammonium bisulfate are displayed in Figure 4-7. The individual scans are normalized with respect to the maximum concentration at 25 °C. For the initial 150 nm particles, the curves show a shift of the volatility size distributions to decreasing particle diameters with increasing conditioning temperatures. The H₂SO₄ particles start to evaporate at relatively low temperatures: at 70 °C a large fraction has already vaporized. At a temperature T_{vapor} of 140 °C the entire sulfuric acid aerosol is essentially vaporized. For initially selected 100 nm particles (not shown here) the results are similar, for smaller, initially selected diameters (15, 35, 50 nm) the aerosol is completely evaporated at even lower temperatures around approximately 120 °C. The results are slightly different for NH₄HSO₄ and (NH₄)₂SO₄ aerosols, showing a complete vaporization of 150 nm particles at temperatures of about 180 °C, i.e., at higher temperatures than for H₂SO₄ particles.

Figure 4-7. Averaged volatility size distributions of (a) H₂SO₄, (b) NH₄HSO₄, and (c) (NH₄)₂SO₄ aerosol particles at initial 150 nm and denoted conditioning temperatures.

Differences between NH₄HSO₄ and (NH₄)₂SO₄ are not very strong and not as easily distinguished as with, e.g., temperature-controlled nephelometry (Rood et al., 1987). It is obvious that for cases (b) and (c) at 70 °C only small amounts of the aerosol mass evaporate, the majority vaporizes between 70 and 120 °C. Nevertheless, the evaporation process seems to be initiated somewhat earlier in the case of NH₄HSO₄, with more mass having evaporated around 100 °C and 180 °C, respectively. In the case of smaller particles (15 – 100 nm), the volatility temperature T_{vapor} is correspondingly decreased by approximately 40 °C. The results of individual sulfuric acid particles basically confirm those found in earlier studies, having volatility temperatures between 70 and 150 °C. Orsini et al. (Orsini et al., 1999), using a volatility analyzer at lower temperatures, found a complete vaporization of 150 nm H₂SO₄ particles at approximately 110 °C but observed no significant evaporation of ammonium sulfate and bisulfate particles up to 150 °C. The volatility

temperatures for quasi-monodisperse NH_4HSO_4 and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ particles in this study do not correspond with those for corresponding samples containing a large particle size range, but are decreased by about 80 °C, being in the volatility range of sulfuric acid. These results are, therefore, novel with respect to the evaporation of individual, size-segregated particles. The temperature-dependent volatile fractions (*'fractionation curves'*) of H_2SO_4 , NH_4HSO_4 , and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ are displayed in Figure 4-8 with respect to their number, volume, and size (cf. Chap. 3.4). The particle

Figure 4-8. Number, volume, and size fractionation curves derived from volatility size distributions of H_2SO_4 , NH_4HSO_4 , and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ aerosols for initial 150 nm particles as a function of conditioning temperatures.

number fractions of all compounds remain constant up to about 100 °C, thereafter, sulfuric acid shows the strongest and ammonium sulfate the flattest decrease. With respect to the volume fractions, ammonium sulfate and bisulfate are not distinguishable and the volume decrease of sulfuric acid is initiated at lower temperatures. Accordingly, the size fractionation curves of ammonium sulfate and bisulfate particles are similar, reaching 50 % in diameter at approximately 120 – 130 °C, but already at approximately 110 °C for sulfuric acid particles. Individual, quantitative results are summarized in Table 4-2.

Fraction	Compound	Temperature [°C]				
		70	100	120	140	180
$\Phi_{N,i}$ [%]	H_2SO_4	102 ± 3	101 ± 5	89 ± 12	1 ± 0	0 ± 0
	NH_4HSO_4	97 ± 5	99 ± 41	77	13 ± 8	0 ± 0
	$(NH_4)_2SO_4$	97 ± 1	98 ± 3	78 ± 24	36 ± 20	0 ± 0
$\Phi_{V,i}$ [%]	H_2SO_4	39 ± 2	24 ± 1	6 ± 1	0 ± 0	0 ± 0
	NH_4HSO_4	95 ± 4	66 ± 26	11	0 ± 0	0 ± 0
	$(NH_4)_2SO_4$	91 ± 0.8	67 ± 2	17 ± 5	1 ± 1	0 ± 0
$\Phi_{Dp,i}$ [%]	H_2SO_4	70	58	39	-	-
	NH_4HSO_4	99	89	55	11	-
	$(NH_4)_2SO_4$	99	89	65	32	-

Table 4-2. Number fraction $\Phi_{N,i}$, volume fraction $\Phi_{V,i}$, and size ratio $\Phi_{Dp,i}$ (in %) of initial 150 nm particles consisting of sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), ammonium bisulfate (NH_4HSO_4), and ammonium sulfate ($(NH_4)_2SO_4$), respectively, as a function of conditioning temperature. Indicated are average values and associated standard deviations.

The results of these laboratory calibrations eliminate the possibility of a clear-cut discrimination among the different sulfate compounds based on their volatility temperature. Although the onset of the evaporation of sulfuric acid takes place at lower temperatures than its neutralized products, its vaporization is not completed up to temperatures where ammonium sulfate and bisulfate already have lost the majority of their fractions with respect to particle number and volume. For sulfuric acid, however, derived results can be employed to identify how well the atmospheric aerosol is ‘aged’. Aged aerosols are less likely to contain much sulfuric acid which is easily neutralized by trace amounts of ammonium. Thus, aged particles can be identified by relatively stable aerosol number and volume fractions around 70 – 80 °C. A differentiation between ammonium sulfate and ammonium bisulfate remains speculative. The volume fraction of both can not be distinguished as a function of temperature since their volume fractionation curves are identical. Their number and size fractionation curves are similar up to a temperature of about 120 °C. Thereafter, ammonium bisulfate decreases somewhat stronger as a function of temperature up to 180 °C compared to ammonium sulfate, but these differences are minor. These results show that the adoption of VTDMA conditioning temperatures up to 180 °C allow us to separate all volatile and the sulfate compounds. At even higher temperatures, i.e., between 180 °C and 280 - 300 °C a portion of less volatile organic carbon compounds might evaporate as well, leaving only the non-volatile fractions behind.

A volatility analyzer has been used previously with size-segregated particles at lower temperatures to measure the volatile sulfuric acid fraction of marine aerosols (Orsini et al., 1999). However, this volatility technique is for the first time applied to quasi-monodisperse aerosol particles in this temperature range. Compared to volatility studies of polydisperse aerosol particles (Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; Rood et al., 1987; O’Dowd and Smith, 1993; Hudson and Da, 1996; Smith and O’Dowd, 1996) or bulk samples of particles, the investigation of the volatile behavior of

monodisperse aerosol particles revealed much lower volatility temperatures. As a result of above calibrations, all following VTDMA studies of atmospheric aerosol particles are performed at four characteristic temperatures steps:

- ① 25 °C: Ambient temperature as standard for the unconditioned aerosol and as a reference.
- ② 80 °C: Temperature to evaporate strongly volatile compounds (e.g., nitrate compounds) and a large portion of sulfuric acid. Ammonium sulfate and bisulfate are stable.
- ③ 180 °C: Temperature to completely evaporate ammonium sulfate and bisulfate, or other volatile compounds.
- ④ 280 °C: Temperature to evaporate volatile carbonaceous compounds. Residual species above 280 °C are considered **refractory**.

Concluding, it can be inferred from the volatility measurements for particles equal or smaller than 150 nm that above 180 °C ammonium bisulfate and ammonium sulfate are completely evaporated. All compounds of atmospheric aerosol samples remaining after heating to 180 °C are assumed to be refractory components, presumably representing volatile, organic carbon compounds up to approximately 280 to 300 °C. Above those temperatures we assume the refractory material to be mostly consisting of non-volatile material, i.e., non-volatile (elemental or black) carbon. However, it can not be excluded entirely that a small fraction of the so-called non-volatile material in this temperature range constitutes less volatile, organic compounds or probably traces of sea salt, crustal material, and fly ash.

5. MIXING OF VOLATILE AND NON-VOLATILE AEROSOL COMPOUNDS

Previous chapters demonstrated the capability of the VTDMA system to evaporate volatile compounds from airborne aerosol particles and to measure the number size distribution of the residual, non-volatile material. Prior to applying the volatility technique to atmospheric aerosols, however, a conceptual framework is developed to explain how non-volatile compounds may be mixed within particles and how this concept relates to measurements with the developed system.

Concentration, composition, and structure of the different types of atmospheric particles is related to their origin and subsequent transformation processes. In order to study the properties of an aerosol population in a simplified way, Junge (Junge, 1952) introduced the concept of mixing state which was extended by Winkler (Winkler, 1973). According to this theory, aerosols are distinguished between externally and internally mixed. An *external mixture* of particles is assumed to comprise a variety of different chemical compounds, but each individual particle consists of only one chemical specie. *Internally mixed* particles contain several chemical substances, either homogeneously or heterogeneously mixed, but particles of the same size have identical composition. Although the mixing concept is important, e.g., for reducing the complexity of aerosol size distributions in atmospheric models, it is an idealistic one since chemical mixtures may occur in any transitional state between internal and external. However, whether the chemical mixture is primarily internal or external substantially influences the physical, chemical, and optical properties of the particles (Covert and Heintzenberg, 1984). Studies show, e.g., that an internally mixed aerosol has more light absorption than an externally mixed aerosol (Heintzenberg, 1978; Horvath, 1998). Furthermore, pure elemental carbon particles are hydrophobic, while coated soot particles show an increased hygroscopicity and absorb light much more efficiently (Bergstrom et al., 1982; Rosen and Hansen, 1984; Andrews and Larson, 1993).

With respect to volatility measurements, it will be useful to investigate the above mixing concept with respect to an aerosol population consisting of only two components, namely volatile and non-volatile compounds. For simplifications, we assume the non-volatile material to be carbonaceous and originate, e.g., from combustion processes. The concept is illustrated in Figure 5-1. In the following, three distinct (hypothetical) cases are presented that consider the size distributions of non-volatile material of a particle population in the light of possible formation, transformation, and transport processes:

1. **Aerosols at a source** of formation, representing only secondary particles (from condensation of low vapor pressure products on primary particles). Assumed is that the non-volatile material is distributed equally within individual particles of the aerosol population, i.e., the particles are internally mixed.

2. **Aerosols near different sources**, resulting from mixing of aerosol populations of different sources (as in 1). Only mixing but no transformation processes of individual particles occur. Then, the aerosol population represents an external mixture of internally mixed particles.
3. **Aerosols at a distance from sources**. The aerosol population may have been influenced by processes such as gas-to-particle mass transport (e.g., absorption, condensation), coagulation, mixing of different air masses, or deposition. The new aerosol represents a range of differently mixed particles.

Figure 5-1. Schematic of a hypothetical aerosol mixing model, considering different sources and transformation processes of particles containing varying fractions of non-volatile material and their resulting volatility size distributions.

From the ensemble of aerosol particles in each of the three cases (cf. Fig. 5-1i) those of a particular, identical diameter are selected using the volatility analyzer (cf. Fig. 5-1ii), and the distributions of non-volatile compounds of the extracted particles are measured by evaporating all volatile material (cf. Fig. 5-1iii). The three cases are discussed below:

1. The volatility size distributions of internally mixed aerosol particles at their source (case 1) has a quasi-monomodal shape with different average residual mode diameters corresponding to the different sources (A, B, ...).
2. The mixing of two particle populations of different sources consisting of internally mixed particles (case 2) produces a bimodal volatility distribution, with each mode relating to a particular source (A, B...). The more types of sources exist the more modes can be found in the residual distribution. With an increase in the number of aerosol sources, the individual modes in the residual non-volatile distribution may, therefore, become more and more indistinct.
3. Aging processes transform the initial particles, resulting in volatility distributions (case 3) very different from those in the source region. In order to understand the effects of such processes they are briefly explained in the following (note, processes iii and iv represent only transformation processes within an entire particle population and not of individual particles and, thus, are only mentioned as a matter of completeness):
 - i. **Adsorption/Condensation:** mass transfer (of volatile compounds) onto preexisting particles containing a fixed amount of non-volatile material increases their size. Therefore, smaller particles with smaller non-volatile fractions may grow into those sizes selected with the volatility analyzer. However, condensational growth (i.e., the increase in particle diameter due to condensational processes), occurs more rapidly on particles with smaller diameters (Seinfeld, 1986), thus, shifting small non-volatile ‘cores’ into the size range of interest. The condensational effect can be observed in the volatility size distribution as an overall shift towards smaller diameters of the non-volatile residuals, with the total number of particles being conserved.
 - ii. **Coagulation:** Collision of particles leads to a reduction of the total number of particles while the total volume of the aerosol population is maintained. *Brownian* coagulation is primarily governed by two parameters, particle size and number. With decreasing size, particle diffusion increases and hence, their probability of collision. With increasing particle size, the cross-sectional area for collision becomes larger. The resulting size distribution of non-volatile material strongly depends on the given distribution of non-volatile material for a given particle size during collision. For example, the average non-volatile mass fraction of a given particle resulting from coagulation of two particles can increase if one of the coagulating particles contains a larger non-volatile mass fraction, and decrease if one of the coagulating particles contains a smaller non-volatile mass fraction. Therefore, coagulation may shift the measured volatility size distribution in either direction.
 - iii. **Convection, Advection:** Transport processes can mix different air masses or change the particle concentration within an air mass without transforming the individual particles. This may re-distribute the non-volatile material for a given particle size. Thus, a measured volatility size distribution may be shifted in either direction.

iv. **Deposition:** Particles may be removed by diffusion, interception, or impaction, thus, resulting in a depletion of particles containing a given amount of non-volatile material.

Due to the above discussed processes the size distributions of non-volatile material may be altered substantially with an increasing number of sources and with increasing distance to the sources. The above defined cases represent simplified scenarios. In reality, formation and transformation processes are more complex. For example, aerosol particles originating from one particular source may contain different internally as well as externally mixed particles. Furthermore, subsequent transformation processes occur at any time after particle formation. Therefore, a particle population is influenced simultaneously by source processes, mixing, and transformation.

The usually complex distribution of non-volatile material within young or aged aerosol populations in the atmosphere does not allow us to draw conclusions about the types of sources or transformation processes. In the following, the distributions of non-volatile material will be discussed in terms of non-volatile composition of the particles. For example, one may assume two particles of identical size and a core consisting of the same non-volatile material. One core is coated with a hydrophobic, the other with a hygroscopic substance. Due to water vapor condensation, the hygroscopic particles grow more than the hydrophobic particles. Consequently, hydrophobic particles are expected to contain mostly non-volatile material whereas hygroscopic particle may take up various amounts of water. These and other particle properties may lead to a diverse non-volatile particle composition. Therefore, the concept of *quasi-non-volatile* and *partially-non-volatile* particle composition is introduced (cf. Fig. 5-2). *Quasi-non-volatile* particles

Figure 5-2. Example of volatility distributions of ambient (dotted) and conditioned (shaded) particles and partitioning of residual particles into *quasi-non-volatile* and *partially-non-volatile* particles with N_{qnv} (gray) and N_{pnv} (black), respectively.

consist almost entirely of non-volatile material. With respect to measured volatility distributions, they are characterized by the unaltered diameter after thermal conditioning, reflecting that the particles contained no evaporative material. All other particles contained variable amounts of volatile material before the conditioning process and are, therefore, denoted *partially-non-volatile*. The residual (conditioned) particles are defined *quasi-non-volatile* as long as the mode of these particles lies within the limits of the initial distribution of the ambient particles, as selected and defined by the DMA-1 transfer function. These limits can be defined quantitatively in terms of a lower and upper diameter, D_p^1 and D_p^2 , respectively (cf. Fig. 5-2). *Partially-non-volatile* particles encompass particles with various amounts of non-volatile material. Thus, the total number and volume fraction of the non-volatile material, Φ_N and Φ_V , respectively (cf. Eqn. 3-2, 3-3), can be divided in a *quasi-non-volatile* portion ($\varphi_{N,qnv}$, $\varphi_{V,qnv}$) and a *partially-non-volatile* portion ($\varphi_{N,pnv}$, $\varphi_{V,pnv}$). Both fractions, φ_{qnv} and φ_{pnv} , are expressed as

$$\varphi_{N,qnv} = \frac{N_{qnv,i^\circ C}}{N_{total,25^\circ C}}, \text{ and } \varphi_{N,pnv} = \frac{N_{pnv,i^\circ C}}{N_{total,25^\circ C}}, \quad (5-1, 5-2)$$

with respect to particle number. i denotes the conditioning temperature, N_{qnv} the integrated number of residual particles of the *quasi-non-volatile* mode, and N_{pnv} the integrated number of the *partially-non-volatile* particles (cf. Fig. 5-2). Similarly defined is the *quasi-non-volatile* and *partially-non-volatile* volume fraction, $\varphi_{V,qnv}$ and $\varphi_{V,pnv}$, as

$$\varphi_{V,qnv} = \frac{V_{qnv,i^\circ C}}{V_{total,25^\circ C}}, \text{ and } \varphi_{V,pnv} = \frac{V_{pnv,i^\circ C}}{V_{total,25^\circ C}}, \quad (5-3, 5-4)$$

The total number and volume fraction is obtained by the sum of both:

$$\Phi_N = \varphi_{N,qnv} + \varphi_{N,pnv}, \text{ and } \Phi_V = \varphi_{V,qnv} + \varphi_{V,pnv}. \quad (5-5, 5-6)$$

The modal parameters (average diameter, width, and height) of the distributions of both, *quasi-non-volatile* and *partially-non-volatile* particles may vary, depending on source, mixing, and transformation processes as described above. Although the volatility distributions of the non-volatile material may not allow to identify individual processes, the total volume of non-volatile particles is expected to increase with increasing distance to their sources.

6. APPLICATION OF THE VTDMA: NON-VOLATILE FRACTIONS OF AEROSOL PARTICLES OF DIFFERENT ORIGIN

This chapter discusses the application of the developed volatility technique to atmospheric aerosol particles. In order to investigate the volatile behavior of different aerosol types, the measurements were performed in environments of varying distance to combustion sources which are known to produce large amounts of non-volatile carbon (cf. Chap. 2). Firstly, volatility measurements of particles directly at combustion sources are presented. The following section focuses on urban aerosol particles, anticipated to still represent significant carbonaceous fractions. The last chapter discusses the volatility of moderately polluted air masses, expected to contain the smallest fractions of non-volatile material.

6.1. AEROSOLS AT COMBUSTION SOURCES

Combustion processes are a major source of airborne particulate matter. In the urban environment, motor vehicle emissions are often the main anthropogenic source of air pollution beside industrial emissions. Until recently, most of the research has been focused on the determination of mass concentrations of the emitted particles, consequentially dominated by the largest particles. However, vehicle-emitted particles are predominantly in the size range between a few nanometers and one micrometer and contribute, therefore, most to the total particle number. Submicrometer particles are found to have substantial implications for the human health. Recent epidemiological studies show that particularly the small particles have a high probability of deposition in the respiratory tract, being carcinogenic and causing pulmonary diseases and allergies (Dockery and Pope, 1994; Brunekreef et al., 1995; Bascom et al., 1996; Peters et al., 1997; Cooney, 1998; Pope and Dockery, 1999). Also, a large number of smaller particles have a greater reactive surface area than the same mass of larger particles. Vehicle exhaust represents a complex mixture of gases and fine particles and the measurement of their physico-chemical parameters is not straightforward. Furthermore, this highly heterogeneous mixture varies within and between cities, with season, weather conditions, and time of day. An experimental volatility study of a series of vehicle-emitted particles was conducted at the *FORD* emission laboratory in Cologne in June 1998.

6.1.1. Vehicle-emitted Carbonaceous Combustion Aerosols

Exhaust emissions from vehicles consist of gaseous and particulate phases, with the main gaseous compounds encompassing hydrocarbons (HCs), CO, CO₂, NO_x, and water vapor. Particulate matter, formed by the incomplete combustion of fuel, is composed of carbonaceous material (elemental and volatile, organic carbon) and sometimes small amounts of fly ash, lead, iron and other trace metals. Some of the volatile species are emitted in the gas phase and condense on the emitted particles during cooling. Type and quantity of the vehicle emissions depend on a number of factors which are, among others, the type of fuel used, the air-fuel ratio during the combustion process, and the engine speed. Diesel fuel (typically C₁₄H₃₀) contains molecules with more carbon

atoms in longer chains than gasoline fuel (typically C_9H_{20}) and has a lower vapor pressure than gasoline fuel. An ideal combustion of hydrocarbon fuel results in the production of CO_2 and H_2O and is expressed as

with x and y indicating the number of carbon and hydrogen atoms, respectively, of the particular fuel type. An air-fuel mixture resulting in a complete combustion of a given quantity of fuel with a precise amount of oxygen is termed *stoichiometric* mixture. The air-fuel ratio (AFR) is defined as the mass of oxygen per mass of fuel and is used as a measure for the amount of oxygen available during a combustion process. The stoichiometric AFR of a typical gasoline is about 14.6 (Seinfeld, 1986). A mixture containing less than the stoichiometric amount of oxygen is called *rich* (sub-stoichiometric AFR), a mixture with excess air is termed *lean* (super-stoichiometric AFR). The composition of the exhaust gas constituents as a function of the AFR is shown in Figure 6-1. A low AFR (less oxygen) leads to the formation of CO and unburnt HCs and, therefore, most

Figure 6-1. Exhaust hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide, and nitrogen oxides as a function of air-fuel ratio (AFR) (from Seinfeld (1986)).

importantly, soot. A high AFR (excess oxygen) favors NO_x formation. During different driving modes of a vehicle different air-fuel mixtures are required. For example, at higher engine speeds (*revs*) more power is needed and the mixture is, therefore, richer (Seinfeld, 1986). The air-fuel mixture is generally much leaner (higher AFR) in a diesel engine than in a spark-ignition engine, although the fraction of elemental carbon produced is higher due to the higher number of carbon versus hydrogen atoms in the diesel fuel. The air-fuel mixture is furthermore often described by the *equivalence ratio* λ (or relative AFR), defined as the ratio of the actual AFR to the stoichiometric AFR, as

$$\lambda = \frac{AFR_{actual}}{AFR_{stoich}}. \quad (6-2)$$

For $\lambda = 1$ the mixture is stoichiometric, and relative AFRs of $\lambda < 1$ and $\lambda > 1$ correspond to rich and lean mixtures, respectively. The number of particles produced depends on the nature of the combustion process (e.g., fuel, operating conditions). In general, total particulate mass emissions from spark-ignition vehicles are significantly lower than those of diesel emissions (Burtcher et al., 1998; Ristovski et al., 1998). Most emitted particles are initially produced in the Aitken particle range, but grow into the accumulation range by condensation and coagulation. Emitted exhaust is rapidly diluted in the atmosphere by several orders of magnitude. The effect of dilution on the particle size development is displayed in Figure 6-2. The total number of particles decreases rapidly with time due to coagulation, corresponding to an increase in particle diameter.

Figure 6-2. Calculated number distributions of diesel-emitted particles diluted with air by a factor of 10 as a function of time (from Kittelson and Dolan (1980)).

The combustion characteristics determine the ratio between elemental carbon and hydrocarbons. Particles emitted from spark-ignition engines are known to contain a large fraction of hydrocarbons, whereas diesel-emitted engines contain a much larger fraction of elemental carbon. The soot particles emitted from a diesel engine are typically observed as chain-like aggregates of primary spherical particles (cf. Chap. 2.2.2). They are often coated by several layers of polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). Ishiguro et al. (1997) showed that primary particles of diesel soot consist of an inner core (with a diameter of about 10 nm) with an outer shell, both revealing different structures.

6.1.2. Vehicle-emitted Aerosol Measurements at *FORD*

The measurements of vehicle-emitted aerosol particles were performed at the emission laboratory of the *FORD* company in Cologne. Besides volatility measurements, a combined Twin Differential Mobility Particle Sizer System (TDMPS) and Aerodynamic Particle Sizer (APS) were employed to record particle number size distributions in the size range 3 nm to 10 μm . The experimental setup is sketched in Figure 6-3. All test were conducted on a chassis dynamometer with a series of selected car types under various operating conditions. The selected automobiles encompassed diesel vehicles, a direct injection vehicle, gasoline vehicles, and a natural gas vehicle. The exhaust pipe of the vehicles was connected via flexible tube (stainless chrome-vanadium alloy) to a standard

particle dilution tunnel which was equipped with a constant volume sampler (CVS) to keep the emitted volume flow downstream constant for sampling. A CVS regulates the amount of dilution air added depending on the emission flow rate of the different vehicle operating conditions. The dilution air consisted of filtered ambient air. During the measurements, the dilution factor varied between 10 and 35 with a total sampling flow of $18 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. An auxiliary dilution unit was installed to additionally dilute particle-rich diesel exhaust at a ratio of 10:1. The distance between car exhaust and sampling port was approximately 14 m with residence times of the emitted particles in the sampling lines of about five seconds (cf. Fig. 6-3).

Figure 6-3. Experimental setup of vehicle-emitted particle measurements. τ_1 , τ_2 , and τ_3 denote the residence times of the emitted particles in the different sections between exhaust pipe and instruments (total residence time is 4.6 s).

According to the standard emission measurements, each test cycle was restricted to a predefined length of approximately 20 min. It encompassed an initial warm-up phase of several minutes and a subsequent phase at constant velocity, conducted at three different driving speeds of 50, 70, and 100 km/h. The velocities matched driving gears III, V, and V, with the lowest engine revolution (*rev*) occurring at 70 km/h, and maximum *rev* at 100 km/h, respectively. The results of the measurements presented in the following are limited to the constant speed phases only. The different vehicles tested are summarized in Table 6-1, along with their corresponding equivalence ratio λ , and their pertinent notation as used in this chapter.

Fuel Type	Engine Type	Notation	λ
1. Diesel	Ford Fiesta 1.8 Endura	D1	$\gg 1.5$
	Ford Mondeo 1.8 TCI	D2	$\gg 1.5$
2. Direct Injection	Mitsubishi Charisma 1.8 GDI	DIJ	> 1.0
3. Gasoline (Super)	Ford Fiesta 1.25 Zetec SE	G1	0.7 (<i>rich</i>)
		G2	1.0 (<i>stoich.</i>)
		G3	1.5 (<i>lean</i>)
	Ford Mondeo 1.8 Zetec	G4	> 1.0
4. Natural Gas	Ford Mondeo 1.8 Zetec	NG	1.0

Table 6-1. Summary of different vehicles types used for measurement, with corresponding equivalence ratio (relative AFR) λ . Each vehicle was tested at driving speeds of 50, 70, and 100 km/h.

6.1.3. The Volatile Behavior of Vehicle-emitted Particles

The VTDMA measurements were designed to retrieve volatility size distributions of representatively selected particle diameters. Due to the relatively short length of the vehicle test cycles and the required size resolution for the individual volatility scans, the VTDMA measurements were confined to a particle diameter of 50 nm, located near the maximum of the particle number size distributions (cf. Fig. 6.4). The results of the individual VTDMA scans were not verified for their reproducibility regarding selected particle size, vehicle type, or driving speed since each vehicle was solely tested once.

Figure 6-4. Averaged particle number size distributions of diesel and direct injection vehicles at different velocities, measured with the TDMPS/APS.

Each volatility distribution was measured at ambient temperature (25 °C) as a reference and at a conditioning temperature of 250 °C. An example is displayed in Figure 6-5, representing diesel-emitted particles. Due to heating of the particles in the VTDMA, the 250 °C-size distribution is shifted unimodally towards smaller particle diameters compared to the reference distribution at 25 °C as a result of the evaporation of volatile particle components. Note, all volatility size distributions presented in the following represent inverted and corrected results (cf. Chap. 3.3 and 4.1, respectively). Unless otherwise indicated, the individual distributions displayed in the figures are normalized with respect to the maximum concentration of the unconditioned particles to indicate the refractory distribution independent of the variable initial particle concentration.

Figure 6-5. Measured volatility size distributions of 50 nm particles emitted from a diesel vehicle (D1) at constant speed of 50 km/h. The scans are normalized to the maximum concentration at 25 °C.

Based on the volatile behavior of the particulate vehicle emissions, the results of the VTDMA measurements for the various car types tested during the experiment are grouped into three classes: diesel cars, direct injection vehicles, and all other cars (gasoline and natural gas). The results are discussed in the following sections.

6.1.3.1. Emissions of Diesel Vehicles

Volatility number size distributions of diesel exhaust were measured at the two diesel vehicles D1 and D2. The VTDMA results for 50 nm particles at three driving speeds are summarized in Figures 6-6, a-f. Illustrated is the reference mode (at ambient temperature) at the selected 50 nm diameter, and a second mode resulting from thermal conditioning of these particles at a temperature of 250 °C. Since the volatile components are expected to have evaporated at this temperature step, the residual material is likely to be comprised mostly of non-volatile carbon, i.e., soot. All volatility scans of the diesel vehicle D1 (cf. Fig. 6-6, a-c) are very similar and show a monomodal shift after

the thermal conditioning towards smaller particle diameters with a slight broadening of the peak. The relative number fraction Φ_N of the residual distribution (i.e., the ratio of total number concentration of 250 °C versus 25 °C (cf. Eqn. 3-2)) yields a value of $102 \pm 8 \%$, averaged over all speeds (note: a total number fraction around 100 % connotes an unchanged total particle number). The relative volume fraction Φ_V is on average $88 \pm 12 \%$, showing increasing values with speed. An increase in the fraction of non-volatile particle compounds, i.e., soot, with increasing engine load is expected due to the fact that the air-fuel mixture becomes richer. Since sub-stoichiometric AFRs favor the formation of soot we anticipate higher fractions of refractory material after the conditioning process than during lower engine loads (Roessler et al., 1981; Seinfeld, 1986; Tobergte, 1999). The relative size ratio Φ_{D_p} is $96 \pm 3 \%$, i.e., the particle decreased in average by about 4 % in diameter. A constant total particle number with a corresponding overall decrease in particle volume upon heating indicates that the particles are possibly composed of a non-volatile core, representing the majority of the particle volume, with a shallow outer shell of volatile (organic) material, contributing to about 12 % in volume. The shape of the non-volatile particle number size distribution suggests internally mixed 50 nm particles (cf. Chap. 5).

Figure 6-6. Normalized volatility number distributions of 50 nm particles emitted from diesel vehicles D1 (a-c) and D2 (d-f), respectively, at 50, 70, and 100 km/h.

The volatile behavior of the second diesel vehicle (D2) (cf. Fig. 6-6, d-f) similarly reveals a unimodal, refractory number size distribution. Although the distributions of D2 at different vehicle velocities are very similar, the residual distributions are much broader compared to D1. After the heating process, the particles seem to be redistributed as a function of diameter. The slight increase in upper particle diameters is possibly caused by coagulation of individual particles during the

heating process. It could furthermore indicate measurements artifacts of these particular refractory compounds due to their non-spherical shape, leading to higher mobility-equivalent diameters. Different types of diesel fuel can cause different structures of soot agglomerates (Roessler et al., 1981; Berube et al., 1999). The relative number fraction Φ_N and volume fraction Φ_V of the residual distributions, averaged over all speeds, is lower compared to the first diesel vehicle, being $88 \pm 4 \%$ and $81 \pm 4 \%$, respectively, increasing with velocity. Although the differences between D1 and D2 are within the range of uncertainty, the results suggest that in the case of D2 more material evaporated during heating. Thus, the emitted particles seem to contain a larger fraction of volatile (organic) material. These results are expected: D2 has a correspondingly higher consumption of oxygen during identical loads (i.e., fuel, driving conditions) compared to D1 (Tobergte, 1999), resulting in a leaner air-fuel mixture and a, therefore, smaller fraction of produced soot. Unexpectedly, the total number of particles remains not constant. About 12 % of all particles are not conserved during the conditioning process, indicating that they contain only volatile material and no non-volatile cores. Latter results are possibly related to the slight increase in particle diameter at elevated temperatures (cf. Fig. 6-6d-f), indicating coagulation of particles during heating and a consequently reduced total number of particles. The relative size ratio Φ_{Dp} of on average $96 \pm 0 \%$ is similar to the previous diesel vehicle, representing a mobility-equivalent diameter of between 47 and 48 nm. The individual results of above measurements are summarized in Table 6-2.

<u>50 nm</u>	Speed [km/h]	Diesel D1	Diesel D2
Φ_N [%]	50	97	87
	70	98	86
	100	111	93
Φ_V [%]	50	75	79
	70	90	79
	100	98	86
Φ_{Dp} [%]	50	93	96
	70	99	96
	100	97	97

Table 6-2. Characteristics of residual, non-volatile material of diesel-emitted 50 nm particles.

6.1.3.2. Emissions of Direct Injection Vehicles

A single direct injection gasoline vehicle was available for VTDMA measurements of the emitted particles. Results of the volatility scans of selected 50 nm particles are shown in Figure 6-7, a-c at corresponding velocities (i.e., 50, 70, and 100 km/h). Significantly different from the volatile behavior of the diesel vehicles, the residual 250 °C number size distributions reveal no clear modal character. After thermal conditioning, most of the particles (in number and volume) vanished, indicating that the majority of the emitted particle constituents predominantly contained volatile

material and practically no soot cores. The relative number fraction Φ_N and volume fraction Φ_V of the non-volatile material averages $57 \pm 10 \%$ and $6 \pm 2 \%$, respectively, i.e., almost half of the initial total number evaporated completely and 94 % of the total, initial volume vaporized upon heating. A size ratio of the residual distribution can not be specified due to the associated flat structure. The individual results of the refractory number and volume fractions are listed in Table 6-3. Similar to the trends for diesel vehicles, the volume fraction of the non-volatile material, although relatively small, increases with increasing velocity.

Figure 6-7. Normalized volatility number distribution of 50 nm particles emitted from the direct injection vehicle (DIJ) at 50, 70, and 100 km/h (a-c).

50 nm Speed [km/h]	Direct Injection Vehicle	
	Φ_N [%]	Φ_V [%]
50	57	3.8
70	68	6.9
100	47	8.0

Table 6-3. Characteristics of residual, non-volatile material of emitted 50 nm particles of the direct injection vehicle.

6.1.3.3. Emissions of Gasoline and Natural Gas Vehicles

The volatile behavior of particles emitted from both, gasoline- and natural gas-driven vehicles is very similar, therefore, the results are combined in this section. The VTDMA measurements of

gasoline-emitted particles were conducted for different vehicle types, fuel types, speeds, and air-fuel-ratios, with G1, G2, and G3 representing an identical vehicle type at different equivalence ratios λ of 0.7, 1.0, and 1.5, respectively. All volatility scans (cf. Figure 6-8) show a significantly different behavior compared to these of diesel and direct injection vehicles. The individual graphs

Figure 6-8. Volatility number distribution of 50 nm particles emitted from the different gasoline- and natural gas-driven vehicles at 100 km/h (a-e). The dotted vertical line indicates the initially selected particle size.

(a-e) show the normalized volatility distributions at 25 °C (ambient) and 250 °C (conditioned) for the different vehicle types at constant speed of 100 km/h. In contrast to diesel and direct injection vehicles, the gasoline- and vehicle-driven vehicles produce bi- or multimodal volatility distributions at ambient 25 °C, indicating that large numbers of the initial particles partly volatilize already at ambient temperatures. This suggests that the physico-chemical nature of these particles causes part of their mass to be lost in the VTDMA system between DMA-1 and after DMA-2. This might be due to evaporation of semi-volatile particle components when passing through the clean DMA-1 sheath air, representing a subsaturated environment, thus, causing partial volatilization of the particles, effectively broadening the transfer function of DMA-1. The process might continue when the particles pass through the heater and sheath air of DMA-2. Results for Φ_N , Φ_V , and Φ_{Dp} , are, therefore, difficult to obtain since the reference quantities at 25 °C are no longer unaffected. If we relate total number and volume of the particles conditioned at 250 °C to those at 25 °C, we obtain upper fractionation values for the tested vehicles. Corresponding parameters are summarized in Table 6-4. The actual values, however, are expected to be much lower. Among the test vehicles G1, G2, and G3, the refractory volume fraction ranges between < 11 % and < 33 %, increasing with

50 nm (100 km/h)	$\Phi_{N,max}$ [%]	$\Phi_{V,max}$ [%]
G1 ($\lambda = 0.7$)	< 96	< 33
G2 ($\lambda = 1.0$)	< 88	< 21
G3 ($\lambda = 1.5$)	< 89	< 11
G4 ($\lambda > 1.0$)	< 65	< 13
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NG ($\lambda = 1.0$)	< 97	< 29

Table 6-4. Upper limits for relative number and volume fractions of residual, non-volatile material of emitted 50 nm particles of the gasoline vehicles (G1-G4) and natural gas-driven vehicles (NG) at 100 km/h.

decreasing λ , i.e., with richer mixtures. These results (which agree with earlier studies (Roessler et al., 1981)) are expected since less oxygen favors the formation of soot and therefore the higher occurrence of non-volatile material. Unexpectedly, retrieved values for Φ_V of particles emitted by the natural gas-driven vehicle are relative high, corresponding to those of gasoline-driven vehicles with rich fuel mixtures. Although the characterization of the aerosol particles of gasoline- and natural gas-driven vehicle exhaust is difficult due to the above mentioned problems, the results indicate that these particles contain a high fraction of compounds that have condensed in the exhaust system and are volatile even at ambient temperatures. The remaining, refractory fraction is much smaller than that of the corresponding diesel-emitted particles, and increases for a decrease of oxygen added to the combustion process. The non-volatile fraction of natural gas-emitted particles is surprisingly high, corresponding to that of rich gasoline-emitted particles .

6.1.4. Summary

The non-volatile behavior of particles emitted near (vehicle) combustion sources was investigated. The vehicles tested included diesel cars, a direct injection vehicle, gasoline-driven vehicles, and a natural gas-driven vehicle under various operating conditions. The VTDMA measurements show that derived non-volatile particle fractions depend on vehicle, fuel type, and operating conditions. The non-volatile size distributions of 50 nm diesel-emitted particles appear mostly internally mixed (cf. Chap. 5), i.e., the fraction of refractory material is evenly distributed over all particles. Diesel-emitted particles contain the largest fraction of non-volatile material, with volume fractions in the range of 75 – 100 %. These diesel-emitted, non-volatile fractions are expected to comprise mostly non-volatile carbon. However, they might still include small fractions of less volatile organic carbon or other non-volatile trace compounds which do not vaporize at temperatures up to 250 °C. Their degree is difficult to quantify without auxiliary analysis methods (e.g., thermodesorption, morphological analysis (cf. Chap. 2.3)). Furthermore, the different diesel vehicles seem to contain different fractions of volatile compounds, with leaner air-fuel mixtures showing smaller values of non-volatile material with respect to both, Φ_N and Φ_V .

In contrast to the diesel-emitted particles, only 4 to 8 % of the particle volume emitted from direct injection vehicles represents non-volatile material, suggesting that the particles mainly consists of

volatile compounds. The results for the diesel and direct injection vehicles are compared in Figure 6-9, showing Φ_N , Φ_V , and Φ_{Dp} of the refractory material. Also displayed is the corresponding engine *rev* for the diesel vehicles (those for the direct injection vehicle are not available). Φ_{Dp} of the particles emitted from the direct injection vehicle can not be quantified since the resulting distributions do not show clear modes. Φ_N and Φ_V of the non-volatile compounds of diesel-emitted particles are very high and change with car velocity. A correlation between Φ_N and *rev* is likely since the engine revolution directly regulates the amount of oxygen added during combustion. An increasing *rev* is associated with a decrease in AFR and, therefore, richer air-fuel mixture (cf. Chap. 6.1.1). This, in turn, should govern the amount of soot produced, and thus, Φ_V . However, the results show a better correlation with Φ_N , however, suggesting a higher influence of *rev* on the non-volatile number fraction. The particle size of the refractory compounds (indicated by Φ_{Dp}) of the diesel-particles remains constant for different engine loads and is very close to the initially selected diameter.

Figure 6-9. Non-volatile aerosol fractions of diesel- and direct injection vehicle-emitted 50 nm particles (columns). The lines denote the corresponding engine *revs* (secondary axis) of the diesel vehicles D1 (black) and D2 (gray), those of the direct injection vehicle are not available.

Particles emitted from gasoline- and natural gas-driven vehicles show a different chemical and physical behavior. A large fraction of aerosol compounds evaporates within the measurement system already at ambient conditions, possibly due to partial volatilization of semi-volatile compounds in the clean sheath air of the DMAs. This effect is significant since it is likely to occur in regular particle size distribution measurements as well (e.g., using a TDMPS), leading to a shift of the measured distribution towards smaller diameters. Derived non-volatile aerosol fractions are, therefore, difficult to quantify. The fraction of volatile material is higher in particles emitted from

gasoline- and natural gas vehicles compared to diesel vehicles. Φ_V of the gasoline-emitted particles (G1 to G4) are estimated to be much lower than 11 - 33 %, depending on fuel type and air-fuel-ratio. Rich mixtures reveal the highest amount of non-volatile material, as expected. Corresponding refractory volume fraction in particles emitted from natural gas-driven vehicles is relatively high and compares to that of rich gasoline-emitted particles. All derived parameters are summarized in Table 6-5.

Vehicle Type		Speed [km/h]	Φ_N [%]	Φ_V [%]	Φ_{DP} [%]	
Diesel	D1	50	97	75	93	
		70	98	90	99	
		100	111	98	97	
	D2	50	87	79	96	
		70	86	79	96	
		100	93	86	97	
Direct Injection		50	57	3.8	-	
		70	68	6.9	-	
		100	47	8.0	-	
Gasoline	G1 ($\lambda=0.7$)	100	< 96	< 33	-	
	G2 ($\lambda=1.0$)	100	< 88	< 21	-	
	G3 ($\lambda=1.5$)	100	< 89	< 11	-	
	G4 ($\lambda>1.0$)	100	< 65	< 13	-	
Natural Gas		($\lambda=1.0$)	100	< 97	< 29	-

Table 6-5. Derived aerosol fractions characterizing non-volatile compounds of emitted particles from different types of vehicles. Φ_{DP} is only available if distinct modes occur.

The above results were retrieved under severe restrictions with respect to the length of the individual measurement cycles, and the reproducibility of the data could not be verified due to logistic reasons concerning the facilities in the emission laboratory. The DMA-based size characterization was conducted with respect to mobility-equivalent diameters which is not always identical with their actual geometric size, particularly if the carbon-containing particles are of non-spherical shape. Measurement uncertainties due to multiply-charged particles are negligible for the measured particle sizes of 50 nm and below (cf. Chap. 3.3). The results show that the VTDMA is capable to identify large as well as very small amounts of non-volatile carbon material in the fine aerosol size range emitted from combustion sources. Furthermore, different combustion processes (e.g., with respect to fuel type, amount of oxygen added during combustion) can be observed. A great advantage to conventional particle sampling methods is the possibility of selecting small, quasi-monodisperse, airborne particle for the detection of the material of interest.

6.2. AEROSOLS IN STRONGLY POLLUTED ENVIRONMENTS

Urban environments are generally characterized by high particle number concentrations due to the proximity to pollutant sources. The predominant sources are anthropogenic, in particular, vehicle traffic, industrial emissions, heat and power generation. Extremely high concentrations of fine particles are found close to sources, and their concentration decreases with increasing distance from the source. Carbonaceous aerosol particles, originating from combustion processes, significantly contribute to the total particle mass. Elemental (or black) carbon is often coated by inorganic and organic species through oxidation and adsorption/condensation processes, thus, forming secondary aerosol components. Among these, the sulfate species are most important. They are directly formed from gaseous precursors and are usually fully or partially neutralized by ammonia (remarkable quantities of unneutralized sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) are only observed in remote locations). The second most abundant secondary inorganic aerosol component in the polluted atmosphere is nitrate, arising from the oxidation of nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) to nitric acid (HNO_3) which reacts with ammonia to form the relatively volatile ammonium nitrate. Other inorganic compounds such as sodium nitrate and ammonium chloride are generally of minor abundance. Particulate organic matter, representing a complex mixture of many different organic compounds, is furthermore known to be a significant constituent of the urban aerosol. It is emitted directly by combustion sources or produced by oxidation reactions in the atmosphere. Due to the variety of sources and subsequent transformation processes, the overall composition of urban aerosol particles is complex and varies with location and time of day.

6.2.1. The *VoLE 99* Urban Aerosol Measurements

Urban aerosol particles were sampled during a cold winter period in the city of Leipzig, Germany. The *VoLE 99* measurements (Volatility of aerosols in LEipzig) were performed between February 10 to 16, 1999 at the Institute for Tropospheric Research (IfT), a few kilometers northwest of the city center. The IfT is surrounded by residential housing and is located near considerably frequented roads, particularly relevant during early morning and late afternoon rush hours. Thus, sources for primary and secondary aerosols are available, comprising sulfate, nitrate, and carbonaceous compounds.

6.2.1.1. Instrumentation

The measurements encompassed continuous measurements with the Volatility-TDMA as well as impactor sampling for the analysis of carbon and ionic components. Additionally, an electrostatic separator was used to investigate the morphology of non-volatile particle compounds by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). Furthermore, measurements of particle number size distributions, trace gases, meteorological parameters and concurrent synoptic information were available. The experimental methods are summarized in Table 6-6. The inlet for airborne particle sampling consisted of a PM_{10} (i.e., a sampler for particulate matter $< 10 \mu\text{m}$) located on the roof of

Instrument	Analyzed Parameter
VTDMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Volatility number distribution ▶ Number and volume of non-volatile compounds
Berner Impactor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Anions, cations ▶ OC^I, OC^{II}, EC
Electrostatic Particle Sampler	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Particle morphology
TDMPS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Particle Number Size Distribution (3-800 nm) ▶ Total particle concentration (3-800 nm) from integration
Trace Gas Monitors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ SO₂, NO_x, CO, O₃ concentration
Meteorological Instruments / Synoptic Charts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ T, p, w_s, w_d, RH ▶ Medium-scale synoptic analysis, backtrajectories

Table 6-6. Instrumentation and analyzed parameters during the *VoLE 99* measurements. OC^I refers to the analysis of organic carbon at 280 °C, OC^{II} to that at 590 °C. Elemental carbon (EC) is determined at 650 °C. T, p, w_s, and w_d denote temperature, pressure, wind speed, and wind direction, respectively.

the building, about 12 m off the ground. Due to the proximity of strong, local sources the atmospheric aerosol is expected to be mostly influenced by processes related to these sources. However, the synoptic situation and associated meteorological parameter will be briefly described in the following to explain possible influences on the aerosol transported into and transformed within the region.

6.2.1.2. Meteorological Situation

The initial phase of the one week measurement period was dominated by a deep pressure trough centered over central Europe, introducing cold, polar-maritime air masses into the region. The center of this low pressure system was characterized by clear, sunny, but cold conditions in the measurement region with little wind. In the course of this synoptic situation a deep cut-off low developed aloft leading to converging lifting on its northern side, accompanied by local precipitation and heavy snowfall. Towards the end of the measurement period the region was influenced by a narrow high pressure bridge over central Europe with temporarily sunny conditions, to be replaced by a newly evolving low pressure system and extensive precipitation. The backtrajectory analysis confirms that air masses near the surface were transported into the region from a northwesterly to northeasterly direction, being cold and polar-marine. Polar air masses aloft were transported along the cut-off low over central Europe, therefore being continentally influenced before reaching the area. The surface meteorological parameters measured at the site on February 10-16, 1999 are shown in Figure 6-10. Particularly between February 10-12 and on February 15 clear, sunny, but cold conditions prevailed, recorded in the data of global radiation (with maxima between 350 and 450 Wm⁻²) and the significant diurnal variations of the temperature (with day-to-night-time differences of more than 10 °C). Substantial precipitation fell

on February 16 in the form of rain. Considerable precipitation on February 12 and 13 was exclusively in the form of snowfall and therefore barely registered by the precipitation probe.

Figure 6-10. Time series of meteorological parameters between February 10-16 at the measurement site, given as 1-hr average values. The date on the abscissa indicates 12 UTC on the respective days.

Associated trace gas concentrations of O_3 , NO_x , CO , and SO_2 are illustrated in Figure 6-11. The O_3 concentration was fairly typical for winter conditions and varied between 0 and 35 ppb. The formation of O_3 in the urban atmosphere is favored by the occurrence of HC and NO_x (due to vehicle emissions) in the presence of sunlight, thus showing maxima shortly after the noon radiation maxima, and minima during nighttime, as obvious during the initial and final measurement days. Increased O_3 concentrations between Julian Day 42.5 to 44.5 were most likely due to the photolysis of NO_2 and less likely due to subsiding, O_3 -rich air from above during the influence of high pressure in the region. The NO_2 and NO concentrations were rather typical for polluted environments, mostly from vehicle emissions, with average values of 15 ± 7.5 and 6.6 ± 10 ppb, respectively. Individual concentrations ranged as high as 36 and 54 ppb, respectively. The CO concentration was high, averaging 1060 ± 960 ppb, and correlates directly with maximum vehicle emissions (e.g., during morning and later afternoon rush hour). Decreased values for CO are obvious, e.g., during the weekend period with correspondingly less traffic. The sources for SO_2 are mostly industrial emissions, ranging up to 200 ppb with an average value of 7.2 ± 17 ppb.

Figure 6-11. Time series of trace gas concentrations. The date on the abscissa indicates 12 UTC on the respective days.

6.2.2. Volatility Size Distributions

Continuous measurements with the VTDMA were carried out to investigate the volatile behavior of atmospheric aerosol particles influenced by or originating from local urban pollution sources. The volatility measurements focused on selected monodisperse particle sizes in the submicrometer size range, i.e., 50 and 150 nm, representing the Aitken and accumulation mode, respectively. The volatility temperatures the particles were exposed to in the VTDMA system were 25 °C (ambient temperature), 80 °C, 180 °C, and 280 °C. The experimental measurement conditions of the VTDMA are summarized in Table 6-7. The time intervals of the individual scans varied, depending on the selected particle diameters and volatilization temperatures, and were in the range between 5 - 8 min. A complete sequence of volatility spectra took about 75 min.

Selected Particle Diameter [nm]	Volatilization Temperature [°C]	Time per Scan [min]
150	25, 80, 180, 280	4.7 - 7.6
50	25, 80, 180, 280	5.0 - 7.7

Table 6-7. Selected particle diameters and volatilization temperatures of the VTDMA measurements during VoLE 99.

A typical set of volatility spectra of 150 nm particles is shown in Figure 6-12, measured on Julian Day 41.76 – 41.78 during late afternoon/early evening rush hour. The results indicate a shift of the initial mode at 150 nm towards smaller particle diameters. All size distributions show a residual mode centered near the selected diameter. The 80 °C distribution shifted monomodally, accompanied by a broadening of the peak. Approximately 20 % of the particle volume vaporized, although the total number of particles remains unchanged. At 180°C, the majority of the particle volume evaporated (~ 60 %), a multi-modal structure developed and the distribution can be partitioned into three different modes. The final distribution at 280 °C shifted further to smaller diameters, revealing the residual trimodal number size distribution of the refractory material, whereby 73 % in volume evaporated.

Figure 6-12. Example of normalized volatility spectra of 150 nm particles conditioned to 25 °C (ambient), 80 °C, 180 °C, and 280 °C on February 11, 1999.

The multimodal volatility distribution demonstrates the inhomogeneous structure of the preexisting aerosol population with respect to non-volatile compounds. The non-volatile number fraction $\Phi_{N,i}$ remained constant throughout the conditioning process up to 280 °C, indicating that all aerosol particles contain refractory material. The relative volume fraction $\Phi_{V,i}$ decreased with increasing temperatures. At elevated temperatures a distinct mode at approximately 145 nm can be observed, representing predominantly non-volatile particles with nearly unchanged diameter. This mode is generally defined as *quasi-non-volatile* mode in this study (cf. Chap. 5). A volatile coating of 2-3 nm on these non-volatile cores is indicated. The change in the average mode diameter is small (< 3-4 %) and can not be identified as systematic shift (e.g., due to volatile material or caused by thermal rearrangement of the refractory compounds) or systematic measurement error (e.g., due to inconstant flow rates in the DMAs (cf. Appendix A.2)). The *quasi-non-volatile* portion $\phi_{N,qnv}$ (cf. Eqn. 5-1) at 280 °C amounts to 23 % by number, i.e., about 23 % of all urban particles are predominantly non-volatile, and the remaining particles are *partially-non-volatile*, i.e., contain

volatile compounds to various degrees. Corresponding results of derived number and volume fractions are summarized in Table 6-8.

Conditioning Temperature [°C]	$\Phi_{N,i}$ [%]	$\Phi_{N,qnv,i}$ [%]	$\Phi_{V,i}$ [%]	$\Phi_{V,qnv,i}$ [%]
80	100	-	78	-
180	110	26	37	24
280	100	23	27	20

Table 6-8. Derived number ($\Phi_{N,i}$) and volume fractions ($\Phi_{V,i}$), as well as pertinent *quasi-non-volatile* number and volume fractions, $\Phi_{N,qnv,i}$ and $\Phi_{V,qnv,i}$, respectively, of volatility spectra on February 11, 99 for selected 150 nm particles (note: $\Phi_{N,qnv,i}$ and $\Phi_{V,qnv,i}$ can be retrieved only when distinct *quasi-non-volatile* modes occur, generally at temperatures ≥ 180 °C).

The above scans represent typical volatility distributions throughout the measurement period for the individual temperature steps. The concentration of the 150 nm particles selected with the VTDMA varies with time according to the overall aerosol concentration. Figure 6-13 shows time series of total number concentrations during *VoLE* of the initially selected increment of particles around 150 nm, recorded by CPC-1 at the entrance of the VTDMA system. The CPC-1 number concentration is denoted by N_{150nm} . Additionally plotted on the secondary axis is the total particle number N_{total} as derived from the integrated number size distribution measured with the TDMPS

Figure 6-13. Time series of particle number concentration of 150 nm particles measured with the VTDMA (N_{150nm}) and total number concentrations (N_{total}) derived from TDMPS measurements (not the different scale of primary and secondary axis). The dotted lines indicate the defined time periods.

between 3 and 800 nm. Data for N_{total} are only available for part of the measurement campaign. In general, $N_{150\text{nm}}$ follows the trend of N_{total} , as expected, with correspondingly lower concentrations by about 2 orders of magnitude, and is probably a good surrogate for the accumulation mode as a whole. According to the variation in particle number concentration, the *VoLE 99* time period can be divided into several sub-periods, as marked in Figure 6-13. During period I, $N_{150\text{nm}}$ averages about 140 cm^{-3} , with low winds ($\sim 2 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) from southeast to southwest, thus, representing local, urban air. During period II, $N_{150\text{nm}}$ increases significantly, averaging 214 cm^{-3} , and coincides with weak and variable winds. The particle concentration is therefore possibly locally increased, accompanied by sunny, cloudless conditions and very low temperatures (e.g., $T_{\text{min}} < -10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) on that particular and previous day, and consequently increased domestic heating activities producing a higher number of aerosol particles. Period III is characterized by a sharp decrease in the particle number (averaging 59 cm^{-3}) as a result of increased winds, frontal activity, and subsequent snowfall. During period IV precipitation continues in the form of snow, decreasing the 150 nm particle number further to a mean value of 31 cm^{-3} . A high pressure ridge establishes again during the following period (V), producing clear, sunny conditions with no precipitation and stronger winds up to $5 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ from the southwest. The average particle number concentration is 74 cm^{-3} . Ensuing strong winds and precipitation cause $N_{150\text{nm}}$ to drop to about 19 cm^{-3} during the last period VI. The individual time periods and associated averaged values for $N_{150\text{nm}}$ are summarized in Table 6-9.

Time Period	Julian Day	$N_{150 \text{ nm}} [\text{cm}^{-3}]$
I	40.00 - 41.17	140 ± 25
II	41.18 - 42.48	214 ± 88
III	42.53 - 43.34	59 ± 25
IV	43.36 - 44.93	31 ± 11
V	44.97 - 46.31	74 ± 22
VI	46.36 - 47.15	19 ± 10

Table 6-9. Individual sub-periods during *VoLE*, indicating associated Julian Day and averaged 150 nm particle concentrations ($N_{150\text{nm}}$).

The processes leading to a decrease or increase in the total number of particles are relevant for the results recorded by the VTDMA measurements. The fraction of non-volatile material in this case depends on the following mechanisms: Firstly, the production/formation of new aerosols within the area at combustion sources, secondly, the advection of aerosol particles containing non-volatile material into the measurement region, and lastly, processes leading to a transformation of the existing particles (cf. Chap. 5). The temporal variation of all ambient $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ volatility spectra of 150 nm particles throughout *VoLE 99* is displayed in Figure 6-14, representing raw (non-inverted) number size distributions. The corresponding size distributions of the non-volatile material at $280 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is shown in Figure 6-15. In contrast, latter scans are normalized with respect to the current 150 nm particle concentration to reflect actual non-volatile fractions independently of the temporal variation.

Figure 6-14. Time series of all raw (non-inverted) volatility number distributions of 150 nm particles at ambient temperatures (25 °C) during *VoLE*. Indicated is also the initial particle diameter at 150 nm.

Figure 6-15. Time series of the normalized, raw (non-inverted) volatility number distributions of 150 nm particles after conditioning to 280 °C. Indicated is also the initial particle diameter at 150 nm.

All 150 nm particle size distributions at ambient temperatures (25 °C) have the expected unimodal structure (cf. Fig. 6-14). The individual mode amplitudes vary according to the 150 nm particle concentration, also causing apparent variation of the mode widths which are actually constant. Similarly to the selected example shown above (cf. Fig. 6-12), the volatility scans of 150 nm particles conditioned to 280 °C reveal a multimodal number distribution of residual, refractory material (cf. Fig. 6-15). A significant mode remains near the initially selected 150 nm. This *quasi-non-volatile* mode indicates particles that consist almost entirely of non-volatile material. A very thin layer of more volatile compounds might exist, i.e., about 1 % in diameter is lost in the VTDMA at ambient temperatures (25 °C) and on average about 2 – 3 % in diameter between the ambient mode and the first mode at 280 °C, respectively. The halfwidth of the *quasi-non-volatile* mode approximately complies with that of the DMA transfer function (cf. Chap. 3.2.3), being about 19 nm at a corresponding average mode diameter of 147 nm. The remaining, non-volatile material at 280 °C, as shown in Figure 6-15, is characterized by a broad distribution with a main mode between 40 and 50 nm. In order to investigate the volatile behavior of the particles throughout the measurement campaign, the volatility scans are averaged over time periods I-VI. Figure 6-16 shows the resulting averaged, non-volatile distributions at 280 °C for the six time periods. The general structure of the different scans is very similar. Subtle differences exist with respect to the amplitude of the *quasi-non-volatile* mode and the structure of the second (*partially-non-volatile*) mode. All six scans show the pronounced *quasi-non-volatile* mode centered between 144 and 147 nm, differing only in magnitude, and the *partially-non-volatile* mode which essentially consists of several peaks and shoulders. All distributions show an overall large width of this second mode. The distributions demonstrate that the initial 150 nm particles contain different amounts of non-

Figure 6-16. Average, normalized volatility number distributions of 150 nm refractory particles at 280 °C, for individual time periods I-VI. The dotted line indicates the initial particle diameter at 150 nm.

volatile material, representing diameters between 15 and 150 nm. The particles relating to the first mode all contain little volatile material. A possible implication is that these are largely hydrophobic compounds which prevent subsequent condensation of volatile material.

The structure of the 280 °C-distributions of selected 50 nm particles is similar. The corresponding graphs are displayed in Figure 6-17. The curves are only shown for diameters above 15 nm, which defines the lower detection limit for the VTDMA (i.e., below 15 nm, the data are subject to large uncertainties (cf. Chap. 4.1)). The larger mode is close to the initially selected diameter, however, its mode diameter is about 4 – 7 % smaller than that at 25 °C which in turn is approximately 2 - 3 % smaller than the initially selected 150 nm. Nevertheless, the larger mode is still within the boundaries of that recorded at 25 °C and therefore considered *quasi-non-volatile*. The smaller mode appears at very small diameters, smaller than the minimum detection limit so that it is not entirely covered by the VTDMA. Between both modes a clear minimum in the non-volatile concentration exists. It is likely that non-volatile residuals are located in the size range < 15 nm where they can not be detected with the VTDMA. Due to the uncertainties associated with investigating non-volatile material of 50 nm particles in the lower diameter range (< 15 nm), the subsequent quantitative study focuses on the larger 150 nm particles.

Figure 6-17. Average, normalized volatility number distributions of 50 nm particles at 280 °C for individual time periods I-VI. The dotted line indicates the initial particle diameter at 50 nm.

6.2.3. Non-volatile Aerosol Fractions

The volatility distributions during the *VoLE 99* campaign discussed in the previous section provide substantial qualitative information about the nature of the non-volatile material inherent to the urban aerosol. This section focuses on the quantification of the non-volatile aerosol fractions of 150 nm particles with respect to their number and volume. The derived parameters allow a better comparison of the individual time periods I-VI and in general a comparison of the *VoLE 99* results with those performed in other surroundings. The non-volatile number and volume fractions, Φ_N

and Φ_V , respectively, of the averaged 150 nm volatility distributions of the six time periods (cf. Tab. 6-9) are displayed in Figure 6-18. Throughout the measurement period, Φ_N at 280 °C remains constant, averaging 100 ± 0.9 %. In contrast, Φ_V varies and ranges between 12 % and 24 % with a mean value of 18 ± 4.6 %. A constant overall number fraction with an associated decrease of the relative volume fraction indicates that the individual particles contain non-volatile material between at least 0.1 % and approximately 95 % in volume of the initially selected 150 nm particles. The individual volume fractions are possibly indicative for the different processes involved in the formation/transformation of non-volatile material. In order to draw conclusions about the chemical nature of the refractory components additional chemical information is necessary and will be discussed later (cf. Chap. 6.2.5).

Figure 6-18. Non-volatile number (light gray) and volume (dark gray) fractions derived from averaged 150 nm volatility distributions of the individual time periods.

The effect of multiply-charged particles on the derived non-volatile number and volume fractions is considered small. From concurrent size distribution measurements, between 25 % and 30 % of the selected particles are calculated to be doubly-charged 235 nm particles (i.e., having the same mobility as the singly-charged 150 nm particles (cf. Chap. 3.3)), and about 5 to 15 % are derived as triply-charged 313 nm particles. Since the total particle number is conserved after conditioning (Φ_N near 100 %), all doublets and triplets selected by DMA-1 are found in the particle size range measured with DMA-2. Φ_N , representing the ratio of the total particle number before to that after conditioning, remains therefore unaffected. The associated volume of the conditioned and unconditioned particles might change with respect to the occurrence of multiply-charged particles. An estimate of the uncertainty in the derived non-volatile volume fraction Φ_V is difficult since the size distribution of the doublets and triplets after conditioning can not be distinguished from that of singly-charged particles. Assuming the particle composition of 150 nm, 235 nm, and 313 nm particles to be similar (all representing accumulation mode particles), the multiply-charged refractory particles will be distributed analogously to the singly-charged residues (i.e., the fraction of doublet and triplets is constant in all size bins). Then, Φ_V will not change since it represents the ratio of the total volume before to that after conditioning, each containing the same volume fraction

of multiply-charged particles. In the unlikely case that the distribution of the non-volatile material of the multiply-charged particles is asymmetric with respect to that of singly-charged particles, Φ_V can be over- or underestimated.

To investigate the extend to which the non-volatile material encompasses particles that contain basically no volatile material, corresponding parameters $\varphi_{N,qnv}$ and $\varphi_{V,qnv}$, representing the *quasi-non-volatile* number and volume, respectively, as well as *partially-non-volatile* number and volume, are derived (cf. Eqn. 5-1 to 5-4). This assumes that the *quasi-non-volatile* mode at 280 °C is located inside the boundaries of the initial mode at 25 °C which is always the case. The results are illustrated in Figure 6-19. The contribution of $\varphi_{N,qnv}$ ranges between 7 and 18 %, and has an average value of 13 ± 4.1 %, i.e., about 13 % of all 150 nm particles are comprised mostly of non-volatile material, amounting to more than two thirds of the entire non-volatile volume. 87 % of the particles contain a non-volatile core plus a large and variable overall volume fraction (75 % or greater) of volatile compounds of all 150 nm particles. Integrated over the volatility distribution, the *quasi-non-volatile* volume fraction $\varphi_{V,qnv}$ ranges similarly between 6 and 17 %, with a mean value of 12 ± 3.9 %. It is obvious that the *quasi-non-volatile* fraction is minor with respect to particle number. The times where $\varphi_{N,qnv}$ is smallest corresponds to the relatively warm, overcast time periods (III and IV) with precipitation and associated low overall particle concentrations. Furthermore, due to warmer temperatures fewer particles are emitted from domestic heating sources and the fraction of particles transported into the region (containing less non-volatile material) might be larger. All derived parameters are summarized in Table 6-10.

Figure 6-19. *Quasi-non-volatile* (solid) and *partially-non-volatile* (hatched) portions of the non-volatile number (Φ_N) and volume fractions (Φ_V) of 150 nm particles for the individual time periods.

Time Period	Φ_N [%]	Φ_V [%]	$\Phi_{N,qnv}$ [%]	$\Phi_{V,qnv}$ [%]
I	98	16	11	10
II	100	23	18	16
III	99	12	7	6
IV	101	16	11	10
V	99	19	14	13
VI	100	24	18	17
mean	100 ± 0.9	18 ± 4.6	13 ± 4.1	12 ± 3.9

Table 6-10. Calculated fractions of non-volatile aerosol compounds from averaged volatility distribution of 150 nm particles of the individual time periods.

6.2.4. Particle Morphology

For morphological analysis, refractory particles after thermal conditioning to 280 °C were sampled downstream of the heating unit. For that purpose, the VTDMA design was altered at the exit of DMA-2 (cf. Fig. 6-20). Instead of scanning the residual distribution, selected particles were extracted (i.e., DMA-2 was kept at constant voltage). Selected particle diameters are representative for the average diameter of the resulting, non-volatile modes. For example, for initial 150 nm particles, the sampling diameters were chosen at approximately 145 and 47 nm, coinciding with the two major modes of the volatility distributions of non-volatile material of initial 150 nm particles (cf. Fig. 6-16). The sampling setup did not allow to simultaneously perform the standard VTDMA measurements. The particle morphology measurements were, therefore, carried out after the actual *VoLE 99* measurement campaign since only one VTDMA system was available. As a consequence, the results for the sampled aerosol are not concurrent with above results and represent, therefore, only typical urban particles. The meteorological situation during morphological sampling changed to our disadvantage with ongoing precipitation (snowfall and rain) and increasing temperatures, leading to a drastic decrease of the particle concentration, thus, requiring long sampling times. Particle sampling was performed on Formvar-coated copper foils² using an Electrostatic Particle Sampler (EPS) (cf. Appendix A.4). To enhance particle sampling through the EPS, the flow rate was adjusted to 0.1 and 0.5 l·min⁻¹ for particle diameters of 145 and 47 nm, respectively. Supplementary sheath air was used to establish a flow rate of 1.0 l·min⁻¹ through DMA-2. The foils were analyzed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, EM 912 Ω , Zeitz, Oberkochen). Due to the low atmospheric particle concentrations, the sampling time was on the order of several days to ensure a sufficient number of particles for TEM analysis. The results, therefore, give only an exploratory survey of refractory particles after thermal conditioning in the VTDMA.

² Formvar, or polyvinyl formal, is utilized as support film for TEM grids.

Figure 6-20. Setup for sampling of refractory particles with Electrostatic Particle Sampler (EPS).

Results of TEM micrographs are shown in Figures 6-21a-d. The graphs reveal a variety of possible shapes of the residual, refractory material. The figures on the left-hand side (a and c) correspond to selected mobility-equivalent diameters of 47 nm, those on the right-hand side (b and d) represent selected mobility-equivalent diameters of 145 nm. Particle morphology indicates carbonaceous material. The particles appear as spheres as well as agglomerates, typical for BC or soot (fly ash, e.g., can be distinguished as porous or spongy spheres). It is obvious that the mobility-equivalent diameter might deviate significantly from the geometric diameter due to the non-spherical shape of the aggregates (e.g., Fig. 6-21c). The above agglomerates are composed of coagulated primary particles that are approximately between 20 and 50 nm in size. The primary particles are not always perfectly spherical, but appear mostly sphere-like or ellipsoidal. The spherical particle in Figure 6-21a possibly signifies carbonaceous material produced in high-temperature processes, inducing a close packing during elevated temperatures (Schmidt-Ott, 1988; Weber et al., 1996). The chain-like structure of non-volatile carbon shows a possible shortcoming for the characterization of particles with a DMA. Due to their non-spherical shape different agglomerates might exhibit the same mobility behavior although their actual geometries are different.

Figure 6-21. TEM-micrographs of sampled refractory material downstream of the VTDMA conditioning unit (with conditioning temperatures of 280 °C), suggesting non-volatile carbonaceous material.

6.2.5. Chemical Composition of Urban Aerosols

For the chemical characterization, two 5-stage, low pressure cascade impactors were used for particle collection with 50 % size cuts at 0.05, 0.14, 0.42, 1.2, 3.5, and 10 μm aerodynamic diameter. Particle sampling throughout the *VoLE 99* campaign was performed at ambient RH, ranging between 50 and 90 %. A total of 11 samples were collected with sampling times between 6 and 18 hrs. In order to get a good overall representation of the urban aerosol, night-time sampling was extended to include morning and evening rush hours, so that the collection intervals during the night were chosen to be longer than during the day. Sampling time during the day was on average 8 hrs, during the night typically on the order of 15 – 16 hrs. One impactor was used for the analysis of ionic compounds, utilizing Tedlar foils, the second one for the determination of organic and

elemental carbon with aluminum foils. The 11 impactor sampling times during *VoLE 99* are listed in Table 6-11.

Sample #	Interval [JD]	Total Time [min]	Sample #	Interval [JD]	Total Time [min]
1	40.60 - 41.35	1081	7	43.8 - 44.42	555
2	41.38 - 41.63	357	8	44.44 - 44.87	620
3	41.65 - 42.32	975	9	44.9 - 45.33	625
4	42.35 - 42.60	365	10	45.36 - 45.64	408
5	42.62 - 43.32	1012	11	45.66 - 46.37	1016
6	43.34 - 43.77	623			

Table 6-11. Chemical impactor sampling times and intervals. The times are given as Julian Day (JD).

Since the results of the chemical measurements are ultimately compared with those of the volatility measurement, the chemical analysis was performed solely for submicrometer particles corresponding to stage 1 through 3 (i.e., 50 to 1200 nm aerodynamic diameter) of the impactor. Aerosol mass was determined gravimetrically at a constant 40 % RH after being conditioned for at least 24 hrs before weighing. The mass concentrations determined at 40 % RH were corrected to corresponding dry mass concentrations by using an experimentally determined (diameter) growth factor of 1.12 from HTDMA measurements (Busch, 1999)³. Cations and anions were determined by ion chromatography including the species Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺. Organic and elemental carbon were analyzed by a thermal desorption/oxidation method during which the samples were heated to specific temperatures to evaporate their volatile components and to obtain the respective carbonaceous compounds (cf. Chap. 2.3.1). Thermal treatment implied a heating of the samples to 590 °C under nitrogen to allow the escape of present organic material. A further heating to 650 °C under oxygen yielded the separation of elemental, non-volatile carbon. An additional heating stage was implemented at 280 °C under O₂ to evaporate volatile, organic carbon for comparison with the VTDMA. The total organic mass associated with OC is calculated by multiplying the measured organic carbon mass with a factor of 1.2 to correct for the volatile carbon compounds that evaporate at temperatures below 590 °C (Gray et al., 1986; Kaneyasu et al., 1995; Neusüß, 1999). Thus, the corrected OC compound is termed ‘organics’ in the following (note, for comparison with the VTDMA, values for OC, not for organics, are employed). The total organic mass (TOC) is hereby discriminated between OC^I and OC^{II}, denoting corresponding OC at 280 °C and 590 °C, respectively⁴. All samples are corrected for blank values.

To give an overview of the chemical composition of the entire submicrometer aerosol, the overall results of the chemical analysis for the sum of stages 1 through 3 (50 to 1200 nm) of the impactor

³ The dry mass was derived from an assumed *growth factor* g_f and dry and wet (40%) densities ($\rho_{\text{dry}} = 1.7$ and $\rho_{\text{wet}} = 1.4 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, respectively), as: $m_{\text{dry}} = 1/(g_f)^3 \cdot \rho_{\text{dry}}/\rho_{\text{wet}} \cdot m_{\text{wet}}$.

⁴ Note, OC analyzed at 590 °C represents the OC fraction remaining after the removal of OC at 280 °C. Thus, $\text{OC}^{\text{II}} = \text{OC} - \text{OC}^{\text{I}}$.

are displayed in Figure 6-22. Shown are concentrations of the different anions and cations, organics, and elemental carbon (note that the individual compounds are listed in the order of their vertical appearance). The total, analyzed mass concentrations of the different anions and cations, organics, and elemental carbon (note that the individual compounds are listed in the order of their vertical appearance). The total, analyzed mass concentration during the measurement period ranges

Figure 6-22. Mass concentrations of analyzed chemical compounds and total weighed mass of all *VoLE 99* samples of submicrometer aerosols summed over impactor stages 1-3 (50-1200 nm aerodynamic diameter) (listed in the order of their vertical appearance). Contributions of Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} are relatively small and therefore invisible on the graph.

between 16 and $64 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ with an average value of $28 \pm 12 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, representing rather heavily polluted air (cf. Chap. 2.2.2). The variation of the total submicrometer mass during *VoLE 99* correlates with the overall variation of the aerosol concentration (cf. Fig. 6-13). Average concentrations for the individual compounds for the entire submicrometer size range are listed in Table 6-12. The submicrometer aerosol mass is mostly dominated by nitrate, carbon (OC and EC), sulfate, and ammonium. The ion balance shows that all of the observed ammonium can be neutralized by the analyzed nitrate and sulfate. Noticeable are the particularly high values for nitrate, which dominates by a factor of two compared to sulfate. The dominance of nitrate is indicative of urban aerosols due to traffic sources (i.e., high concentrations of emitted NO_x). Total carbon (organics and elemental carbon) is the next significant compound, with the organic component being predominant.

Chemical Compound	Mass Concentration [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$]	Chemical Compound	Mass Concentration [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$]
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Cl ⁻	0.48 ± 0.27	Ca ²⁺	0.02 ± 0.02
SO ₄ ²⁻	4.8 ± 1.5	Mg ²⁺	0.0 ± 0.0
NO ₃ ⁻	9.6 ± 2.8	Organics	7.1 ± 6.2
NH ₄ ⁺	4.2 ± 1.3	EC	1.9 ± 1.4
Na ⁺	0.07 ± 0.04	Total	28 ± 12
K ⁺	0.16 ± 0.07		

Table 6-12. Average concentrations of the submicrometer chemical composition during the entire *VoLE 99* campaign.

The mass fractions of the individual compounds for the submicrometer particle size range are displayed in Figure 6-23. Shown is the mass fraction of each compound as part of the total weighed and RH- corrected mass, ordered by weight. The total carbon fraction is high, averaging $26 \pm 10\%$. Individual values range between 15 and 50%. The carbon fraction is mostly dominated by organics which was four times the amount of EC. The organic fraction represents the organic carbon fraction corrected for associated volatile (organic carbon) species (Gray et al., 1986). About 10% of the total mass can not be attributed to any of the before mentioned, analyzed components. It might be due to measurement uncertainties, other unidentified species, or uncertainties in the growth factor. The *VoLE 99* chemical composition differs from the average fine particle composition of the urban aerosol derived from an extensive study comparing a series of different results (Heintzenberg, 1989). The urban results of Heintzenberg (1989) showed that the submicrometer urban aerosol was found to be dominated by OC and sulfate, comprising more the half of the total mass, with nitrate being only a minor constituent (cf. Chap. 2.1).

Figure 6-23. Average mass fractions (in %) of chemical compounds as part of the total weighted mass throughout *VoLE 99*. Due to their low values, the fractions for K⁺, Na⁺, Ca²⁺, and Mg²⁺ are combined.

The partitioning between OC^I, OC^{II}, EC is illustrated in Figure 6-24. Also shown are the corresponding VTDMA-derived volume fractions $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$ (the actual comparison between the

results of both methods is discussed in Chap. 6.2.6). Elemental carbon ranges between 3 % and 12 % with an average value of 5.6 ± 2.8 % over the entire time period. Organic carbon is dominantly volatile at the lower temperature step (280 °C). In average, 79 % of the total organic fraction ($OC^I + OC^{II}$) is comprised of OC^I . This indicates the majority of the organic mass is evaporated at temperatures up to 280 °C. This result will be particularly important for the comparison of these data to the VTDMA-derived non-volatile particle fractions. As part of the total carbon, the fractions of OC^I , OC^{II} , and EC amount in average to 59, 16, and 25 %, respectively. The fraction of less volatile organic carbon, OC^{II} , is therefore, less than EC.

Figure 6-24. Submicrometer mass fractions (in %) of OC^I , OC^{II} , and EC for the individual samples and volume fraction, $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$, of refractory compounds of initially selected 150 nm particles after conditioning to 280 °C derived from VTDMA measurements.

Ultimately, the OC and EC mass fractions from the chemical analysis are to be compared with the non-volatile volume fractions from VTDMA analysis. With the VTDMA method being focused on particle diameters below 150 nm, the relevant size ranges of the chemical method are impactor stages one and two, corresponding to 50/140 and 140/420 nm aerodynamic diameter, respectively. The analyzed mass fractions for both stages averaged over all *VoLE* measurements are shown in Figure 6-25. Displayed are mass fractions of the individual, analyzed compounds as part of their total (dry) mass. There are no substantial differences between both stages with the fraction of organics and nitrate being dominant. The organic compound predominates in the smaller size range (i.e., averaging 31 %) whereas the nitrate compound is largest in the larger size range (i.e., averaging 31 %).

Figure 6-25. Average mass fractions of analyzed chemical compounds of impactor stages 1 and 2 (50/140 nm and 420/1200 nm aerodynamic diameter) throughout *VoLE 99*.

The average carbon fractions are also very similar between the two size ranges (cf. Tab. 6-13). The fraction of OC is about 75 % of the total carbon, with EC constituting about 25 % of the total carbon. Again, the majority of the organic carbon fraction is dominated by the volatile OC^I fraction, being about twice to four times as large as OC^{II}, and being slightly larger in the larger size range (i.e., 140/420 nm).

	50 – 140 nm	140 – 420 nm
OC / TC [%]	76 ± 14	74 ± 16
EC / TC [%]	24 ± 14	26 ± 16
OC / EC	3.4 ± 2.5	3.0 ± 2.0
OC ^I / TC [%]	49 ± 13	60 ± 2.8
OC ^{II} / TC [%]	27 ± 12	14 ± 8.2
OC ^I / OC ^{II}	1.8 ± 0.8	4.2 ± 2.5

Table 6-13. Average ratios between the different fractions of OC (OC^I+OC^{II}), EC, and TC.

6.2.6. Comparison of Chemical Analysis and Non-volatile Fractions derived from VTDMA

Volume fractions of non-volatile compounds derived from VTDMA measurements give a good estimate of the maximum amount of non-volatile carbon at a particular size. Nevertheless, the definition “*non-volatile carbon*” is method-based and depends on the temperature the aerosol particles are exposed to during the conditioning process. Although elemental carbon is clearly assigned to this category, there is still a wide variety of organic particulate matter showing various degrees of volatility. Similarly, a variety of methods exist using different temperatures to

distinguish between elemental and organic carbon (cf. Chap. 2.3), ranging from about 300° to more than 600 °C for bulk aerosol. The VTDMA method is unique due to its capability to separate and on-line examine monodisperse aerosol particles. Of particular interest is the comparison of non-volatile volume fractions with carbon mass fractions derived from the chemical measurements. The different characteristics of both methods are specified in Table 6-14.

Characteristics	VTDMA	Chemical Impactor / Thermal Desorption	Assumptions
Sampling Method	on-line / airborne	bulk / substrate	
Particle Size	quasi-monodisperse	size range	
Equivalent Diameter D_p	Mobility-equivalent ($D_{p,geo}$)*	aerodynamic ($D_{p,aero}$)	Density ρ $D_{p,geo} = D_{p,aero} / \sqrt{\rho}$
Technique	Thermal conditioning / volatilization	thermal conditioning / volatilization (& oxidation)	
Volatilization Temperature	280°C	590 °C	
Investigated Compound	all non-volatile	non-volatile carbon	
Derived Parameter	Volume fraction Φ_V	Mass fraction Φ_M	Density parameter $\vartheta(\rho)$ $\vartheta(\rho) = \Phi_M / \Phi_V$

Table 6-14. Comparison of method-specific characteristics of VTDMA and chemical analysis. Assumed density ρ and density parameter $\vartheta(\rho)$ are specified in Equations 6-3 and 6-5, respectively. *Note, the mobility-equivalent diameter equals the geometric diameter $D_{p,geo}$ only for spherical particles.

For the comparison, the volatility size distributions during *VoLE 99* were averaged over the individual chemical sampling periods (sample 1–11) (cf. Tab. 6-11). The results of the averaged non-volatile volume fractions Φ_V of 150 nm aerosol particles at 280 °C derived from VTDMA measurements are summarized in Table 6-15, along with the mean number concentrations of the 150 nm particles. Over the entire measurement period, Φ_V averages 18 ± 4 % for 150 nm particles. The highest values of Φ_V do not necessarily correspond with the highest aerosol concentrations (cf. Fig. 6-13) but might be rather indicative for the conditions during the aerosol formation process. Since the coldest time periods with clear, sunny conditions (i.e., samples 1 - 3 and 9-11) suggest highest emissions from residence heating, increased non-volatile volume fractions are expected. Φ_V ranges between 17 and 25 % for samples 1 - 3. The second time period (i.e., samples 9 - 11) with increased aerosol concentrations coincides with a weekend during which vehicle traffic is significantly reduced. However, the non-volatile volume is still increased and shows values between 16 and 22 %. During the intermediate precipitation period the refractory volume fractions are generally lower.

Sample	$N_{150\text{nm}}$ [cm^{-3}]	Φ_V [%]	Sample	$N_{150\text{nm}}$ [cm^{-3}]	Φ_V [%]
1	186	17	7	26	14
2	179	19	8	25	19
3	240	25	9	70	22
4	105	20	10	61	23
5	60	12	11	75	16
6	38	16	<u>mean:</u>	97 ± 73	18 ± 4.0

Table 6-15. VTDMA-derived volume fractions (Φ_V) of 150 particles after conditioning to 280 °C, averaged over impactor sampling times (cf. Tab. 6-11).

For the intercomparison of VTDMA-derived non-volatile aerosol fractions and chemically-determined EC and OC fractions one is confronted with the problem of assuming a density for the VTDMA-derived data which are volume-based, whereas chemically-derived data are mass-based. Both quantities are related by the density of associated compounds. Furthermore, the particle size for the chemical analysis is described by an aerodynamic sampling diameter. For VTDMA measurements, particle size is expressed as mobility-equivalent diameter. The mobility diameter is similar to the geometric diameter only if the particles in question are spherical (measurement uncertainties due to particle non-sphericity affects aerodynamic impactor sampling as well). The shape of the particles, however, is unknown. They might be spheres and, in the case of non-volatile carbon compounds, chains and agglomerates of primary particles (cf. Fig. 6-21). Geometric diameter $D_{p,geo}$ and aerodynamic diameter $D_{p,aero}$ are related by particle density ρ through

$$D_{p,geo} = D_{p,aero} / \sqrt{\rho} . \quad (6-3)$$

Although the density of graphite is as high as $2.22 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (Cotton et al., 1988), the density of BC is believed to be smaller than $2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (Wagner, 1981). For BC consisting of chains of individual spherules, often a density of $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ is used (Schultz, 1993; Hitzenberger et al., 1999). In other studies, values lower than $1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ were assumed for particles that are not spherical and/or contain fluffy material (Zier and Goetz, 1982; Samson et al., 1987).

For comparing non-volatile volume fractions $\Phi_{V(150\text{nm})}$ of 150 nm particles with mass fractions of OC and EC the value of the density ρ is crucial for considering the appropriate particle size range. For a density of $0.87 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ the geometric diameter of 150 nm complies with the aerodynamic diameter of 140 nm separating the impactor stages one and two (i.e., 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm, respectively). For $\rho < 0.87 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ the particle diameter of 150 nm needs to be compared with the smaller size range, i.e., 50 to 140 nm, whereas for $\rho > 0.87 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ the corresponding size range is 140 to 420 nm (cf. Eqn. 6-3). Both cases are illustrated in Figures 6-26 and 6-27, respectively. Displayed are $\Phi_{V(150\text{nm})}$ and the individual contributions from the chemical analysis: OC^I , OC^{II} , EC, and a quantity termed as TC-OC^I . TC-OC^I defines the mass fraction of particles being refractory at 280 °C, and is ultimately the ‘non-volatile’ carbon (mass) fraction that is directly compared with the values for $\Phi_{V(150\text{nm})}$ of monodisperse aerosol particles, and termed Φ_M in the following. Except

for the VTDMA-derived volume fraction Φ_V , all other quantities denote mass fractions. It is obvious in both figures that the curves of $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$ and Φ_M correlate well, with the non-volatile volume fraction (averaging 18 ± 4.0 %) being generally larger than Φ_M (averaging 17 ± 6.5 % and 11 ± 3.9 , respectively). The relative deviation δ_{rel} of the individual sample values, defined as

$$\delta_{rel} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\sqrt{(\Phi_M - \Phi_{V(150nm)})^2}}{\Phi_{V(150nm)}}. \quad (6-4)$$

results in differences of 23 % and 39 % between $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$ and Φ_M of the smaller (50-140 nm) and the larger (140 – 420 nm) size range, respectively. However, since the results for Φ_V and Φ_M represent different parameters (i.e., volume and mass fractions) they will be compared by introducing a density parameter $\mathcal{G}(\rho)$, as

$$\mathcal{G}(\rho) = \frac{\Phi_M}{\Phi_V}, \text{ with} \quad (6-5)$$

$$\Phi_M = \frac{\rho_M V_M}{\rho_{total} V_{total}} \quad \text{and} \quad \Phi_V = \frac{V_{non-volatile}}{V_{unconditioned}}. \quad (6-6, 6-7)$$

with ρ and V indicating density and volume of the according quantity. Thus,

$$\mathcal{G}(\rho) = \frac{\rho_M}{\rho_{total}} \cdot \frac{V_M}{V_{non-volatile}} \cdot \frac{V_{unconditioned}}{V_{total}}. \quad (6-8)$$

Therefore, the density parameter $\mathcal{G}(\rho)$ is dependent on the ratio of the density of TC-OC^I (ρ_M) to that of the total aerosol (ρ_{total}) and, furthermore, on the ratios of the volume of the conditioned (V_M , $V_{non-volatile}$) to the unconditioned aerosol (V_{total} , $V_{unconditioned}$). The volume ratios essentially reflect the method-based differences (cf. Tab. 6-14). For $\mathcal{G}(\rho) = 1$ we can infer from above equations that Φ_V and Φ_M are solely a function of ρ_M and ρ_{total} . If we calculate $\mathcal{G}(\rho)$ from the measured volume and mass fractions, we obtain average values of 0.95 ± 0.29 and 0.61 ± 0.16 for comparing $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$ with $\Phi_{M(50/140nm)}$ and $\Phi_{M(140/420nm)}$, respectively. The question is, if the refractory volume derived by the VTDMA can be attributed entirely to non-volatile carbon, or if it contains a certain fraction of less volatile organic carbon or other non-volatile compounds. The less volatile organic carbon fraction determined by the thermodesorption method is defined OC^{II}.⁵ OC^{II}_(50/140nm) averaged over all samples yields a value of 8.9 ± 4.2 % and OC^{II}_(140/420nm) averages 3.9 ± 2.4 %. This indicates that for aerosol particles between 50 and 140 nm about 35 %, and for particles between 140 and 420 nm about 19 % of the TOC can be apportioned to the less volatile compound OC^{II}. These values represent possible fractions of organic material that are identified as non-volatile by the VTDMA method, assuming that thermal conditioning of bulk samples (containing a range of particle sizes)

⁵ OC^I + OC^{II} + EC = TC. Therefore, OC^{II} + EC = TC - OC^I = Φ_M and, thus, OC^{II} = Φ_M - EC.

Figure 6-26. VTDMA-derived volume fractions ($\Phi_{V(150nm)}$) of non-volatile compounds of 150 nm particles (solid) and chemically-derived mass fractions of TC-OC₁^I (dashed), OC₁^I (white), OC₁^{II} (gray), and EC₁ (black dotted) of the particle size range 50 to 140 nm aerodynamic diameter.

Figure 6-27. VTDMA-derived volume fractions ($\Phi_{V(150nm)}$) of non-volatile compounds of 150 nm particles (solid) and chemically-derived mass fractions of TC-OC₂^I (dashed), OC₂^I (white), OC₂^{II} (gray), and EC₂ (black dotted) of the particle size range 140 to 420 nm aerodynamic diameter.

behaves similar to that of airborne quasi-monodisperse particles which is not necessarily likely. Based on the results from the calibration measurements demonstrating that the volatility temperature of quasi-monodisperse (sulfate) particles is lower than that of bulk samples (cf. Chap. 4.2), the potential fraction of less volatile organic carbon that can not be evaporated in the VTDMA system is assumed to be even lower. The fraction of non-volatile material that is not carbonaceous (e.g., traces of sea-salt, crustal material, fly ash) can not be inferred from both methods.

In general, the intercomparison between VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fractions and chemically-derived carbon mass fractions show good agreement. However, a large uncertainty still exists due to method-based differences, i.e., for comparing monodisperse particles with particle size ranges, assuming a density for converting mobility-equivalent diameters to aerodynamic diameters, applying different conditioning temperatures (280 °C versus 590 °C), comparing volume with mass fractions, and comparing total non-volatile fractions with non-volatile carbon fractions. The VTDMA has the advantage of sampling airborne particles of a specific size with high temporal resolution. Lack of mass is no handicap since particles at small concentrations can be measured at sizes smaller than 100 nm. A summary of advantages and disadvantages of both methods is given in Table 6-16.

VTDMA	Chemical Impactor / Thermal Desorption
<u>Advantage</u>	<u>Disadvantage</u>
+ good temporal resolution (~ 10 min)	– poor temporal resolution (~ hours)
+ good size resolution (quasi-monodisperse sizes)	– poor size resolution (size range)
+ results for non-volatile compounds residing in small particle sizes (> 15 nm)	– high uncertainty in smallest size range (0.05-0.14 µm aerodynamic) due to small mass
+ adequate results for small atmospheric concentrations	– high uncertainties for small atmospheric concentrations (→ long sampling times)
<u>Disadvantage</u>	<u>Advantage</u>
– non-volatile compounds = non-volatile carbon?	+ carbon-specific determination
– volatilization temperature T_{\max} : 280 °C	+ volatilization temperature T_{\max} : arbitrary
– $D_{p, \max}$: 150 – 250 nm	+ $D_{p, \max}$: 10 µm
– possible uncertainties due to non-sphericity of sampled particles	+ independence of particle shape

Table 6-16. Advantages and disadvantages of VTDMA and Thermodesorption method for determining non-volatile (carbon) fractions.

6.2.7. Summary

The composition of submicrometer urban aerosol particles was investigated with respect to their non-volatile constituents during a cold winter period in the city of Leipzig. Urban aerosols contain a significant fraction of non-volatile (carbonaceous) material which is due to the proximity to local vehicle traffic, residential and industrial emissions. The meteorological conditions favored an

enhanced occurrence of combustion aerosol particles. The VTDMA measurement period was subdivided into six characteristic sub-periods for which the measured volatility distributions were averaged. Although the overall particle concentration varied considerably, all 280 °C-volatility distributions were very similar. Generally, the residual distributions of refractory compounds show a multimodal structure with two significant modes: one *quasi-non-volatile* mode near the initially selected particle diameter and a further, broad mode at smaller particle diameters, indicating a variety of different sources (cf. Chap. 5). A constant mode near the initially selected particle diameter characterizes the aerosol particles to mainly consist of non-volatile material. The non-volatile number fraction of 150 nm particles remains constant after conditioning to 280 °C. This suggests that all initial particles contain non-volatile cores. The distributions indicate further that the volume fractions of these non-volatile cores (and therefore also the corresponding volatile fraction) can vary between small and very large. The non-volatile volume of initially 150 nm particles varies between 12 and 24 % and has an average value of about 18 %. About 13 % of all 150 nm particles can be attributed to the *quasi-non-volatile* fraction, i.e., contain mostly non-volatile material. The highest non-volatile volume fractions coincide with time periods of highest aerosol concentration and coldest temperatures. Morphological analysis indicates that the refractory particles are carbonaceous because of their typical structure, representing spheres as well as chain aggregates or clusters.

To investigate the non-volatile compounds of these urban particles, the size-segregated chemical composition of the submicrometer particles was analyzed. The results show that the total carbon (TC) mass fraction of all submicrometer aerosol particles, consisting of organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC), is high, averaging 23 ± 9 %. TC is partitioned between more volatile organic carbon (OC^I , 59 %), less volatile organic carbon (OC^{II} , 16 %), and elemental carbon (EC, 25 %). Thus, the carbon mass is dominated by organic carbon. The remaining mass of the submicrometer particles mainly consists of nitrate (31 %), sulfate (16 %), and ammonium (14 %). VTDMA-derived, non-volatile volume fractions Φ_V of 150 nm particles were compared with chemically-derived carbon mass fractions $\Phi_M (= TC - OC^I)$ at volatilization temperatures of 280 °C in two size ranges, 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm. For the comparison, Φ_V was averaged over the total of 11 chemical samples. Both parameters, Φ_V and Φ_M , agree well, with Φ_V (averaging 18 %) being larger than Φ_M (averaging 17 % and 11 % for size ranges 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm, respectively). Corresponding density parameter, representing the ratio between Φ_M and Φ_V , has a mean value of 0.95 and 0.61, respectively. As part of the total organic carbon, an average OC^{II} fraction (analyzed at temperatures of 590 °C) of 35 % in the lower and 19 % in the larger size range, respectively, is identified as less volatile organic and therefore potentially missed by the VTDMA method. Assuming that both, monodisperse particles and bulk particles behave differently (i.e., monodisperse particles are believed to evaporate at lower temperatures than samples containing a range of particles (cf. Chap. 4.2)), this fraction is possibly smaller. The chemically analyzed EC fraction averages 8.5 ± 7.5 % and 7.3 ± 4.1 % for both size ranges, respectively. Remaining discrepancies between Φ_V and Φ_M might be due to other, non-volatile compounds, e.g., sea-salt, crustal material, or fly ash. However, the differences are presumably method-based. Because of the differences in methods, the results of the comparison are very satisfactory.

Although the non-volatile particle fraction Φ_v derived by the VTMDA can not be identified more specifically, the results of the morphological and chemical analysis demonstrate that the majority of Φ_v can be attributed to the non-volatile carbon compound. The VTDMA uses an airborne technique and is capable of sampling small monodisperse particles with short temporal resolution, which represents a great advantage over conventional chemical analysis techniques.

6.3. AEROSOLS OF MODERATELY POLLUTED AIR MASSES

The non-volatile fraction of fine aerosol particles is expected to decrease with increasing distance from combustion sources, largely due to a decrease of the carbonaceous portion. Compared to urban locations, the concentration of elemental carbon in non-urban and remote location is smaller by about one or two orders of magnitude (cf. Chap. 2.2.1). Trace concentrations are recorded in marine background regions which are due to long-range tropospheric transport and associated residence time of these fine particles (~ order of days to a week). The longer the residence time of continental air masses in polluted regions, the higher the uptake of carbonaceous material. Thus, the fraction of elemental carbon is considered a tracer for anthropogenic air pollution. Continental submicrometer aerosols examined at a distance from urban locations represent transformed particles, being more or less influenced by anthropogenic processes. The volatility of such particles of moderately polluted air masses is investigated within the *LACE 98* field study, aimed at understanding the physico-chemical and optical aerosol properties and related processes in an anthropogenically-influenced atmosphere.

6.3.1. The Lindenberg Aerosol Characterization Experiment (*LACE 98*)

The objectives of *LACE 98* were to characterize aerosol particles of moderately polluted air masses in central Europe with respect to their microphysical, chemical, and optical properties and related processes, to pursue closure between differently measured and modeled quantities, and finally to assess their relevance to radiative forcing and climate. The field study encompassed a large number of research platforms and instrumentation involving both, in-situ and remote measurement techniques, focusing on local as well as column closure experiments. In this study the discussion of the aerosol characterization focuses on the parameters employed for a volatility-related discussion.

6.3.1.1. Sampling Site, Instrumentation and Meteorology

The *LACE 98* campaign was conducted in a non-urban region about 70 km south-east of Berlin (14° 8' E, 52° 0' N). The in-situ measurements covered a period of about four weeks between July 13 and August 14, 1998 (the entire measurement campaign encompassed the Julian Day period 193 – 224). The instrumentation for the in-situ characterization comprised physical, chemical, and optical aerosol sensors and samplers. The samples for the physical and chemical aerosol characterization were taken from a 10 m high inlet stack, preceded by a low-flow Andersen PM₁₀ and modified high-flow Andersen PM₁₀ inlet, respectively. A summary of the instrumentation discussed in this chapter is listed in Table 6-17. The immediate environment of the measurement site has agricultural-rural characteristics, mixed with local industries and smaller towns. Due to its location in East-Germany close to the Polish border the air masses reaching the area were influenced by a number of larger cities with associated industries and traffic at a distance of about

Instrument	Analyzed Parameter
VTDMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Volatility number distribution ▶ Number and volume of non-volatile components
5-stage-Berner Impactor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Anions, cations (IC/CE) ▶ OC, EC
PSAP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Absorption coefficient (→ BC)
Meteorological Instruments / Synoptic Charts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ T, p, RH, w_s, w_d ▶ Medium-scale synoptic analysis, backtrajectories

Table 6-17. Instrumentation and analyzed parameter during the *LACE 98* field campaign. IC and CE denote the chemical analytical methods of ion chromatography and capillary electrophoresis, respectively.

50 to 100 km, particularly to the northwest, southwest, and especially to the east. The predominant wind direction was from northwest to southwest, associated with the passage of low pressure systems embedded in the prevailing westerlies. During the initial part of the experiment and at times throughout the field campaign, low pressure systems over Scandinavia carried cold maritime polar air masses (mP) to the site. These moist and unstable air masses were warmed from below as they crossed the continent, lifted and, thus, frequently caused showers and thunderstorms. Depending on their route, these marine air masses were continentally influenced as they moved across Europe. Southwesterly winds ahead of approaching large troughs over Europe carried maritime tropical air masses (mT) into the region, usually associated with warm and moist conditions. High pressure system over central Europe, typical for this season, occurred rarely, but were generally accompanied by low winds speeds, often from the east or southeast. The complete time series of the meteorological parameters recorded at the measurement station at an altitude of 10 m are displayed in Figure 6-28. Due to industries and power plants in these regions, the air masses are expected to be relatively strongly polluted.

In order to distinguish the different aerosol types relevant at the site, they were categorized into different types. For the air mass analysis, 72 hr-backtrajectories (950, 850, and 700 mb level), surface maps, meteorological parameters, as well as the measured chemical aerosol composition were considered. The air mass types arriving at the measurement site were classified into four categories (A-D) (cf. Fig. 6-29). Category A represents marine air masses which were, themselves, sub-categorized to capture the different pollution levels (i.e., ranging from clean-marine (A₀), less polluted-marine (A₁) to more polluted-marine (A₂) and marine, potentially Berlin-influenced (A₃)). Air mass types B and D represent air which stayed most of the time over the continent and are therefore classified according to their origin, i.e., direction. Air masses passing over Berlin were defined as ‘potentially Berlin-influenced’ (type C).

Figure 6-28. Time series of measured meteorological parameters during LACE 98.

Figure 6-29. Major air mass types arriving at the LACE 98 measuring site.

6.3.2. Aerosol Volatility during *LACE 98*

The VTDMA measurements were carried out throughout the *LACE 98* campaign. The set-up for the volatility measurements was chosen at selected initial particle diameters of 150 and 50 nm. Volatility studies were conducted at conditioning temperatures of ambient 25 °, 80 °, 180 °, and 280 °C. An example of volatility distributions at these temperatures is shown in Figure 6-30, each representing an average distribution during a 24 hr period between Julian Day 218.3 and 219.3. Corresponding non-volatile number and volume fractions at respective temperature steps are listed in Table 6-18.

Figure 6-30. Average, normalized volatility spectra of number size distribution of 150 nm particles conditioned to 25 °C (ambient), 80 °C, 180 °C, and 280 °C between Julian Day 218.3 and 219.3.

The averaged volatility scans shown above represent typical polluted-marine cases (air mass type ‘A1/A2’), originating in the northern Atlantic region and having passed over Great Britain and northern Germany. During their journey over continental emission regions, the aerosol particles were possibly transformed and are, therefore, aged (a likely transformation process is the neutralization of sulfuric acid to ammonium bisulfate and ammonium sulfate by ammonium). The aerosol particles are influenced by processes such as condensation, coagulation, or mixing with other air masses.

The initial monomodal volatility spectrum of selected 150 nm particles at ambient temperatures has its average diameter at about 148 nm. This slight decrease at ambient conditions (corresponding to a decrease of about 1–2 % in diameter), typically observed during VTDMA measurements (cf. Chap. 6.2.2), corresponds to a volume fraction of 4 %. The more volatile components evaporate at

Conditioning Temperature [°C]	$\Phi_{N,i}$	$\Phi_{N,qnv,i}$	$\Phi_{V,i}$	$\Phi_{V,qnv,i}$	$\Phi_{S,i}$
80	100 ± 2.3	-	86 ± 0.7	-	94
180	101 ± 8.6	6.3 ± 1.4	17 ± 0.5	5.9 ± 1.1	100 , 42
280	98 ± 15	4.9 ± 0.1	11 ± 0.4	4.7 ± 0.0	99 , 25

Table 6-18. Derived number fraction ($\Phi_{N,i}$), volume fraction ($\Phi_{V,i}$), size ratio ($\Phi_{S,i}$), as well as pertinent *quasi-non-volatile* number and volume fractions, $\phi_{N,ext}$ and $\phi_{V,ext}$, respectively, of average volatility distributions between Julian Day 218.3 and 219.3 for selected 150 nm particles.

a conditioning temperature of 80 °C, resulting in a decrease in size by 6 % and in volume by 14 %. The particle number remains constant at 80 °C (i.e., $\Phi_{N,80^\circ C}$ is 100 %). After conditioning to 180 °C, i.e., after all sulfate compounds are evaporated (cf. Chap. 4.2), the volatility distribution is modified, revealing a multimodal structure with two significant modes: a first *quasi-non-volatile* mode, centered around a diameter of 148 nm, and a second *partially-non-volatile* mode near 60 nm. The *quasi-non-volatile* mode characterizes the particles to be almost completely non-volatile at this temperature step. The total number fraction $\Phi_{N,180^\circ C}$ still remains unchanged, with the *quasi-non-volatile* number fraction $\phi_{N,qnv,180^\circ C}$ comprising about 6 % of all aerosol particles. The total volume is greatly reduced by about 83 % compared to the initial volume. The remaining aerosol compounds at 280 °C represent all residual refractory material. The volatility distribution similarly shows two significant modes at 147 nm and 38 nm, respectively. The total particle number is still constant (98 %) but the total, non-volatile volume at 280 °C decreased to about 11 %. About 5 % of all residual particles pertain to those particles that are unaffected by thermal conditioning and experience no evaporative losses (i.e., excluding the 1-2 % diameter losses at ambient conditions).

Figure 6-31 contrasts the volatility distributions from *LACE 98* in a moderately polluted air mass with those of previously discussed urban particles from the *VoLE 99* campaign, representative for aerosols in a heavily polluted air mass (cf. Fig. 6-12). The structure of the distributions after conditioning differs in the two cases. The shape of the 80 °C distribution of non-urban aerosol particles (*LACE 98*) is narrower and contains a smaller fraction of material that evaporates at 80 °C compared to urban particles. Corresponding volume fractions are 86 % versus 78 %, respectively. This might be explained by a large fraction of compounds present as ammonium sulfate which is stable at 80 °C compared to urban particles, containing large amounts of nitrate which is volatile (cf. Chap. 6.2.5). The distributions of non-volatile compounds at 180° and 280 °C reveal different shapes as well. The *quasi-non-volatile* mode is much smaller in the moderately polluted case. Furthermore, the particles with a non-volatile core and various amounts of volatile material shape a mode that is narrower and located at smaller diameters. Corresponding residual distribution of urban particles appears multimodal with a broad mode at larger particle diameters. Resulting non-volatile volume fractions are therefore larger in the more heavily polluted case at 280 °C, amounting to 27 % compared to 11 % for aerosols in moderately polluted air masses.

Figure 6-31. Normalized volatility distributions of 150 nm particles conditioned to 25 °C (ambient), 80 °C, 180 °C, and 280 °C in a) moderately polluted, non-urban locations (*LACE 98*) and b) strongly polluted, urban locations (*VoLE 99*).

The corresponding number and volume fractions of both cases at the individual temperature steps are listed in Table 6-19 below.

Conditioning Temperature [°C]	Moderately polluted		Strongly polluted	
	$\Phi_{N,i}$	$\Phi_{V,i}$	$\Phi_{N,i}$	$\Phi_{V,i}$
80	100	86	100	78
180	101	17	110	37
280	98	11	100	27

Table 6-19. Derived number and volume fractions, $\Phi_{N,i}$ and $\Phi_{V,i}$ of 150 nm particles of moderately (*LACE 98*) and strongly polluted (*VoLE 99*) regions.

For a comprehensive analysis of the aerosol volatile behavior of 150 nm aerosol particles throughout *LACE 98*, the study period was divided into different subperiods (L1 – L26). These periods correspond to the chemical sampling times for which the volatility scans were averaged, usually encompassing between 8 and 24 hr periods (cf. Tab. 6-20). In order to show the variability of the volatility distributions over a given time interval of 24 hrs, the (not normalized) measured ambient and conditioned 280 °C scans of sample L19 are plotted in Fig. 6-32 (note: the corresponding average distributions and derived number and volume fractions were previously displayed in Fig. 6-30 and Tab. 6-18, respectively).

Sample	Julian Day	Sample	Julian Day
L1	194.44 - 195.42	L14	214.80 - 215.35
L2	200.34 - 200.78	L15	216.31 - 216.78
L3	200.83 - 201.33	L16	216.81 - 217.24
L4	201.35 - 201.66	L17	217.26 - 217.78
L5	204.39 - 204.76	L18	217.81 - 218.29
L6	204.80 - 205.29	L19	218.32 - 219.30
L7	205.32 - 205.79	L20	219.33 - 219.70
L8	205.83 - 206.31	L21	220.33 - 220.82
L9	206.35 - 207.30	L22	220.84 - 221.30
L10	209.36 - 209.77	L23	221.32 - 221.79
L11	211.29 - 212.26	L24	221.82 - 222.29
L12	212.29 - 212.73	L25	222.32 - 222.72
L13	214.33 - 214.77	L26	222.75 - 223.71

Table 6-20. Characteristic Julian Day time periods during *LACE 98*, corresponding to chemical sampling times (cf. Chap. 6.3.3).

Sample L19 represents a time period of relatively stable meteorological conditions with wind speeds of $3.0 \pm 1.6 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ (initially higher and decreasing towards the second half of the time period), and wind directions of $245 \pm 41^\circ$, i.e., westerly. Figure 6-33 displays the corresponding normalized distributions (with respect to the current 150 nm particle concentration) of the

Figure 6-32. Measured volatility distributions of ambient and conditioned 150 nm particles during 24 hr period between Julian Day 218.32 and 219.3 corresponding to sample L19. Indicated is also the initial particle diameter at 150 nm.

Figure 6-33. Normalized volatility distributions of conditioned 150 nm particles during 24 hr period between Julian Day 218.32 and 219.3. Indicated is also the initial particle diameter at 150 nm.

conditioned particles. Figure 6-33 indicates that individual distributions are similar, however, they show subtle differences in the amplitude and diameter of the second mode, possibly due to different transformation processes. The above example demonstrates the advantage of this airborne technique, allowing to retrieve information about the aerosol with high temporal resolution. For all sampling periods L1 through L26, number (Φ_N) and volume (Φ_V) fractions of the refractory compounds were derived for the initially selected 150 nm particles. The results are illustrated in Figure 6-34. Throughout *LACE 98*, Φ_N ranges between 93 and 102 %, indicating that the total particle number remains constant. This signifies that all 150 nm particles contain a non-volatile core. In contrast to particle number, the total volume largely evaporated during conditioning, with individual values for Φ_V ranging on average between 8 and 21 %. Mean values for Φ_N and Φ_V over all individual sample periods yield 98 ± 2.1 % and 11 ± 2.9 %, respectively.

Figure 6-34. Non-volatile number (gray) and volume (black) fractions of 150 nm particles, Φ_N and Φ_V , respectively, derived from average 280 °C-volatility distributions of individual time periods during *LACE 98*.

Errors in Φ_N and Φ_V due to multiply-charged particles, similar as in *VoLE 99* (cf. Chap. 6.2.3), are considered small. In average, about 25 % of the selected particles are doublets of 235 nm size, and about 5 % are triplets of 313 nm size. The total particle number is conserved (Φ_N is 100 %), therefore, the uncertainties due to multiple charging remain constant before and after heating and consequently cancel out. Similar is true for Φ_V if we assume that singly- and multiply-charged refractory particles are distributed evenly within the residual size range, all representing initially selected accumulation mode particles.

Figure 6-35 illustrates the partitioning of Φ_N and Φ_V in *quasi-non-volatile* and *partially-non-volatile* portions, with respect to both, number and volume. On average, 6.1 ± 1.9 % of all 150 nm particles are *quasi-non-volatile*, i.e., contain almost exclusively non-volatile compounds, encompassing 5.8 ± 2.1 % of the total volume. Although $\phi_{N,qnv}$ is relatively small, $\phi_{V,qnv}$ amounts to about half of the total non-volatile portion. A summary of all derived parameters is listed in Table 6-21.

Figure 6-35. *Quasi-non-volatile* (solid) and *partially-non-volatile* (hatched) portion of the non-volatile number (Φ_N) and volume fractions (Φ_V) of 150 nm particles for the individual time periods.

Figure 6-36 shows average, normalized volatility distributions of 150 and 50 nm particles over the entire *LACE 98* time period. The 150 nm distribution shows a small mode at approximately 144 nm and a more significant peak between 30 and 40 nm. In contrast, the 50 nm distribution is almost flat above 20 nm, indicating that completely non-volatile particles do not occur. The majority of the non-volatile material is located at diameters smaller than 20 nm, a size range associated with high measurement uncertainties (note, the distributions are only shown for diameters larger than 15 nm due to the VTDMA efficiency). Therefore, the entire 50 nm distribution is not covered and is shown only qualitatively.

Time Period	150nm				Time Period	150nm			
	Φ_N	Φ_V	$\Phi_{N,qnv}$	$\Phi_{V,qnv}$		Φ_N	Φ_V	$\Phi_{N,qnv}$	$\Phi_{V,qnv}$
L1	100	11	7.6	7.1	L15	99	8.6	4.5	4.4
L2	96	8.8	4.7	4.1	L16	-	-	-	-
L3	102	7.7	3.8	3.5	L17	99	8.1	4.1	3.9
L4	99.2	8.5	4.3	3.7	L18	97	9.5	4.6	4.3
L5	100	11	6.0	5.7	L19	98	11	4.9	4.7
L6	99	12	8.4	7.8	L20	99	9.0	3.5	3.3
L7	99	9.2	5.8	5.5	L21	95	8.4	4.4	4.3
L8	99	11	7.3	11	L22	99	15	6.9	6.4
L9	98	10	5.7	5.0	L23	98	11	4.7	4.5
L10	100	11	6.3	6.3	L24	96	21	9.1	8.2
L11	100	12	8.0	7.2	L25	94	13	4.6	4.4
L12	99	8.7	5.2	4.8	L26	93	13	8.1	6.9
L13	97	14	9.2	8.8					
L14	99	14	10	9.6	mean	98 ± 2.1	11 ± 2.9	6.1 ± 1.9	5.6 ± 1.8

Table 6-21. Calculated fractions of non-volatile aerosol compounds from averaged volatility distributions of 150 nm particles for the individual time.

Figure 6-36. Mean, normalized volatility distribution of initially selected 150 nm (upper graphs) and 50 nm particles (lower graphs) conditioned to 280 °C (solid) of the individual time periods. The dashed line indicates associated standard deviation, the short dotted line the initial particle diameter.

6.3.3. Chemical Aerosol Characterization

The chemical characterization involved two 5-stage, low pressure cascade impactors for particle sampling in the size range between 0.05 and 10 μm aerodynamic diameter. The sampling periods are denoted L1 through L26 (cf. Tab. 6-20). Particle sampling was performed at controlled RH of 60 %. Similar to the *VoLE 99* measurements, one impactor was used for the analysis of ionic compounds using capillary electrophoresis (CE⁶), the other for the determination of organic and elemental carbon by the thermodesorption/oxidation method. Cation and anion analysis included the species Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} . The carbonaceous compounds were differentiated between organic carbon (OC), representing the volatile carbon portion, and elemental carbon (EC), representing the non-volatile carbon portion. Both together yield total carbon (TC). The total organic mass is derived by multiplication of OC with a factor of 1.4 for aged aerosol particles (Jaenicke, 1978; Gray et al., 1986; Neusüß, 1999). The following chemical discussion focuses only on submicrometer particles, corresponding to impactor stages one through three. The results for the mass concentrations of the analyzed compounds for the individual sampling periods are displayed in Figure 6-37 (the individual compounds are listed in the order of their vertical appearance). Differences between the total analyzed and total (gravimetric) mass can be attributed to water (Neusüß, 1999). The total, analyzed submicrometer mass ranges between 1 and 13 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ with an average value of $6.3 \pm 3.2 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ over the entire *LACE 98* period. This

Figure 6-37. Mass concentrations of analyzed chemical compounds and total gravimetric mass of the individual samples of submicrometer aerosol particles encompassing impactor stages 1-3 (50-1200 nm aerodynamic diameter).

⁶ CE is an analytical separation method based on differences in the electrophoretic migration of charged species.

value is considerably smaller than that of urban aerosol particles sampled during *VoLE 99* by a factor of four to five (corresponding submicrometer mass averaged $28 \pm 11.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) (cf. Chap. 5.2.6). Average concentrations of the individual compounds over the entire *LACE 98* period are summarized in Table 6-22. The particle mass is mostly dominated by sulfate, carbon (Organics and EC), and ammonium. The concentration of TC is significantly lower than in urban areas (i.e., $2.3 \pm 1.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ versus $9.0 \pm 7.0 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). The contribution of nitrate is minor compared to urban particles. The ion balance shows that nearly all of the observed ammonium can be neutralized by

Chemical Compound	Mass Concentration [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$]	Chemical Compound	Mass Concentration [$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$]
Cl ⁻	0.01 ± 0.04	Ca ²⁺	0.02 ± 0.0
SO ₄ ²⁻	2.7 ± 1.8	Mg ²⁺	0.01 ± 0.0
NO ₃ ⁻	0.20 ± 0.35	Organics	1.5 ± 1.1
NH ₄ ⁺	0.95 ± 1.3	EC	0.84 ± 0.59
Na ⁺	0.05 ± 0.6	Total	6.3 ± 3.2
K ⁺	0.05 ± 0.05		

Table 6-22. Average concentrations of the submicrometer aerosol composition during *LACE 98*.

sulfate (the contribution of nitrate is minor). The mass fractions (as part of the total weighted mass) of the individual compounds for all submicrometer particles are illustrated in Figure 6-38. Sulfate and ammonium together comprise the main portion, (i.e., 41 %). The TC mass fractions of non-urban particles are surprisingly similar to those of urban particles during *VoLE 99*, averaging 27 % versus 26 %, respectively. The TC fraction is dominated by organics. The majority of the

Figure 6-38. Average mass fractions (in %) of analyzed chemical compounds of the submicrometer particles as part of the total gravimetric mass during *LACE 98*. K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and Cl⁻ are combined since their individual fraction are very low.

unidentified mass is due to water as derived from hygroscopic growth calculations (Neusüß, 1999). The above chemical composition is similar to the average fine particle composition of the non-urban aerosol derived from (Heintzenberg, 1989). During that study, non-urban aerosols also were found to be dominated by sulfate and ammonium, comprising almost half of the total mass, with TC still constituting about 20 – 30 % by mass (cf. Chap. 2.1). Since the analyzed carbon fractions corresponding to stage one and two of the impactor (i.e., 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm, respectively) are of importance for comparison with the VTDMA results, the individual contributions of OC, EC, and TC are illustrated in Figure 6-39. The average values for the individual stages are listed in Table 6-23. On average, OC is on the same order of magnitude as EC in both size ranges, representing 13 % and 10 – 11 %, respectively. Individual values, however, vary widely, depending on associated air mass type.

Figure 6-39. Mass fractions (in %) of OC (gray), EC (black), and TC (line) for the different impactor stages one (i.e., 50/140 nm) and two (i.e., 140/420 nm) during *LACE 98*.

	Mass Concentration [ng·m ⁻³]		Mass Fraction [%]	
	50 – 140 nm	140 – 420 nm	50 – 140 nm	140 – 420 nm
OC	120 ± 150	440 ± 320	13 ± 11	11 ± 6.1
EC	100 ± 70	440 ± 360	13 ± 6.8	10 ± 4.4
TC	220 ± 180	880 ± 600	26 ± 9.9	21 ± 6.1
OC / EC	-	-	1.0	1.1

Table 6-23. Mass concentrations and mass fractions of OC, EC, and TC, averaged over all individual samples, and corresponding OC/EC ratio for the impactor stages one and two (i.e., 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm, respectively) during *LACE 98*.

The next chapter will compare the chemically-derived carbon mass fractions with the VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fractions, followed by a discussion of relevant aerosol types during *LACE 98*.

6.3.4. Comparison of Chemical Analysis and Non-volatile Fractions derived from VTDMA

Analogous to the previous comparison for urban aerosol particles (cf. Chap. 6.2.6), the non-volatile aerosol fractions Φ_V of 150 nm particles derived from volatility measurements are compared to the non-volatile carbon fractions Φ_M determined from chemical analysis. Carbon mass was distinguished solely by OC and EC, i.e., individual fractions for less and more volatile OC are not available individually. Therefore, the comparison of Φ_V focuses on the EC mass fraction, denoted as $\Phi_{M,EC}$. Since the density of the non-volatile fraction is unknown, Φ_V is compared with $\Phi_{M,EC}$ of both size ranges: 50 to 140 nm (aerodynamic) and 140 to 420 nm, respectively (cf. Eqn. 6-3). Both cases are illustrated in Figures 6-40 and 6-41, respectively, for the samples L1 – L26 during *LACE 98*.

Comparison of Φ_V of 150 nm particles with $\Phi_{M,EC1}$ of the smaller size range (50 – 140 nm) shows a large difference (cf. Fig. 6-40). Discrepancies might be caused by the density of the non-volatile material, being larger than $0.87 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, suggesting that considered particle size range might not be adequate (note, the value of $0.87 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ corresponds to the density that exactly relates the geometric diameter of 150 nm to the aerodynamic diameter of 140 nm (cf. Eqn. 6-3)). However, a majority of the analyzed EC_1 values, indicated by EC_1^* , are close to the detection limit (due to little mass) and therefore highly uncertainty. Unfortunately, most of the chemically-derived values in the smaller size range are near the detection limit. Averaged over all samples, Φ_V and $\Phi_{M,EC1}$ yield $11 \pm 2.9 \%$ and $14 \pm 6.4 \%$, respectively, leading to a density parameter $\mathfrak{S}(\rho_{EC})$ that varies widely between 0.2 and 2.4 with a mean value of 1.3 ± 0.6 . Contrary to $\mathfrak{S}(\rho)$, $\mathfrak{S}(\rho_{EC})$ indicates that the considered non-volatile carbon mass is solely elemental and contains no less volatile organic compounds (cf. Chap. 6.2.6). $\mathfrak{S}(\rho)$, covering elemental carbon as well as the less volatile organic fraction, would yield even higher values. Due to the uncertainty associated with the EC values derived from chemically analysis a comparison remains difficult.

The results of the comparison of Φ_V with $\Phi_{M,EC2}$ of the larger size range (140 – 420 nm) show a correlation between both quantities (cf. Fig. 6-41). Overall, Φ_V and $\Phi_{M,EC2}$ are on average $11 \pm 2.9 \%$ and $12 \pm 2.9 \%$, respectively. Associated density parameter $\mathfrak{S}(\rho_{EC})$ averages 1.2 ± 0.3 . However, it is obvious from Figure 6-41 that Φ_V also correlates well with TC_2 (i.e., TC in the size range 140 – 420 nm), predominantly containing organic carbon (cf. Chap. 6.3.3). It is likely that the volume fraction expressed by Φ_V covers a fraction of less volatile organic material which did not evaporate at VTDMA conditioning temperatures of 280 °C. A quantitative comparison between VTDMA results and those of the chemical analysis remains difficult since both methods encompass different techniques, assumptions, and parameters (cf. Chap. 6-14). The comparison confirms, however, that the volume fractions inferred from VTDMA analysis are reasonable, allowing to detect non-volatile material for size-segregated particles in short time intervals.

Figure 6-40. Comparison of VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fractions (Φ_V) of 150 nm particles (solid) with non-volatile mass fractions of EC₁ ($=\Phi_{M,EC1}$, diamonds) and TC₁ (dotted) in the 50-140 nm particle size range. EC₁* (open diamonds) denotes those EC mass fractions being close to the detection limit (i.e., associated with higher uncertainty).

Figure 6-41. Comparison of VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fractions (Φ_V) of 150 nm particles (solid) with non-volatile mass fractions of EC₂ ($=\Phi_{M,EC2}$, diamonds) and TC₂ (dotted) in the 140-420 nm particle size range.

6.3.5. Non-volatile Fractions of Specific Aerosol Types

The air mass classification (A-D) during *LACE 98* was introduced earlier in this chapter (cf. Chap. 6.3.1.1). Four different aerosol types were defined which are characterized by different meteorological regimes (cf. Tab. 6-24).

Classification	Air Mass Type
A → A0	clean-marine
→ A1	less polluted-marine
→ A2	more polluted-marine
→ A3	marine, potentially Berlin-influenced
B	southwest-continental (mT)
C	potentially Berlin-influenced
D	east-continental / local

Table 6-24. Air mass classification during LACE 98 (cf. Fig. 6-29).

The individual 26 time periods were assigned to the above aerosol types. Between these, mixed types occurred since clear-cut situations did not always exist. The non-volatile volume fractions Φ_V for 150 nm particles was averaged for each aerosol type, encompassing between one and four samples. Figure 6-42 shows the results of the averaged aerosol type-dependent values for Φ_V . Also displayed are the corresponding results for the non-volatile carbon mass fractions $\Phi_{M,EC}$ determined

Figure 6-42. Non-volatile volume fractions Φ_V (solid) and non-volatile carbon mass fractions Φ_M (open) of different aerosol types. The error bars indicate associated standard deviation of the averaged samples. The numbers denote corresponding mean values for Φ_V (in %).

by the chemical analysis for the particle size range 140 – 420 nm. In general, the average values of Φ_V and $\Phi_{M,EC}$ for the different aerosol types vary between 9 and 15 % and 8 and 15 %, respectively. Differences between individual aerosol types are not large and often within the uncertainty range of each other. The continentally-influenced, marine particles (i.e., aerosol type A) contain on average 10.4 ± 2.0 % non-volatile material by volume. Except for aerosol type A0 (clean-marine), an increase in Φ_V seems to correlate with increasing pollution level (i.e., aerosol type A1 to A3), going from about 9 to 12 %. The high value for A0 might be caused by low winds leading to a larger influence of local pollution. Southwesterly-continental conditions as well as potential influences of the city of Berlin (i.e., aerosol type B and C, respectively) can not be detected in an increase of non-volatile material. Associated values for Φ_V are even lower than on average, being 9.1 ± 1.4 %. On the contrary, eastern continentally-influenced aerosol types (D) show remarkably higher non-volatile aerosol fractions, most likely caused by enhanced industrial emissions from Poland or the Czech Republic. Individual values for Φ_V are as high as 21 % and are on average 13.8 ± 4.4 %, the mean value for $\Phi_{M,EC}$ amounts to 13.5 ± 3.2 % by mass. $\Phi_{M,EC}$ shows a similar trend with aerosol type and mostly matches Φ_V well. The results for the individual aerosol types are listed in Table 6-25.

Aerosol Type	Φ_V [%] (150 nm)	# of Samples	Period	$\Phi_{M,EC}$ [%] (140-420 nm)
A0	11.7 ± 3.6	3	L21,22,23	9.4
A1	8.6	2 (1)	L15,16	8.1
A2	9.2 ± 0.4	2	L18, 20	12.8 ± 1.4
A3	11.6 ± 0.5	2	L6,8	12.7 ± 0.4
A1-A2	10.1 ± 1.6	4	L1,11,17,19	10.5 ± 3.0
A2-B	8.8	1	L2	11.2
A3-B	11.4	1	L5	
B	9.1 ± 1.8	3	L3,4,10	13.4 ± 3.0
C	9.2	1	L7	9
D	15.5 ± 4.8	3	L24,25,26	15.2 ± 5.2
B-C-D	12.1 ± 2.9	3	L12,13,14	11.7 ± 1.5

Table 6-25. Non-volatile volume fractions Φ_V of 150 nm particles and non-volatile carbon mass fractions $\Phi_{M,EC}$ for particles between 140 and 420 nm of different aerosol types.

6.3.6. Particle Absorption Measurements

Finally, Φ_V is compared to the results of PSAP (Particle Soot/Absorption Photometer) measurements which determine the absorption coefficient $\sigma_{a(10\mu\text{m})}$ for sub- and supermicrometer particles. BC concentrations are derived assuming an appropriate specific attenuation cross section σ_s , similar as in aethalometer measurements (cf. Chap. 6.2.7). Since σ_s varies depending on aerosol type and ranges between 2 and 25 $\text{m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, with low values found in remote regions and mid-high values in industrial locations (Liousse et al., 1993), a general assumption of σ_s over the entire LACE 98 study period is incorrect. Therefore, Φ_V for 150 nm particles is compared directly to the measured absorption coefficient $\sigma_{a(10\mu\text{m})}$. Figure 6-43 contrasts both methods for the individual sampling periods L1 to L26. $\sigma_{a(10\mu\text{m})}$ generally varies between 1 and 18 $\times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$, averaging $8.4 \pm 4.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$. It can be seen that, except for the initial time periods, $\sigma_{a(10\mu\text{m})}$ and Φ_V correlate well qualitatively, showing that a large fraction of the non-volatile determined by the VTDMA is possibly due to non-volatile carbon. Discrepancies, however, are possible due to comparing Φ_V of a particular quasi-monodisperse particle size with $\sigma_{a(10\mu\text{m})}$, encompassing a large size range of

Figure 6-43. Comparison of measured absorption coefficient σ_a ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$) and non-volatile volume fraction Φ_V (for 150 nm particles), averaged over the time periods L1-L26.

particles. Similar to Chapter 6.3.5, the values for $\sigma_{a(10\mu\text{m})}$ of the individual time periods L1 through L26 can be grouped according to the different aerosol types (cf. Tab. 6-25) to determine the influence of pollution level on the absorption coefficient. The results are displayed in Figure 6-44, along with the corresponding VTDMA-derived value for Φ_V . Differences between marine-continental samples (i.e., aerosol types A, A/B), averaging $6.8 \pm 2.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$, and eastern-continental samples (i.e., aerosol type D), averaging $12.7 \pm 6.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^{-1}$, are obvious. A potential influence of Berlin (i.e., aerosol types A3, C) can not be found either. Although only qualitatively,

the results of the PSAP measurements, representing the absorbing black carbon fraction, correlate well with those derived from the volatility measurements, confirming that non-volatile carbon seems to predominate the non-volatile particle fraction.

Figure 6-44. Absorption coefficients σ_a (solid) and corresponding non-volatile volume fractions Φ_V (open) of different aerosol types. The error bars indicate associated standard deviation of the averaged samples.

6.3.7. Summary

In this chapter, the volatility of rural aerosol particles at a distance from combustion sources was investigated. The *LACE 98* measurement site was located in a rural-agricultural environment in northeastern Germany. The measurement period was divided into 26 sampling periods for which the volatility distributions were averaged. The results from VTDMA measurements revealed that the typical distributions of non-volatile compounds at 150 nm are multimodal, with a small *quasi-non-volatile* mode near the initial diameter and another, more substantial *partially-non-volatile* mode at small diameters near 40 nm. The total number of particles did not change upon heating, indicating that all particles contain non-volatile cores. The total volume $\Phi_{V(150\text{ nm})}$ of the refractory material varies between 8 and 21 % and is on average 11 ± 2.9 %. About 6 % of all 150 nm particles are *quasi-non-volatile*, i.e., contain mostly non-volatile material. The chemical characterization showed that the majority of submicrometer aerosol mass is dominated by sulfate (31 %), ammonium (11 %), and total carbon (TC) (22 %), representing typical continentally-influenced, aged aerosols. TC is partitioned between organic (OC) and elemental carbon (EC) at a ratio of one to one. Similar to the above non-volatile volume fractions (averaging 11 %), derived values of non-volatile carbon mass fractions from chemical analysis over the entire *LACE 98* campaign average 12 ± 2.9 %. A comparison between both methods shows that $\Phi_{V(150\text{ nm})}$ correlates with the mass fractions of non-volatile carbon $\Phi_{M,EC}$ of the larger size range 140 – 420 nm.

However, it is likely that the VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume contains a fraction of less volatile organic compounds. In general, the results are very satisfactory considering the different nature of both methods. Averaged over all samples, the density parameter $\vartheta(\rho)$, representing the ratio between $\Phi_{M,EC}$ and $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$, is 1.3 ± 0.4 and 1.2 ± 0.3 for size ranges 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm, respectively. A classification of the non-volatile particle fractions Φ_V with respect to different aerosol types showed that continentally-influenced marine particles hold the smallest Φ_V , increasing with increasing pollution level, whereas eastern-continentally-influenced aerosol particles (i.e., from areas of enhanced industrial activity) have the highest non-volatile volume fractions. An influence of the city of Berlin could not be observed. A correlation between measured aerosol absorption coefficients (although the measurements consider all particles below 10 μm) and non-volatile volume fractions can be found, indicating that a large portion of the VTDMA-derived non-volatile material might contain non-volatile carbon. Overall, the results show that the fraction of non-volatile material of particles of moderately polluted air masses is smaller compared to those of strongly polluted urban regions.

6.4. SYNOPSIS

Previous chapters demonstrated and discussed the application of the volatility analyzer to the characterization of submicrometer aerosol particles. Volatility was measured during three field campaigns in different environments: at combustion sources, in a strongly polluted, urban environment, and in a moderately polluted, non-urban region. The distribution of the non-volatile aerosol compounds was investigated with respect to their number and volume, and furthermore compared to the carbonaceous mass fractions derived from chemical analysis. The key results from the measurements are contrasted and summarized in the following.

6.4.1. Volatility Size Distributions

The volatility size distributions of selected quasi-monodisperse aerosol particles at ambient temperatures (25 °C) and after the conditioning process (250/280 °C) for the three aerosol cases are displayed in Figure 6-45. They represent averaged, normalized distributions of particles measured (a) at combustion sources (*FORD 98*), (b) in a strongly polluted, urban environment (*VoLE 99*), and (c) in a moderately polluted, non-urban region (*LACE 98*). On average, the concentration of the

Figure 6-45. Averaged, normalized volatility size distributions of 25 °C ambient (dotted) and 250/280 °C conditioned (solid) aerosol particles of different origin, representing (a) vehicle-emitted 50 nm diesel particles, (b) 150 nm particles of a strongly polluted, urban region, and (c) 150 nm particles of moderately polluted, non-urban air masses. Cases b and c represent averaged results over the entire measurement campaigns.

initially selected 50 nm particles during *FORD* was approximately $4700 \pm 2600 \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The concentration of initially selected 150 nm particles during *VoLE 99* and *LACE 98* averaged $89 \pm 84 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $50 \pm 68 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, respectively. The particle concentration during the *FORD* measurements was regulated (vehicle exhaust is diluted to reduce the high number of particles emitted), whereas those during *VoLE 99* and *LACE 98* corresponded to actual atmospheric concentrations. The *FORD* measurements represent averaged results for diesel-emitted 50 nm particles at three different driving velocities (50, 70, and 100 km/h), while those of the *VoLE* and *LACE* campaigns are averaged over the entire measurement campaigns for all initially selected 150 nm particles. Depending on aerosol type (i.e., composition), the particles lose a portion of their volume due to thermal conditioning, expressed in a shift of the initial (unconditioned) size distribution towards smaller sizes. The structure of the volatility distribution of the remaining, non-volatile compounds of diesel-emitted particles at their sources is monomodal, indicating that the fraction of refractory material is evenly distributed over all particles (cf. Fig. 6-45a). These particles shrink by about 3.8 % in diameter after conditioning. Volatility distributions at a distance from combustion sources (e.g., urban, non-urban) are significantly different (cf. Fig. 6-45b and c). The associated distributions are multi-modal with a *quasi-non-volatile* mode near the initial diameter and a *partially-non-volatile* mode at smaller particle diameters. The *quasi-non-volatile* particles are characterized as consisting of mainly non-volatile material and are on average approximately 2.5 % and 3.0 % smaller in diameter than the initial 150 nm particles for urban and non-urban cases, respectively. *Partially-non-volatile* particles initially (at selected 150 nm diameter) contain a non-volatile core with varying amounts of volatile material. The *quasi-non-volatile* mode of the urban particles is more significant and the *partially-non-volatile* mode is broader than that of the non-urban particles. Since the distribution of non-volatile material depends on particle origin and subsequent atmospheric processes, the results for both aerosol types at 150 nm in cases b and c suggest different sources, mixing, transformation, and removal processes (cf. Chap. 5). Particles directly at combustion sources are expected to have the highest fraction of non-volatile material. With increasing distance to combustion sources, non-urban particles are expected to show smaller amounts of non-volatile material. The individual non-volatile aerosol fractions will be discussed in the following sub-chapter.

Note, in the above results, volatility distributions of 50 nm particles (*FORD*) are compared with those of 150 nm particles (*VoLE*, *LACE*). Volatility scans during *FORD* were performed solely at 50 nm, representing a particle size near the maximum of the particle number size distribution. Volatility size distributions of atmospheric aerosols during *VoLE* and *LACE* are not suitable for comparison since particles at 50 nm are much more volatile and the residual non-volatile portion is in the size range $< 15 \text{ nm}$ where measurement uncertainties are high. Thus, *VoLE 99* and *LACE 98* results focused on 150 nm particles. From the differences in the derived non-volatile volume fractions between 150 and 50 nm particles in *VoLE 99* and *LACE 98* which indicate that the larger particles contain a higher fraction of non-volatile material, it can be assumed that vehicle-emitted 150 nm particles might also contain a higher fraction of non-volatile material than 50 nm particles. Therefore, the results for the vehicle-emitted 50 nm particles represent at least a lower limit for the derived values.

6.4.2. Non-volatile Aerosol Fractions

The volatility size distributions of the different aerosol types of cases a, b, and c are compared by quantifying the non-volatile aerosol fractions. The resulting number and volume fractions (Φ_N and Φ_V), size ratio (Φ_{Dp}), and *quasi-non-volatile* number and volume fractions ($\varphi_{N,qnv}$ and $\varphi_{V,qnv}$) are summarized in Table 6-26. The results show that in all three cases, Φ_N is near 100 %, indicating that particle number was conserved in the heating process. This means that all individual particles contain some refractory material. Corresponding non-volatile volume is largest for particles at the source of combustion processes, averaging 88 ± 12 % (the corresponding portion in 150 nm particles is assumed to be even larger). The fraction of non-volatile material decreases with increasing distance from combustion sources, averaging 88 ± 12 % at the source, 18 ± 4 % and 11 ± 3 % in heavily polluted urban and moderately polluted rural air masses, respectively.

Case	Aerosol Type	Φ_N [%]	Φ_V [%]	Φ_{Dp} [%]	$\varphi_{N,qnv}$ [%]	$\varphi_{V,qnv}$ [%]
a	At combustion sources	102 ± 8.1	88 ± 12	96	-	-
b	Strongly polluted (urban)	102 ± 3.6	18 ± 4.0	97 (34)	14 ± 4.1	13 ± 3.7
c	Moderately polluted	98 ± 2.1	11 ± 2.9	97 (27)	6.1 ± 1.9	5.8 ± 2.1

Table 6-26. Averaged non-volatile number fractions Φ_N , volume fractions Φ_V , size ratio Φ_{Dp} (the number in bracket refers to the size ratio of the major *partially-non-volatile* mode), and *quasi-non-volatile* number and volume fractions $\varphi_{N,qnv}$ and $\varphi_{V,qnv}$ of different aerosol types with associated standard deviations.

Due to the large non-volatile portion in aerosol particles at the diesel source, Φ_N can not be distinguished between *quasi-* and *partially-non-volatile*. The fraction of particles that consists almost completely of non-volatile material ($\varphi_{N,qnv}$) is larger for urban particles, averaging about 14 %, and decreases to 6 % in the case of non-urban particles in less polluted regions. This shows that the *quasi-non-volatile* portion increases with increasing proximity to combustion sources.

Chemical analysis of atmospheric submicrometer particles (the chemical composition in case a was not investigated) shows that urban particles (case b) contain a large fraction of nitrate (i.e., 31 %) compared to non-urban particles (case c) (i.e., 2.3 %). In contrast, the fraction of sulfate is considerably smaller for urban particles (16 % versus 31 %, respectively). In both cases, the total carbon fraction (OC + EC) is equal, amounting to 22 – 23 % of the total mass. However, the fraction of OC is three times as high as the fraction of EC for urban particles, whereas for non-urban particles the OC fraction is about the same as the EC fraction. The correlation between the VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fraction $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$ of 150 nm particles and chemically-derived non-volatile carbon mass fractions Φ_M of particles in the 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm size range is obvious and confirms that a large portion of the non-volatile material is comprised of non-volatile carbon. Since the density of the non-volatile material is unknown, the aerodynamic particle size range corresponding to 150 nm particles could be both, 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm. In the

strongly polluted case, on average 35 and 19 % of the TOC of particles in the size range 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm, respectively, can be attributed to less volatile OC. The less volatile OC fraction is determined at temperatures above the maximum conditioning temperatures of the VTMDA and is, therefore, possibly missed by the VTMDA technique. The corresponding fractions for particles in the moderately polluted case are not available, they are presumably lower since the total organic carbon fraction a smaller part of the total carbon. The ratio between both quantities, Φ_M and Φ_V , is expressed as density parameter $\vartheta(\rho)$ (cf. Eqn. 6-5). Table 6-27 lists the different values for $\vartheta(\rho)$ obtained for comparing $\Phi_{V(150nm)}$ with Φ_M of the size ranges 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm, respectively. The density parameter is distinguished between $\vartheta(\rho)$ and $\vartheta(\rho_{EC})$, representing the

Aerosol Type	50 – 140 nm		140 – 420 nm	
	$\vartheta(\rho)$	$\vartheta(\rho_{EC})$	$\vartheta(\rho)$	$\vartheta(\rho_{EC})$
Strongly polluted (<i>VoLE 99</i>)	0.95 ± 0.29	0.44 ± 0.28	0.61 ± 0.16	0.39 ± 0.22
Moderately polluted (<i>LACE 98</i>)	-	1.3 ± 0.61	-	1.2 ± 0.34

Table 6-27. Average results of the density parameter $\vartheta(\rho)$, representing the ratio of the carbon mass fractions (Φ_M) (of both impactor size ranges, 50/140 nm and 140/420 nm) to the non-volatile volume fraction Φ_V of 150 nm particles for different aerosol types. $\vartheta(\rho)$ connotes that the carbon mass fraction Φ_M includes EC and the portion of less volatile organic carbon (i.e., being the equivalent to the VTMDA-derived, refractory fraction), the index ‘EC’ indicates EC carbon mass fractions only.

ratio of Φ_M and $\Phi_{M,EC}$ to Φ_V , respectively⁷. Φ_M includes the mass fraction of elemental plus less volatile organic carbon (determined at 280 °C), $\Phi_{M,EC}$ indicates solely elemental carbon. Therefore, $\vartheta(\rho)$ is always larger than $\vartheta(\rho_{EC})$ (note that Φ_M is only available during *VoLE 99*). Overall, $\vartheta(\rho_{EC})$ is larger during *VoLE 99* than during *LACE 98*. This could be due to a different density of the non-volatile material of both aerosol types. Furthermore, a larger OC/EC ratio during *VoLE 99* compared to *LACE 98* might imply a larger value of Φ_V (due to a potentially higher fraction of less volatile organic carbon included in the VTMDA residuals) which could decrease $\vartheta(\rho_{EC})$. Prominent differences of $\vartheta(\rho)$ between the different size ranges do not exist, although the filter-derived mass fractions derived for the smaller particle size range are associated with higher uncertainties due to the small mass. A quantification of Φ_M versus Φ_V remains difficult since both represent different parameters derived from different methods. Despite the uncertainties (e.g., due to quasi-monodisperse particles versus particle size ranges, on-line versus filter sampling, volume versus mass fractions, non-volatile versus non-volatile carbon), the correlation between both quantities confirms the quality of the volatility measurements, which is furthermore supported by the results of the black carbon measurements during *LACE 98* at the PSAP. Morphological results emphasize the carbonaceous character of the refractory material.

⁷ As a reminder, $\vartheta(\rho) = \Phi_M(OC+EC)/\Phi_V$ and $\vartheta(\rho_{EC}) = \Phi_M(EC)/\Phi_V$.

The volatility results show an increasing fraction of non-volatile material with increasing proximity to combustion sources. Directly at a source (producing diesel particles), predominantly non-volatile compounds are found. The different types of volatility distributions of particles in strongly and moderately polluted air indicate the possibility of different sources, mixing and transformation processes, relating to the different types of aerosols. The VTDMA is not only capable of determining non-volatile aerosol compounds but also to differentiate the particles between those that are *quasi-non-volatile* and only *partially-non-volatile*. The volatility analyzer, therefore, is a valuable tool for investigating the carbonaceous nature of the submicrometer aerosol, particularly in the light of the uncertainties associated with conventional sampling and analytical methods. It can be deployed in polluted regions where high non-volatile aerosol fractions are present. Even in less polluted areas where associated non-volatile fractions are small, reliable results with a high temporal resolution for the size-segregated aerosol can be derived.

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This dissertation focuses on the development, calibration, and application of a volatility analyzer to investigate size-segregated submicrometer aerosol particles with respect to their non-volatile composition in differently polluted environments.

To date, a number of experimental methods employ the volatility technique to determine the non-volatile fraction, i.e., non-volatile carbon of submicrometer aerosol particles (Cadle and Groblicki, 1982; Huntzicker et al., 1982; Wolff et al., 1982; Cachier et al., 1989; Chow et al., 1993; VDI-Richtlinie 2465, 1997). Due to the lack of mass of submicrometer aerosols, these conventional (chemical) methods are often combined with particle collection over long sampling times (on the order of hours or days). This does not allow to infer size-segregated chemical information on short times scales, being essential in rapidly changing environments.

Development and Calibration of the Volatility Analyzer

The present Volatility Tandem Differential Mobility Analyzer (VTDMA) was designed to investigate non-volatile compounds of airborne particles with high temporal resolution. The instrument selects quasi-monodisperse submicrometer particles from polydisperse particles, and subsequently evaporates their volatile compounds by exposing them to different conditioning temperatures between 25 °C and 300 °C (non-volatile aerosol compounds are characterized as being thermally refractory to predefined heating temperatures). The change in particle size is recorded by measuring the resulting number size distribution of the non-volatile material. A deconvolution of the measured size distribution is necessary to retrieve the actual size distribution and is realized by an advanced data inversion algorithm developed by Voutilainen et al. (2000). The inverted results can be parameterized in terms of number and volume fractions, representing the total number and volume of the non-volatile particles with respect to the initially selected particles.

The VTDMA was calibrated in the laboratory to correct the measured data for particle losses in the sampling lines due to diffusion and thermophoresis. The VTDMA transport efficiency decreases with decreasing particle size and with increasing temperature. For example, at ambient temperatures (25 °C) 96 % of 150 nm particles are being transmitted through the system, whereas at 300 °C the corresponding value decreases to 81 %. Depending on conditioning temperature, the transport efficiency decreases to 50 % for particles between 10 and 20 nm diameter. This suggests that VTDMA measurements of particle sizes below 15 nm are associated with high uncertainties.

The laboratory measurements furthermore investigated the volatility of artificial test aerosols of known composition in the VTDMA. For particles sizes up to 150 nm characteristic conditioning temperatures of 80 °C, 180 °C, and 280 °C were established. At 80 °C a large portion of sulfuric acid is volatile (as well as, in particular, the more volatile nitrate and presumably some volatile organic compounds). At 180 °C, all sulfate compounds including the neutralized species

ammonium sulfate ((NH₄)₂SO₄) and ammonium bisulfate (NH₄HSO₄) are completely evaporated. Differences in the volatile behavior of (NH₄)₂SO₄ and NH₄HSO₄ can not be deduced. These results of the volatility of quasi-monodisperse particles are novel since the derived volatility temperatures are considerably lower than those found in previous studies for heating an entire particle size distribution (Clarke et al., 1987; Pinnick et al., 1987; Rood et al., 1987; O'Dowd and Smith, 1993; Hudson and Da, 1996; Smith and O'Dowd, 1996). At 280 °C additional volatile compounds (in atmospheric aerosols), e.g., the more volatile organic carbon are likely to be evaporated in the VTDMA system (Novakov et al., 1997). The remaining 'refractory' compounds are considered non-volatile, encompassing non-volatile carbon and possibly some less volatile organic compounds. Other non-volatile material, e.g., sea salt, crustal material, or fly ash are considered minor in the particle size range up to 150 nm.

Application of the Volatility Analyzer to Atmospheric Aerosol Particles

In the atmosphere, the distribution of non-volatile material within aerosol particles varies considerably with region and time and primarily depends on its sources (i.e., combustion processes in the case of non-volatile carbon). However, due to mixing processes of aerosol populations of different sources and transformation processes (e.g., condensation, coagulation), the distribution of non-volatile material of aged aerosols is altered substantially, depending on the number of sources and the distance to the sources.

In order to investigate the volatile behavior of different aerosols, volatility measurements were performed in environments of varying distance to combustion sources, anticipated to contain different amounts of non-volatile material.

- At first, a volatility study directly at combustion sources was conducted (*FORD 98*), encompassing measurements of emitted particles of the following vehicles types: diesel cars, a direction injection vehicle, gasoline-driven vehicles, and a natural gas-driven vehicle. The results show that the non-volatile fractions of emitted particles depend on vehicle, fuel type, and operating conditions.

Non-volatile size distributions of the 50 nm diesel-emitted particles appear monomodal, indicating that for each test condition all selected particles contain the same amount of non-volatile material. Among all tested vehicles, diesel-emitted particles contain the highest amount of non-volatile material, with volume fractions ranging between 75 and 100 %. The non-volatile number and volume fractions increase with increasing velocity (i.e., engine revolution) and decreasing air-fuel ratio. The number of diesel-emitted particles remains approximately 100 % after conditioning, indicating that all particles contain non-volatile cores.

In contrast to the diesel-emitted particles, only 4 to 8 % of the particle volume emitted from the direct injection vehicle represents non-volatile material, suggesting that the particles mainly consist of volatile compounds. About 50 % of the initial particles evaporate completely during conditioning.

Particles emitted from gasoline- and natural gas-driven vehicles show a different chemical and physical behavior. Large aerosol fractions evaporate within the VTDMA system already at

ambient conditions, possibly due to partial volatilization of semi-volatile compounds in the clean sheath air of the differential mobility analyzers (DMAs). This effect is significant since it is likely to occur in DMA-based particle size distribution measurements as well, where it is not detectable. It is a measurement artifact which leads to a shift of the measured number size distributions towards smaller particle diameters. For volatility distributions this effect implies that the ambient particles are no longer unconditioned and non-volatile fractions can not be quantified exactly, representing only upper limits. Compared to diesel vehicles, particles emitted from gasoline-driven vehicles contain a considerably smaller fraction of non-volatile material. Associated non-volatile volume fractions are estimated to be lower than 11 - 33 %, increasing with decreasing air-fuel-ratio. Rich mixtures reveal the highest amount of non-volatile material, as expected. Unexpectedly, the corresponding refractory material in particles emitted from natural gas-driven vehicles is comparable to that of rich gasoline-emitted particles, being (maximally) 30 %.

- The second series of VTDMA measurements was performed in a strongly polluted, urban environment during a cold winter period (*VoLE 99*). The structure of the measured volatility distributions of 150 nm particles throughout the entire campaign are very similar, being multimodal with two significant modes: one mode near the initially selected particle diameter, representing *quasi-non-volatile* particles, and a further, broad mode located at smaller particle diameters comprising initial *partially-non-volatile* particles. The non-volatile number fraction remains constant after conditioning, suggesting that all initial particles contained non-volatile cores. The total non-volatile volume varies between 12 and 24 % and averages about 18 %. Approximately 14 % of the initially selected particles can be attributed to the *quasi-non-volatile* particles, comprising more than half of the refractory volume. The highest non-volatile volume fractions coincide with time periods of highest aerosol concentration and coldest temperatures. Morphological analysis indicates that the refractory particles are carbonaceous because of their typical structure, representing spheres as well as chain aggregates or clusters.

Concurrent measurements of chemical particle composition show that the total carbon mass in submicrometer particles comprises on average about 23 %. About 75 % of the total carbon is organic, with the more volatile organic carbon portion constituting the majority of the total organic carbon. VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fractions (of 150 nm particles) and sample-derived non-volatile carbon mass fractions (representing EC plus the less volatile OC portion) of corresponding particle size ranges (50/140 nm, 140/420 nm) obviously correlate. Remaining differences are presumably method-based.

- Lastly, a volatility study was carried out in a non-urban region to investigate the volatile behavior of particles in a moderately polluted region (*LACE 98*). The results from VTDMA measurements reveal that typical distributions of non-volatile compounds at 150 nm are also multimodal, with a small *quasi-non-volatile* mode near the initial diameter and another, more substantial *partially-non-volatile* mode at small diameters. The total number of particles does not change upon heating, indicating that all particles contained non-volatile cores. The total volume of the refractory material varies between 8 % and 21 % and averages 11 % over the

entire measurement campaign. About 6 % of all 150 nm particles are considered *quasi-non-volatile*.

Results from chemical measurements show that the total carbon comprises 22 % of the submicrometer aerosol mass. About half of the total carbon is organic. Total organic carbon was not separated between more and less volatile organic carbon as done during *VoLE 99*. The comparison shows that VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fractions for 150 nm particles and sample-derived non-volatile EC mass fractions correlate well with particles in the size range 140/420 nm (most of the EC mass fractions of the size range 50/140 nm are close to the detection limit and are, therefore, uncertain). Less volatile organic carbon identified as part of the non-volatile material by the VTDMA method is presumably smaller during *LACE 98* than during *VoLE 99* since the OC/EC ratio is smaller during *LACE 98*.

A classification of the VTDMA-derived non-volatile volume fractions with respect to different aerosol types shows the following trend: continentally-influenced marine particles hold the least amount of non-volatile material, increasing with increasing pollution level, while eastern-continentally-influenced aerosol particles (i.e., from areas of enhanced industrial activity) have the highest non-volatile volume fractions. An influence of the city of Berlin can not be observed. A correlation between measured aerosol absorption coefficients (derived from PSAP measurements) and non-volatile volume fractions confirms the predominant carbonaceous nature of the VTDMA-derived non-volatile material.

In conclusion, the volatility results from *FORD 98*, *VoLE 99*, and *LACE 98* show an increasing fraction of non-volatile material with increasing proximity to combustion sources. High amounts of non-volatile compounds are found directly at a source (producing diesel particles), averaging 88 % by volume for 50 nm particles. Away from sources, the non-volatile portion decreases considerably. Corresponding non-volatile volume fraction for 150 nm particles is on average 18 % and 11 % for urban and non-urban particles, respectively. In all three cases, the number of particles remains constant after heating which demonstrates that all particles contain non-volatile cores. Latter results are particularly important for investigating mechanisms of secondary particle formation (by nucleation and subsequent condensation). The structures of the non-volatile volatility distributions of particles in a strongly and moderately polluted environment reflect the potential influence of different sources, mixing and transformation processes. The *quasi-non-volatile* aerosol fraction is larger during *VoLE 99*, averaging about 14 %, and decreases to 6 % during *LACE 98*. This suggests that the *quasi-non-volatile* portion increases with increasing proximity to combustion sources. A quantitative comparison between the results of VTDMA and the chemical volatility method (thermodesorption) remains difficult since both are based on different techniques (e.g., comparing volume with mass fractions, quasi-monodisperse particles with entire particle size ranges, non-volatile compounds with non-volatile carbon). Nonetheless, the correlation of the results suggest that a large portion of the non-volatile material is non-volatile carbon. The less volatile organic carbon compounds are likely not to be evaporated in the VTDMA system.

This research work shows that the VTDMA emerges as a valuable instrument for the investigation of non-volatile compounds of submicrometer aerosols. The instrument can be deployed in areas

where high non-volatile aerosol fractions are present (i.e., at combustion sources) as well as in less polluted areas where overall particle concentrations and associated non-volatile fractions are small. The VTDMA technique of sampling airborne particles is of great advantage for the in-situ investigation of quasi-monodisperse aerosol particles. The investigation of a range of particle sizes delivers valuable information about the distribution and mixing of non-volatile material in polydisperse aerosol populations. Size-segregated information can be obtained of particles having masses too small to be sampled with conventional methods with a sufficient temporal resolution. Therefore, the study of non-volatile particle compounds can be pursued in rapidly changing environments.

Outlook

A valuable extension of this work will be the performance of comprehensive volatility studies in the laboratory using a series of artificial aerosols of pre-defined composition (internal and/or external mixtures of elementary and different organic carbon compounds). This would allow to refine the interpretation of the volatile behavior of atmospheric aerosol particles as well as to draw conclusions about possible transformation processes. In future work, the VTDMA will prove as valuable tool for studying the physico-chemical processes of fine aerosol particles and to provide necessary model input parameters to assess the impact of non-volatile aerosol compounds on climate and human health.

APPENDIX A: VTDMA - INSTRUMENTAL COMPONENTS

A.1. Bipolar Diffusion Charger

A bipolar diffusion charger is used to obtain charge equilibrium for aerosol particles prior to entering the differential mobility analyzer (DMA, cf. Appendix A.2). It contains a 2.0 millicurie Krypton-85 radioactive beta-source producing positive and negative gaseous ions to charge the particles by bipolar diffusion. A schematic of the neutralizer is shown in Figure A-1.

Figure A-1. Schematic of the bipolar diffusion charger.

The bipolar charge distribution of negatively and positively charged ions is non-symmetric, with the negatively charged ions being more abundant due to their higher electrical mobility. The charge level of the particles is calculated according to the approximated Fuchs equilibrium charge distribution (Wiedensohler, 1989) which is illustrated in Figure A-2. The fraction of singly- and doubly-charged particles increases with increasing particle diameter and multiply-charged particles become significant for diameters larger than about 80 to 100 nm.

Figure A-2. Bipolar charge distribution of particles obtained in a bipolar diffusion charger (in %).

A.2. Differential Mobility Analyzer

The differential mobility analyzer (DMA) is used to classify particles according to their electrical mobility. Before entering the DMA the particles are charged in a bipolar diffusion charger as described in Appendix A.1. A schematic diagram of the DMA is shown in Figure A-3. It consists of two concentric cylinders, resembling a cylindrical capacitor, with an adjustable voltage applied to the inner rod and the outer housing being grounded. Particles entering the analyzer move in a laminar flow of particle-free sheath air through the DMA.

Figure A-3. Schematic of the differential mobility analyzer.

During their passage through the DMA the negatively charged particles are deflected toward the inner cylinder by the imposed electric field. The electrical mobility of a particle is calculated from

$$Z_p = \frac{\varepsilon \cdot C(D_p)}{3\pi\mu D_p}, \quad (A-1)$$

with D_p being the particle diameter, ε the elementary unit of charge, $C(D_p)$ the Cunningham slip correction factor, and μ the air viscosity. Only particles with electrical mobilities within a narrow range ΔZ_p leave the DMA through an exit slit. The midpoint mobility is related to geometry and flow rates of the DMA (Knutson and Whitby, 1975), as

$$Z_p = \frac{Q - \frac{1}{2}(Q_s + Q_a)}{2\pi Ul} \ln \frac{r_2}{r_1}, \quad (\text{A-2})$$

The mobility half-width is given by

$$\Delta Z_p = \frac{(Q_s + Q_a)}{2\pi Ul} \ln \frac{r_2}{r_1}. \quad (\text{A-3})$$

Q_s and Q_a denote the sample and aerosol flow rate, Q is the sum of aerosol and sheath air flow rate, U represents the electrode voltage. l , r_1 , and r_2 are the distance between entrance and exit boundary, radius of inner and of outer electrode, respectively. The probability of a particle within the mobility band ΔZ_p passing through the sampling slot is defined by the DMA transfer function Ω , assuming laminar flow and neglecting Brownian motion (Knutson and Whitby, 1975). The width of the transfer function Ω is controlled by the ratio of the aerosol to sheath air flow rate. In the case of an ideal transfer function the aerosol and sample flow rate are equal and the ratio of aerosol to sheath air flow rate is 0.1, with Ω representing a triangular shape.

In the VTDMA two DMAs are used, a first DMA-1 for the selection of specific particle diameters from a given particle size distribution, and a second DMA-2 to determine resulting size distributions of conditioned aerosol particles. Both DMAs used in this work are the Vienna-type (short) according to the design presented by Winklmayr et al. (1991) with geometric dimensions of $l = 11.0$ cm, $r_1 = 25.0$ cm, and $r_2 = 33.5$ cm. The flow rates of DMA-1 were adjusted to 20/2 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for sheath air/aerosol flow rate, and to 10/1 and 5/1 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for the DMA-2, respectively. The ratio of DMA-2 was altered from the initial 10/1 to 5/1 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to enlarge the scanned mobility size range without decreasing time resolution.

A.3. Condensation Particle Counter

The particle concentration is determined with a condensation particle counter (CPC, TSI Model 3010, St. Paul, MN). A schematic of the CPC is shown in Figure A-4. The aerosols are drawn into the CPC at a prefixed flow rate (nominally 1 $\text{l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) where they first enter a heated chamber saturated with butanol vapor. In a following cooled tube (condenser) the supersaturation reaches a certain level causing the alcohol vapor to condense onto the particles which grow to a detectable size. They are subsequently directed through a focused laser beam which scatters the light onto a photo detector. The signals are registered as analog or digital pulses which reflect the particle concentration with respect to flow rate and time. The particle counters used in the VTDMA were repeatedly calibrated to determine their instrument-specific counting efficiencies.

Figure A-4. Schematic of the condensation particle counter.

The calibrations were performed with monodisperse silver (Ag) aerosol particles generated in a tube furnace. After selection in an ultrafine DMA, the monodisperse particles were diluted with particle-free air to obtain constant number concentrations at approximately 1000 cm^{-3} . The calibration was carried out utilizing two identical ultrafine CPCs (UCPC, TSI Model 3025, St. Paul, MN) for reference. The UCPCs were themselves calibrated with an electrometer. The resulting CPC efficiencies were fitted with an exponential two-parameter fit. The averaged efficiency curves for the two CPCs used in the VTDMA of the January 1997 and June 1998 calibration measurements at a flow rate of $1.0 \text{ l}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ and standard pressure are displayed in Figure A-5. The 50 % counting efficiencies were found to be about 12 nm. All particle concentration measurements presented in this study were corrected for pertinent counting efficiencies.

Figure A-5. Counting efficiencies of the CPCs 3010 obtained from the calibration measurements at a flow rate of $1.0 \text{ l}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ and standard pressure.

A.4. Electrostatic Particle Sampler

The Electrostatic Particle Sampler (EPS) is used to sample aerosol particles by electrostatic deposition. A schematic of an EPS is sketched in Figure A-6. Charged particles (cf. Appendix A.1) are passed over an electrode with an applied voltage up to several thousand Volts (the outer case of the EPS is connected to ground). According to electrical mobility and velocity of the particles and electrical field they are exposed to particles of a particular size are deposited on sampling grids located on the charged plate.

Figure A-6. Schematic of Electrostatic Particle Sampler (top view).

The voltage U necessary to deposit particles of a given mobility Z_p , i.e., size, is calculated according to the theory of a parallel-plate capacitor, as

$$U = \frac{Q \cdot d}{Z_p \cdot b \cdot l}. \quad (\text{A-4})$$

Q denotes the aerosol flow rate, d the height of the entering particles from the plate, b is the width of the plate, and l indicates the distance from the beginning of the plate to the spot where the particles are deposited. The size of the particles is derived from their electrical mobility, assuming Stokes-equivalent spheres and singly-charged particles. The voltage necessary to deposit the particles on the grids is a strong function of their velocity (cf. Fig. A-7). Since the maximum voltage in the EPS is limited to about 3.5 kV (due to short circuiting), the maximum flow rate becomes very small. To extract particles, e.g., of about 145 and 47 nm, the flow rates for the chosen EPS design were adjusted to 0.1 and 0.5 l min^{-1} , requiring voltages of about 3 and 2 kV for the electrode of the EPS, respectively.

Figure A-7. Calculated EPS voltage as a function of particle size and aerosol flow rate Q . The dotted lines denote selected particles at 145 and 47 nm, respectively.

APPENDIX B: TEMPERATURE PROFILE AND EVAPORATION OF PARTICLES IN THE CONDITIONING TUBE

The temperature field inside the conditioning tube was simulated by a 2D model (COMPACT Vers. 4.0). The boundary conditions in the model were adjusted to the geometries of the heating path (length of 395 mm, radius of 2 mm), an air velocity of $v = 1.33 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ corresponding to the aerosol flow rate of $1 \text{ l}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, an entrance temperature T_{initial} of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and a wall temperature T_{wall} of $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ ($300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ represents the maximum conditioning temperature). The resulting temperature profile of the laminar aerosol flow inside the heating column is shown in Figure B-1. After entering

Figure B-1. Modeled temperature field of laminar air flow through VTDMA heating column, assuming an initial air temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a wall temperature of $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The location of the thermocouple is indicated at 36 mm distance from the end of the tube.

the conditioning path, the aerosol is heated from the wall boundary to the center by conduction. The temperature field is symmetric with respect to the center line. About halfway through the tube at approximately 210 mm, the aerosol particles are exposed to a homogeneous temperature field where they attain their final temperature T_{max} . The total residence time τ_t of the particles inside the heating tube is 300 ms to the given geometries and aerosol flow rate. The residence time τ_{max} of the particles at elevated temperatures T_{max} ($\approx T_{\text{wall}}$) can be derived as 140 ms. For other selected wall temperatures of, e.g., 80 and $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the point at which a uniform constant temperature is achieved is accordingly after 210 and 250 mm, corresponding to τ_{max} of 110 and 140 ms, respectively (not shown in Fig. B-1). The evaporation rate of H_2SO_4 particles in the heating tube was modeled with the aerosol dynamics model MADMAcS II which is adapted for laminar flow diffusion processes (Wilck, 1998). Input to the model are the above calculated temperature profile inside the tube (with

a wall temperature of 300 °C), an aerosol velocity of $1.33 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, and an initial aerosol concentration of $n = 10$ and 100 cm^{-3} , respectively. The calculations were performed for particles sizes between 35 and 150 nm and at different distances from the tube center. 150 nm is the maximum diameter of particles investigated. The results for the initial 150 nm particles are displayed in Figure B-2. It is obvious from the results that the particles evaporate rapidly in the elevated temperature field, even

Figure B-2. Modeled evaporation of sulfuric acid particles of 150 nm initial diameter as a function of distance from the entrance of the heating path (in mm), time (in ms), and distance from tube center (in mm).

before the final temperature is achieved (the abscissa is plotted logarithmically in order to resolve the rapid evaporation process). As expected, the particles in the center of the tube (radius $r = 0 \text{ mm}$) evaporate slower compared to those near the wall since the temperature is lower in the center for a given distance from the entrance. Particles close to the wall ($r = 2 \text{ mm}$) are evaporated after approximately 13 mm from the tube entrance, corresponding to a evaporation time τ_{vap} of 10 ms and a local temperature of 113 °C. Particles at $r = 1 \text{ mm}$ and $r = 0 \text{ mm}$ are vaporized after 26 and 43 mm, respectively, corresponding to a time τ_{vap} of 20 and 32 ms, and a local temperature of 118 and 120 °C. The results are identical for initial aerosol concentrations of 10 and 100 cm^{-3} . Particles smaller than 150 nm evaporate even faster, i.e., 50 nm and 35 nm particles encompass evaporation times between 8 and 26 ms, and between 7 and 25 ms respectively, depending on the distance from the center (not shown in the figure). The results demonstrate that the residence time in the heating path is sufficient for the complete evaporating of sulfuric acid particles.

APPENDIX C: INVERSION OF VTDMA DATA

The initial inversion algorithm ('*TDMAFIT*') was developed by Stolzenburg et al. (Stolzenburg and McMurry, 1988; Rader and McMurry, 1986) that uses a least square fitting procedure to fit theoretical TDMA transfer functions to the raw, measured distribution, assuming a unimodal or bimodal (Gaussian) mobility distribution upstream of DMA-2. The deconvoluted solution is hereby described by the parameters number fraction (number of particles detected by DMA-2 compared to DMA-1), growth factor (ratio of midpoint diameters (i.e., mode average diameter) for given mode before and after conditioning), and a correction factor for the width of size distribution (e.g., concerning diffusion). Since the algorithm allows to describe the mobility distribution of the conditioned particles with only one or two modes, it was not sufficient for VTDMA measurements which predominantly reveal a multimodal distribution.

Stratmann et al. (Stratmann et al., 1997) suggested a new inversion algorithm that disregards the actual structure of the distribution $n_1'(D_p)$ after the conditioning process and enables to resolve the features of the resulting distribution in greater detail and with a higher resolution: In a first step of this procedure the measured number concentration $N_2(D_p)$ is interpolated and smoothed by applying a least square cubic spline fit and Fourier low pass filter. Subsequently, the distributions are discretized with the DMA-2 transfer function Ω_2 and described by a set of linear equations with respect to the actual distribution $n_2(D_p)$ upstream of DMA-2. In a third step the deconvoluted solution of the measured distribution is iteratively calculated in discrete form. This procedure represents a significant improvement of the initial *TDMAFIT*. For the VTDMA measurements, however, this algorithm emerged to be still inadequate. The adoption of high temperatures in the conditioning path of the VTDMA lead to broad, multimodal number size distributions since the aerosol particles lost various fractions of their mass during evaporation. The scanning of a broader size range, however, decreased the size resolution in order to achieve a high temporal resolution. Consequently, certain modal features were disregarded or overemphasized (cf. Fig. C-1), causing incorrect solutions. Furthermore, small errors in measurement lead to large errors in the solution.

Figure C-1. 'True' size distribution (I) and effects of over-smoothing (IIa) and over-emphasis (IIb) during inversion, leading to incorrect solutions for existing features. The circles denote the measurement points, the lines are the corresponding deconvoluted distributions.

APPENDIX D: THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS OF DIFFUSIONAL AND THERMOPHORETIC DEPOSITION

During their transport through the VTDMA system aerosol particles are lost to the walls due to diffusion and thermophoresis. Particle losses caused by gravitational, inertial, turbulent, and electrostatic deposition can be excluded due to the small size of the sampled particles, due to laminar flow conditions inside the system, and due to electrically conductive sampling lines (= stainless steel) used, respectively. The transport tubes are designed with minimal distance and number of bends. The flow through the sampling lines is maintained laminar, holding a Reynold number of $R_e = 350$ (R_e smaller than 2300 is considered the laminar flow regime). The Reynold number is derived from

$$R_e = \frac{\rho_{air} v d}{\eta_{air}}, \quad (D-1)$$

with ρ_{air} being the density of air ($= 1.21 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), v is the flow velocity ($= 1.33 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), d is the diameter of the sampling line ($= 4\cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}$), and η_{air} represents the viscosity of air ($= 1.83\cdot 10^{-5} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), all at 296.2 K and 1010.0 mb.

Diffusional Deposition

Diffusional losses in the sampling lines are caused by the a movement of small particles from high particle concentrations in the aerosol flow to low particle concentrations near the wall of the tubes where they are deposited. The diffusional particle deposition in a laminar flow regime depends on particle size, flow velocity, and the geometries of the sampling lines. The transport efficiency η_{diff} is calculated as (Willeke and Baron, 1993):

$$\eta_{diff} = 1 - 2.56\xi^{2/3} + 1.2\xi + 0.77\xi^{4/3} \quad (D-2)$$

for $\xi < 0.02$, and

$$\eta_{diff} = 0.819 \exp(-3.657\xi) + 0.097 \exp(-22.3\xi) + 0.032 \exp(-57\xi) \quad (D-3)$$

for $\xi > 0.02$, with ξ being

$$\xi = \frac{\pi D_B L}{Q}. \quad (D-4)$$

The transport efficiency is, therefore, solely a function of ξ , where D_B is the particle 'Brownian' diffusion coefficient, L the length of the tube considered, and Q the flow rate through the tube. The particle diffusion coefficient D_B is inferred from

$$D_B = kTB, \quad (D-5)$$

where the particle dynamic mobility B is defined as

$$B = \frac{C_c}{3\pi\eta_{air}D_p}, \quad (D-6)$$

with the Cunningham slip correction factor C_c

$$C_c = 1 + \frac{\lambda}{D_p} (2.514 + 0.8\exp(-0.55\frac{D_p}{\lambda})). \quad (D-7)$$

k is the Boltzmann constant ($= 1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), T the absolute air temperature (in K), η_{air} the viscosity of air, D_p the particle diameter, and λ the mean free path. Figure D-1 illustrates the transport efficiency η_{diff} for particle diffusion in a laminar air flow, derived from the above equations, as a function of Reynold number (Eqn. D-1). The corresponding diffusion coefficient is plotted on the secondary ordinate. The results are shown for actual conditions at ambient air temperature of 296.2 K, an inner tube diameter of 4 mm, and a total tube length of the aerosol flow through the VTDMA of 3 m. It is obvious that below diameters of about 100 nm, particles are increasingly affected by diffusion, leading to a decreasing transport efficiency η_{diff} . Furthermore, an increasing η_{diff} for increasing Reynold numbers can be observed ($Re = 350$ corresponds to the

Figure D-1. Transport efficiency in sampling lines due to diffusional deposition of particles in laminar air flow as a function of particle diameter and Reynold number. The diffusion coefficients are shown on the secondary y-axis.

flow conditions inside the VTDMA). In the VTDMA-effective particle size range ($10 \text{ nm} < D_p < 200 \text{ nm}$), diffusional deposition leads to a transport efficiency between 80 and 100 % (with the corresponding diffusion coefficient ranging from 5.42 to $0.07 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$).

Thermophoretic Deposition

Thermophoretic deposition is caused by the temperature gradient in the sampling line. Thermophoresis is effective within the VTDMA heating path where the walls are heated up to $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This temperature gradient acts to move the particles away from the walls towards the center of the tube. However, downstream of the heating path the same mechanism causes the heated air to move from the center of the tube towards the cooler tube walls. Therefore, in laminar tube flow the transport efficiency due to thermophoresis becomes complex since thermophoretic processes can act in the same as well as in the opposite direction as the diffusional processes. Thus, the total deposition (sum of diffusional and thermophoretic deposition) is decreased inside the heating path, whereas it is increased immediately behind the heating path (causing the particles to move towards the tube walls). The calculation of η_{thermo} is complicated by the fact that the thermal conductivity of aerosol particles is usually unknown due to their unknown chemical constituents or complex compositional structure (agglomerates, mixing state, etc.).

The overall transport efficiency due to diffusion and thermophoresis of aerosol particles in the VTDMA system is not easily obtained by theoretical considerations and is, therefore, retrieved by experimental calibration studies. The VTDMA calibration is performed for the particle diameters of interest and temperatures in the heating path.

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